

Funded by
the European Union

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D1.2 – Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights Handbook

Author(s):	Rada Stoilova
Leading Partner:	LIF
Version - Status:	V1.0
Submission Date:	24/12/2024
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message: ©iDriving Consortium, 2024-2027. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Report information

Purpose of the Report	The first iteration of the Data and IPR Management Handbook aims to ensure the legal and ethical implementation of all activities envisioned in the project, based on the GA.		
Relevant Work package:	WPI		
Relevant Task:	T1.4 & T1.5		
Contributors:	CERTH, SIMAVI		
Next version Title:	Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights Handbook v.2	Next version Date:	31/12/2025
Official Submission Date:	31/12/2024	Actual Submission Date:	24/12/2024

ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU’s goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES

6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES
7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
9	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO
13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
16	GRAD KARLOVAC	COK	HR
17	MOBILYSIS SARL	MOBILYSIS SARL	CH

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Description
0.1	07/10/2024	Rada Stoilova	LIF	First version of ToC
0.2	08/11/2024	Rada Stoilova	LIF	First version
0.3	15/11/2024	Nikolaos Dourvas	CERTH	Review of first version
0.4	04/12/2024	Rada Stoilova	LIF	Second version
0.5	16/12/2024		SIMAVI	Review of second version
0.6	17/12/2024	Mpampis Chatzimalis, Martha Papadopoulou, Pantelis Velanas	ACCELI	Formatting, editing review and quality check.
0.7	20/12/2024	Rada Stoilova	LIF	Final version
1.0	24/12/2024	Nikolaos Dourvas	CERTH	Submission to EC

Executive summary

The first iteration of the Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Handbook is a key document for the iDriving project, providing crucial guidelines for data and intellectual property management among project partners. This initial version is based on the Grant Agreement (GA), and it establishes a foundation for continuous development, ensuring alignment with the project's objectives and ethical standards. Future versions will incorporate new insights to enhance the handbook's effectiveness and compliance with the iDriving project's goals.

This document emphasises the importance of effective practices in ensuring that all partners follow established protocols for data management and intellectual property protection, while fostering collaboration and innovation. It clearly defines responsibilities for data collection, sharing, storage, and usage, aiming to protect proprietary information and enable smooth communication among stakeholders.

The handbook further covers the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) within the project, highlighting the legal and ethical considerations involved. This includes adhering to relevant regulations and standards to ensure AI applications align with the project's goals and respect participants' rights and privacy.

Finally, the document addresses ethical considerations related to human participation in the iDriving project. It outlines best practices for engaging with participants, focusing on informed consent, transparency, and the protection of personal data. By addressing these ethical aspects, the handbook aims to maintain the project's integrity and foster trust and collaboration among all partners.

Table of Contents

ABOUT iDRIVING	2
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope	10
1.2 Document Structure	10
2 Legal Framework	11
2.1 The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union	11
2.2 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	11
2.2.1 Key Data Protection Rules for Partners	12
2.2.1.1 GDPR Principles	12
2.2.1.2 Ensuring Protection of Data Subjects' Rights	15
2.2.1.3 Additional Internal Rules for Partners	18
2.2.1.4 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)	18
2.2.1.5 Obligations of Data Controllers	20
2.2.1.6 Joint Contollership	20
2.3 Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union	21
3 Data Management Plan	22
3.1 FAIR Data	22
3.1.1 Findable Data	24
3.1.2 Accessible Data	25
3.1.3 Interoperable Data	26
3.1.4 Reusable Data	26
3.1.5 Allocation of Resources	26
3.2 Data Quality	27
3.3 Data Security and Personal Data Protection	28
3.3.1 iDriving Personal Data Protection Approach	28
3.3.2 iDriving Data Security Approach	29
4 Intellectual Property	31
4.1 Copyright	31
4.1.1 Applicable Legal Framework	32
4.1.1.1 International Legal Framework	32
4.1.1.2 European Legal Framework	33
4.2 Trademarks	34
4.2.1 Applicable Legal Framework	34
4.2.1.1 International Legal Framework	34
4.2.1.2 European Legal Framework	37
4.3 Trade Secrets	37

4.3.1	Applicable Legal Framework	37
4.3.1.1	International Legal Framework	37
4.3.1.2	European Legal Framework	38
4.4	National Legal Frameworks	38
4.5	Licensing	38
4.5.1	Software licensing	39
5	Trustworthy AI	41
5.1	AI within iDriving	41
5.2	Legal Framework	43
5.2.1	The AI Act	43
5.2.1.1	Objectives	43
5.2.1.2	Scope	43
5.2.2	Risk Assessment Methodology under the AI Act	44
5.2.2.1	Unacceptable Risk (Prohibited AI systems)	44
5.2.2.2	High-Risk AI Systems	44
5.2.2.3	Limited Risk AI Systems	45
5.2.2.4	Minimal or No Risk AI Systems	45
5.3	Ethics Framework	45
5.3.1	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (hereinafter “Guidelines”)	46
5.3.1.1	Ethical Principles in the Context of AI Systems	48
5.3.1.2	Requirements for Trustworthy AI	48
5.3.2	The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment (hereinafter “ALTAI”).	51
6	Ethical Considerations of iDriving Implementation	52
6.1	Human Participation	52
6.1.1	Recruitment of participants	52
6.1.1.1	Informed Consent	53
6.1.1.2	Equity, Fairness and Cultural Sensitivity	53
6.1.2	Incidental Findings Policy	53
6.2	Environmental, health and safety	55
6.3	Research Integrity	55
7	Annexes	58
7.1	Annex 1 Information Sheet and Consent Form	58
7.2	Annex 2 – List of criteria for assessing whether processing operations are likely to result in high risks	61
7.3	Annex 3 - Data Summary	64
7.3.1	ACCELLIGENCE	65
7.3.2	CERTH	81
7.3.3	DREVEN	94
7.3.4	Netcompany-Intrasoft	105

7.3.5	MobiLysis	116
7.3.6	Université Gustave Eiffel	127
7.3.7	LIF	139
7.3.8	TUC	155
7.3.9	City of Karlovac	166
7.3.10	ALP.Lab	177
7.3.11	SIMAVI	188
7.3.12	INFRA	200
7.3.13	AUSTRIATECH	211
7.3.14	INGARTEK	224
7.3.15	TEKNIKER	237
7.3.16	Thessaloniki	250
7.3.17	ALBA JULIA	261
	PROJECT FACTS	272

Table of tables

Table 1	Three-pillar Test for Legitimate Interest	13
Table 2	FAIR Principles	24
Table 3	iDriving Pilots	41
Table 4	AI Development on WP Level	42
Table 5	Ethics Assessment for Human Participation	52
Table 6	Incidental Findings Policy Procedure	54
Table 7	Principles of Research Integrity	56

Table of figures

Figure 1	AI Risk Levels	44
Figure 2	Trustworthy AI	46

Glossary

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCL	Creative Common Licenses
C-ITS	Communication Intelligent Transport System
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EU	European Union
EUIPO	European Union Intellectual Property Office
EILA	End-User License Agreement
EUPL	European Union Public Licence
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITMS	Intelligent Traffic Management System
MS	Member State
NCL	The Nice Classification
SCC	Safety Criteria Catalogue
SMEs	Medium-sized enterprises
TM	Trademark

TRIPS	Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
VMS	Variable Message Signs
V2I	Vehicle-to-infrastructure
WCT	The WIPO Copyright Treaty
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation
WP	Work Package
WTO	World Trade Organisation
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

As outlined above, the first iteration of the Data Governance and IPR Handbook aims to ensure the legal and ethical implementation of all activities envisioned in the project. It provides a comprehensive framework for managing intellectual property rights and data, ensuring compliance with relevant laws and regulations, and addressing ethical considerations throughout the project's lifecycle. The handbook serves as a key reference for partners, guiding them in the proper handling of data, the protection of intellectual property, and adherence to legal and ethical standards.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- **Introduction** - This section outlines the purpose, scope, and structure of the document, providing a roadmap for the reader.
- **Legal Framework** – Describes the overall legal framework to be adhered to throughout the project implementation.
- **Data Management Plan** – Offers a comprehensive guide on managing data efficiently and compliantly, covering collection, processing, storage, sharing, and preservation, while addressing ethical and legal considerations.
- **Intellectual Property Rights** - This section explains the ownership and usage rights of intellectual property generated during the project.
- **Trustworthy AI** – Outlines the legal and ethical guidelines for developing trustworthy AI systems within the iDriving project, ensuring adherence to applicable standards.
- **Ethical Considerations of iDriving Implementation** – The final section provides guidelines for conducting research and involving human participants ethically within the project.

2 Legal Framework

This section provides an overview of the applicable legal framework in the areas of privacy and human rights protection. It begins by outlining the relevant provisions of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, before moving on to examine partners' obligations under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A brief overview of Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 on the processing of non-personal data is further provided. The legal framework relevant to the protection of intellectual property rights and the development of trustworthy AI is discussed in the relevant sections below.

2.1 The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union

The iDriving project is committed to upholding the core rights and principles outlined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union¹ (EU) (hereafter 'the Charter'), including human dignity, privacy and data protection, equality and non-discrimination, physical and mental well-being, intellectual property, accessibility for persons with disabilities, and environmental protection.

Within iDriving, each initiative, from new technologies to infrastructure improvements, will be designed to respect individuals and safeguard their dignity. Given the data-driven nature of the project, privacy and data security are crucial, and all data will be handled in full compliance with the GDPR as well as other relevant legal instruments. The project is also committed to equality, ensuring that its benefits are accessible to everyone, with special attention to inclusivity for people with disabilities in design and functionality. Finally, iDriving will consider environmental impact at every stage, aligning with EU sustainability goals to support both road safety and environmental responsibility.

These fundamental rights are consistently referred to in all related legal and ethical documents that should be adhered to by iDriving partners. They should serve as the foundation for the implementation of all envisioned activities within the project duration.

2.2 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The right to privacy is a fundamental human right protected under both the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights

¹ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [2012] OJ C 326/391, ELI: http://data.europa.eu/eli/treaty/char_2012/oj.

(ECHR)² which grant everyone the right “to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications.”³ Furthermore, the Charter protects everyone’s right to “the protection of personal data concerning him or her.”⁴ According to Article 4 of the GDPR, personal data is “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’).”⁵ This definition excludes legal persons as data subjects, defining an identifiable natural person as someone who can be recognised, either directly or indirectly, especially through an identifier like a name, ID number, location information, online identifier, or by one or more characteristics unique to their physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity.⁶

The concept of privacy is vital in safeguarding personal autonomy, dignity, and freedom, enabling individuals to make informed choices about their personal data and how it is shared. Privacy laws and regulations, particularly in the EU, are designed to protect individuals' rights and ensure that personal data is processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently. The GDPR sets stringent standards for data protection, emphasising the principles of data minimisation, purpose limitation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, confidentiality, and accountability.

2.2.1 Key Data Protection Rules for Partners

Based on the key provisions of the GDPR, this Section of the Handbook focuses on the protection of personal data within the iDriving Project. It sets out the key rules and principles to be followed by the iDriving partners to ensure the privacy of the partners, participants, stakeholders, and road users affected by the project.

2.2.1.1 GDPR Principles

The GDPR lists 7 key principles to be followed in the collection and processing of personal data.

Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency:⁷ In order to process any personal data, partners should have at least one of the legal bases listed in Article 6 of the GDPR. Additionally, the fairness principle covers that the processing of the data will not go out of the reasonable scope and that the participants will not be misled regarding the process, neither affected adversely. Transparency will be ensured through an

² Council of Europe, *European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14*, ETS 5, 4 November 1950.

³ Article 7 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union; Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR).

⁴ Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

⁵ Article 4(1) GDPR.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Article 5(1)(a) of the GDPR.

open and clear approach for the processing of the data that will enable the participants to fully understand how their information is being handled.

Guidelines for Partners:

In the iDriving context, partners will be collecting personal data on two of the legal bases provided for in the GDPR. Where personal data is collected indirectly through road cameras, drones and other similar means, the legal basis for processing is also justified under Article 6(1)(f) of the GDPR, pertaining to legitimate interest. This basis is appropriate as the primary purpose of data collection is to enhance road safety by monitoring traffic flow and identifying unsafe driving behaviours. However, as shown in Table 1 Three-pillar Test for Legitimate Interest below, to rely on legitimate interest, a three-pillar balancing test must be conducted to weigh the public interest in road safety against potential impacts on individual privacy rights, ensuring that data collection is proportionate and necessary. The Court of Justice of the European Union confirmed this approach to establishing legitimate interests in the Rigas case (C-13/16, 4 May 2017), which relates to the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC that had a similar provision. The Court emphasised the importance of conducting a balancing test to ensure that the legitimate interests pursued do not override the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals.⁸

Table 1 Three-pillar Test for Legitimate Interest

Three-pillar Test for Legitimate Interest ⁹	
Purpose test	<p>The first step is to establish a clear and specific purpose for the data collection. In this context, the purpose is enhancing road safety, which includes improving traffic management, reducing accidents, and fostering better infrastructure planning. The objective should be explicitly articulated, as this clarity is essential for demonstrating that the data processing is necessary for legitimate interests.</p> <p>Example: The installation of road cameras aims to monitor traffic patterns to identify high-risk areas where accidents frequently occur. This information will then be used to implement safety measures, such as</p>

⁸ Robert Bateman, 3 Part Test for Legitimate Interests Under the GDPR, available at: [3 Part Test for Legitimate Interests Under the GDPR - TermsFeed](#).

⁹ Information Commissioner’s Office, What is the ‘legitimate interest basis’, available at: [What is the ‘legitimate interests’ basis? | ICO](#).

	<p>adding traffic signals or redesigning intersections.</p>
<p>Necessity test</p>	<p>The necessity test assesses whether data collection is essential to achieve the stated purpose. This involves evaluating if there are alternative approaches that could be taken to meet the goal without relying on personal data or reducing the impact on privacy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it proportionate? - Are there alternative? <p>Example: If road safety can be improved by using aggregated traffic data from existing sources without identifying individual vehicles or individuals, this alternative should be considered. However, if specific data from cameras is necessary to analyse trends, such as identifying repeat offenders of traffic violations, then the collection of personal data may be justified.</p>
<p>Balancing test</p>	<p>Finally, the benefits of the data collection must be weighed against the potential risks to individual privacy rights. This test considers factors such as the nature of the data, the context of its collection, and any safeguards in place to mitigate privacy concerns. It ensures that the data processing is proportionate and respects individuals' rights.</p>

Purpose limitation obliges partners to refrain from processing personal data in a manner incompatible with the established purpose.¹⁰

Data minimisation: Data collectors within iDriving should only collect personal data that is relevant and necessary for achieving the established purpose.¹¹ To ensure this, partners should periodically review the collected data to ensure that no

¹⁰ Article 5(1)(b).

¹¹ Article 5(1)(c).

unnecessary or irrelevant personal information is retained. Any extra data that is not required for the project's stated purposes should be deleted.

Accuracy: Partners are responsible for ensuring that personal data is accurate and kept up to date. Any inaccuracies must be rectified without delay.¹²

Storage limitation: Personal data must not be kept in a form that allows identification of individuals for longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data was collected. Partners should implement retention policies to define appropriate timeframes for data storage and ensure timely deletion.¹³

Integrity and confidentiality (security): Data collectors must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect personal data against unauthorised access, loss, or destruction. This includes using encryption, access controls, and regular security assessments to safeguard the data.¹⁴

Accountability: Partners are required to demonstrate compliance with all the principles outlined above. This involves maintaining documentation of data processing activities, conducting regular audits, and being prepared to demonstrate how personal data is handled responsibly and in accordance with the regulation.¹⁵

2.2.1.2 Ensuring Protection of Data Subjects' Rights

To ensure compliance with the above-mentioned principles and the protection of fundamental rights, the GDPR grants data subjects specific rights related to the collection and processing of their personal data. As data controllers, the iDriving project consortium is responsible for safeguarding these rights.

Right to Information

The right to information requires data collectors to clearly inform data subjects (e.g., road users, stakeholders and other participants) about the collection, processing, and purpose of their data. This includes details on:

- The identity and contact details of the controller.
- The purpose of the processing of personal data.
- The legal basis for processing of personal data.
- The recipients or categories of recipients of the collected data.
- Transfer to third countries.
- The exact duration of the period for which the personal data will be stored. Where providing the exact duration is not possible, the data controller must inform the data subject of the criteria used to determine that period.

¹² Ibid, Article 5(1)(d).

¹³ Ibid, Article 5(1) (e).

¹⁴ Ibid, Article 5(1)(f).

¹⁵ Ibid, Article 5(2).

- The rest of the rights of the data subject.
- The existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.
- The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

This information can be made accessible through a public privacy notice, the project website, or the app used by road users. Furthermore, Annex 1 of this document provides an information sheet to be provided to data subjects by iDriving partners when directly collecting personal data from stakeholders and other participants.

Right to Consent and Withdrawal of Consent

Consent is freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.¹⁶ Users should be able to consent to individual processing purposes separately and retain the right to withdraw consent at any time, affecting only future processing. Withdrawal must be as easy as providing consent, ensuring data processing remains lawful up to the point of withdrawal.

Where the collection of personal data is based on consent, partners should obtain informed consent wherever data is linked to an individual (even if indirectly identifiable). This is to be done using the Consent form and information sheet in Annex 1. Partners should ensure data subjects have an easy way to withdraw consent. They are further required to maintain precise records detailing when and how consent was obtained, including the specific information shared with data subjects and the consent method used. These records must be securely stored and accessible for audits or compliance reviews if needed.

Data subjects must be notified at the point of consent if their personal data will be shared with third parties, with clear information provided about who these third parties are and why the data will be shared. Consent for such sharing must be explicitly granted, and individuals should have the right to opt out without it affecting their participation in other areas of the project.

Partners must routinely review consent procedures, and the information provided to ensure they remain compliant with GDPR and aligned with current data processing activities. If processing activities change, new consent must be obtained from data subjects.

Right of Access

Data subjects can request confirmation of whether their personal data is processed and, if so, access to it. This includes information on processing purposes, data

¹⁶ Recital 32 GDPR

categories, and any automated decision-making. For automated decision processes, individuals should receive an understanding of the logic, significance, and potential impacts of these decisions.

Data collectors within iDriving should allow data subjects to request access to their data, explaining how they can make a request and the type of information they will receive. For instance, in cases where anonymised data indirectly involves personal data, participants should detail how individuals can view relevant processed data.

Right to Rectification

If identifiable errors occur, partners should allow individuals to correct or update this information. This right, however, may be limited if data is aggregated or anonymised.

Right to Erasure ('Right to be Forgotten')

Data subjects can request deletion of their personal data if it is no longer necessary, consent has been withdrawn, they object to processing, data was unlawfully processed, or when deletion is required to comply with legal obligations. However, this right does not apply if processing is necessary for public interest, legal obligations, or the establishment of legal claims. The right to erasure supports the principle of data minimisation.

To protect this right, partners within the iDriving project should establish a process for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data where applicable. Anonymised or aggregated data used for traffic analysis may not need deletion, but any personal identifiers, if stored, must be erasable upon request.

Right to Restriction of Processing

GDPR grants data subjects the right to restrict processing in specific situations: if the data's accuracy is contested, if processing is unlawful but deletion is not desired, if data is no longer needed for processing but is required for legal claims, or if the subject has objected to processing while awaiting verification. When restrictions are applied, data subjects must be informed before they are lifted.

Right to Data Portability

For any personal data processed based on consent or contract, partners should provide data subjects with an option to receive their data in a structured, machine-readable format or transfer it to another provider, if relevant to the project scope.

Right to Object

Data subjects should be informed by data collectors of their right to object to data processing, particularly if profiling or personalised suggestions based on traffic data are involved.

Right Not to be Subject to Automated Decision-Making

Where automated decision-making affects individuals, such as route optimisation based on traffic conditions, partners should include an option for individuals to seek human intervention or explanation of such decisions. If automated decisions have significant impact, partners should provide transparent criteria and rationale, especially if safety or emergency response actions are involved.

2.2.1.3 Additional Internal Rules for Partners

Data protection by Design and Default

Data collectors within the iDriving project should ensure that the tools and solutions developed within the project's framework are compliant by default and by design with the regulations of the GDPR.

To do so, controllers should implement technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, as well as put in place the necessary safeguards to protect data subjects' rights and ensure the above-mentioned data protection principles.¹⁷

Regular Review

Data controllers should regularly review and update the necessary safeguards and consent procedures, to ensure compliance with personal data protection regulations.¹⁸ Should there be any changes in the processing activities, partners should obtain new consent from data subjects.

Incident Reporting

In cases of a personal data breach, controllers should immediately notify the supervisory authority and the project coordinator. Such notification should be made no later than 72 hours after having become aware of it.¹⁹

The notification should describe the breach, provide contact details, outline the consequences, and detail measures taken to address and mitigate the breach.²⁰

2.2.1.4 Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)

A DPIA is a procedure intended to address "risky" processing operation of personal data, evaluate their necessity and proportionality, and assist in managing the risks to individuals' rights arising from such processing by identifying and mitigating those risks. DPIAs provide a structured approach for assessing risks to data subjects

¹⁷ Article 25(1) GDPR.

¹⁸ Ibid, Article 24(1).

¹⁹ Ibid, Article 33(1).

²⁰ Ibid, Article 33(2).

and finding ways to mitigate them, which is particularly crucial for implementing "data protection by design" in high-risk processing operations.²¹

According to Article 35(3) of the GDPR, data controllers should carry out a DPIA in the following scenarios:

- a) when there is a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal characteristics of individuals through automated processing, including profiling, which forms the basis for decisions that have legal consequences or similarly significant effects on those individuals;
- b) when processing large volumes of special categories of data as specified in Article 9(1), or personal data related to criminal convictions and offenses as specified in Article 10;
- c) when there is large-scale systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area.

Additionally, Article 35(7) requires that the assessment conducted must include, at a minimum, a comprehensive outline of the planned processing activities and their objectives, including the legitimate interests pursued by the controller when applicable. It should further encompass an evaluation of the necessity and proportionality of these processing activities in relation to their purposes. Furthermore, the assessment must consider the potential risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, as noted in paragraph 1 of Article 35(7). To mitigate these risks, it is essential to outline the proposed measures, such as safeguards, security protocols, and mechanisms designed to protect personal data and demonstrate compliance with this regulation, while also considering the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other relevant parties.

Furthermore, the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) has established an open list of processing operations subject to the requirement for a DPIA. The list is provided in this document (Annex 2) and is to be used by the iDriving partners when assessing processing operations taking place within the project. If two or more criteria from the list apply, the controller must conduct a DPIA. If the controller determines that despite meeting multiple criteria, the risks are not deemed "high," they must provide a clear explanation and justification for why they believe the processing does not pose high risks. Each criterion is accompanied by examples and counterexamples to illustrate what typically would (not) trigger each criterion.²²

It is important to remember that failure to comply with DPIA regulations may result in fines from the relevant national data protection authorities.

²¹ European Data Protection Supervisor, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), available at: [Data Protection Impact Assessment \(DPIA\) | European Data Protection Supervisor](#).

²² European Data Protection Supervisor, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), available at: [Data Protection Impact Assessment \(DPIA\) | European Data Protection Supervisor](#).

2.2.1.5 Obligations of Data Controllers

To promote the principles outlined above and protect data subject's rights, data controllers within the iDriving project should establish technical and organisational measures to ensure GDPR-compliant processing. Measures should reflect the nature, scope, context, and purpose of the data collected, as well as the risks associated with processing activities. Controllers should further evaluate the sensitivity of the data, the volume and diversity of information, and potential impacts if data is misused or exposed. They should align all data processing activities with the legitimate purposes of the project, and regularly assess risks to individual rights and freedoms to determine proportional security measures. These measures should be reviewed and updated regularly to ensure ongoing compliance.²³

Where appropriate to the scale and nature of processing, formal data protection policies should be established. Policies should outline essential data handling procedures, including processes for collecting, processing, storing, and securely deleting data. Implement access controls to restrict data access to authorised personnel and establish protocols for reviewing access permissions. A protocol for managing data breaches should be defined, including immediate reporting to project leads and measures to mitigate impact.²⁴

To further demonstrate compliance, partners should consider adherence to approved data protection codes of conduct and recognised certification mechanisms. Approved codes of conduct (as referenced in GDPR Article 40) help maintain consistent standards across partners, while certification mechanisms (as referenced in Article 42) provide formal recognition of compliance with data protection and privacy requirements.²⁵

2.2.1.6 Joint Controllership

Joint controllership under Article 26 of the GDPR refers to a situation where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and methods of processing personal data. It requires the controllers to clearly define their roles and responsibilities in accordance with EU or national law through a legally binding agreement. The Joint Controllership Agreement must ensure compliance with GDPR principles and uphold the rights of data subjects. Part of their obligation includes informing data subjects about how responsibilities are allocated and providing a clear understanding of the agreement's essence. Notably, joint controllers also share responsibility in the event of GDPR violations.

²³ Article 24(1) GDPR.

²⁴ Ibid, Article 24(2).

²⁵ Ibid, Article 24(3).

Where joint controllership occurs in the iDriving project, appropriate agreements will be concluded between partners and/or other parties.

2.3 Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union

In addition to the collection of personal data, the successful implementation of the iDriving project requires the processing and/or generation of non-personal data. The processing/generation of such data is envisioned in the research and development activities in WP2-7, and it is important that partners differentiate between and accurately categorise personal and non-personal data in the various datasets. To support this process, LIF – the legal and ethical partner of iDriving, created and distributed among partners a Data Management Questionnaire, which is to be updated biannually by each partner.

The use of non-personal data in the EU is mainly governed by Regulation (EU) 2018/1807,²⁶ which establishes a framework for the free flow of non-personal data within the EU, aiming to eliminate barriers to data movement across Member States. Key objectives include removing unnecessary data localisation requirements (except for justified public security reasons), enhancing data portability and interoperability among providers, and ensuring regulatory authorities have access to data stored across Member States for oversight. This Regulation governs the processing of non-personal data needed for the project, applying to datasets containing only non-personal data, as well as to the non-personal segments of mixed datasets, provided there is no requirement for GDPR to take precedence.

²⁶ Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union, OJ L 303, 28.11.2018, p. 59–68, ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2018/1807/oj>.

3 Data Management Plan

As Task 1.4 of the iDriving project envisages, LIF with the assistance of the rest of the project partners, will prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) which will cover all data governance practices within the consortium including all data processing activities that the project partners will conduct during the lifetime of the project.

The DMP of iDriving describes the data planned to be collected, processed and generated in the Project, and categories them with respect to 1) their confidentiality, ethical treatment, possibility to be shared in the open data initiative, and 2) their format and standardisation, and specifies guidelines for managing all generated data in accordance with their categorisation. Additionally, the collected data is then presented in view of how it observes the FAIR Principles, as well as the data security measures that would be applied.

For the composition of the current DMP, the lead partner – LIF, has designed a Data Management Plan Questionnaire which was distributed to all project partners for feedback. The information presented Annex 3 presents iDriving partners contributions 'as is', which were provided in this initial stage of the project.

It is important to note that this is the first iteration of the iDriving DMP. Two more versions will follow in M18 and M36 (with D1.3 and D1.4) in order to assess whether the information input by the respective partner is still relevant and valid. If not, changes will be introduced. What is more, over the course of the project's duration it is expected that more and more information will be provided to allow the DMP to be as robust as possible.

3.1 FAIR Data

The main objective of the FAIR data concept is to give data greater value, considering enhanced reusability for future projects and research. Therefore, data should be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, and intelligible, usable beyond the original purpose for which it was collected and wherever possible, interoperable to specific quality standards. The concept of the holistic and systemic approach considers that data should be as open as possible to increase the scientific and social value, but also needs to be restricted when needed.

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Table 2 FAIR Principles below sets out the FAIR Guiding Principles as follows:²⁷

²⁷ FAIR Guiding Principles, available at: <https://fairtoolkit.pistoiaalliance.org/fair-guiding-principles/>

Table 2 FAIR Principles

The FAIR Guiding Principles:
Findable
F1. (meta)data is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
F2. data is described with rich metadata
F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes.
F4. (meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
Accessible
A1. (meta)data is retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol.
A1.1. the protocol is free, open and universally implementable.
A1.2. the protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary
A2. metadata is accessible, even when the data are no longer available
Interoperable
I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2. (meta)data uses vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
Reusable
R1. (meta)data is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1. (meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
R1.2. (meta)data is associated with data provenance.
R1.3. (meta)data meet domain relevant community standards.

Since the iDriving project is an EU funded project, FAIR principles are essential for research data, wherever applicable. This plan tries to extend those principles also to the datasets collected and generated in the innovation activities of the project, whenever possible.

3.1.1 Findable Data

Within the iDriving project the data management activities will ensure that data is findable with the usage of unique identifiers (e.g., DOI) to prevent ambiguity and ensure datasets can be easily referenced in another research. In second place

detailed metadata will accompany all data sets to make them easily searchable. The metadata will include descriptions of data sources, methods, formats, and relevant keywords. Adopting established metadata standards for the data processing activities (e.g., ISO/IEC standards or Dublin Core Metadata Initiative²⁸) will enhance findability. Additionally, data will be deposited in reputable data repositories (iDriving will use SharePoint and other reputable data repositories) to increase visibility and findability. These repositories will ensure that data can be easily located via standard search engines and academic indexing.

Proper file naming that sufficiently describes the content so that it can be inferred to regardless of the location where the file is stored will be adopted for the purposes of iDriving. File names must contain the minimum possible number of characters. Here is an initial list of good practices for partners to follow, that will be evaluated and refined accordingly in the following months:

- No special characters: @, #, etc.
- No white space, instead underscore is recommended.
- No abbreviations or codes.
- Use of period only before the file – name extensions.
- File version to be included.
- Standard date following ISO (8601) (YYYYMM).

Files will follow the naming conventions iDriving_ContentType_Date_Version.extension (e.g., iDriving_Brochure_20241001_v1.0.pdf).

3.1.2 Accessible Data

The main aim of the Horizon Europe Open Science mandate is to make research data generated in Horizon Europe projects accessible, so it is possible to:

- Build on previous results.
- Sharing of knowledge, data and tools.
- Encourage collaboration.
- Speed up innovation and,
- Involve citizens and society.

While at the same time also accepting restrictions and protection for data due to security and/or commercial reasons or privacy concerns.

iDriving differentiates between publicly accessible data, like e.g., scientific publications, and datasets coming from the research activities that are subject to special conditions of availability.

Publicly accessible data will be openly available through the open-source data repositories. The access to confidential data, e.g., non-anonymous datasets

²⁸ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublincore/dces/>.

(security and/or privacy concerns) and innovation data which will be used for commercial and/or exploitation, will be restricted to the iDriving partners and stored at the consortium's SharePoint folder, since it ensures GDPR compliance, provides robust encryption mechanisms, and provide enough tools for enforcing access control policies.

3.1.3 Interoperable Data

The project will follow metadata standards for general data documentation. This will ensure compatibility with other datasets and systems, facilitating easier data sharing and integration. For example, with web analytics data, Google Analytics metadata standards will be followed.

As far as possible, standard vocabularies and machine-readable file, formats are used when storing research data in the chosen data repositories. iDriving will not generate project specific vocabularies and will not produce formal mappings of terms to established vocabularies or ontologies. Vocabulary maintainers to ensure editorial control of consistency should do such mappings. iDriving focus is not to maintain common vocabulary for the research community

3.1.4 Reusable Data

Third parties will be able to make use of all publicly accessible data sets published by iDriving consortium. In principle, this is regulated by Creative Common Licenses (CCL) or other open-source initiative licenses, like for e.g., MIT License or Apache2.0 License. The type of licenses which will be applied to which part of public data will be considered by the iDriving consortium during the project duration and will be documented and updated in each version of the DMP. Licenses that will apply for specific data must be assessed for each case in close collaboration with the iDriving project partners involved.

In iDriving data will be reused by third parties upon request and approval by the data owner. Only processed and anonymised data may be made freely available upon request. Raw data and sensitive operational data will have restricted access due to security and privacy restrictions. Specific restrictions will be adopted on who can re-use the data. Only authorised users within the consortium or those who meet specific ethical and legal criteria will be allowed to reuse restricted data.

3.1.5 Allocation of Resources

In order to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project, all project partners we asked to provide estimation what resources would be required to ensure proper data management during the project.

In the first few mounts it was estimated by the iDriving partners that data management activities will be conducted by experts in the participating in the project organisations. Additional costs may arise I relation to the usage of cloud computing services and to cover expenses for the necessary data encryption. A more accurate estimation regarding the allocation of resources will be done in the following iterations of this report.

3.2 Data Quality

The Data Quality Assurance Processes and measures are essential parts of specific tasks in iDriving project. Specific measures will be adopted to ensure data quality through all different phases of the project including data collection, data deposition, data prevention, access and reuse.

Specific attention will be given to the quality of data that will be used for the development of the AI components within iDriving. As the AI Act²⁹ envisages in Art. 10 - training, validation and testing data sets shall be subject to data governance and management practices appropriate for the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system. The specific practices shall cover the following:

- The relevant design choices.
- Data collection processes and the origin of data, and in the case of personal data, the original purpose of the data collection.
- Relevant data-preparation processing operations, such as annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation.
- The formulation of assumptions, in particular with respect to the information that the data are supposed to measure and represent.
- An assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed.
- Examination in view of possible biases that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination prohibited under Union law, especially were data outputs influence inputs for future operations.
- Appropriate measures to detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases.
- The identification of relevant data gaps or shortcomings that prevent compliance with this Regulation, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed.

²⁹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act).

3.3 Data Security and Personal Data Protection

As data security and personal data processing can pose various types of implications (incl. negative) to the data subjects, it is of primary importance for all the necessary safeguards to be put in place in order to ensure an adequate level of protection. For this reason, the iDriving project has envisaged a clearly defined framework to abide by all data protection considerations.

3.3.1 iDriving Personal Data Protection Approach

The data protection framework for iDriving project will adhere to GDPR principles, ensuring that data protection design and by default, transparency and accountability are followed. Key areas of focus will include the following topics:

- Lawfulness, Fairness and Transparency: Processing of personal data will only occur if lawful bases are clearly established (e.g., consent, legitimate interest etc.).
- Purpose limitation: Data will be collected solely for the purposes directly related to the goals of the iDriving project. Any secondary usage will require separate approval and justification.
- Accuracy: The data collected will be regularly updated to maintain accuracy.
- Storage Limitation: Data will only be retained for as long as needed for the project purposes considering the requirements for Horizon Europe research projects with clear protocols for timely data anonymisation or deletion.
- Integrity and Confidentiality: Measures will be implemented to secure data against unauthorised access, accidental loss and destruction.

To address properly the data protection matters relevant to the iDriving project a dedicated mapping exercise will be launched within the iDriving Data Management Plan Questionnaire in order to provide a comprehensive review in terms of who processes personal data for what purpose, upon which legal ground, of which data subjects, whether it is going to be shared and with whom (incl. recipients in third countries), for how long this is going to be stored, and how this complies with the principles data minimisation, purpose limitation, integrity and confidentiality. It should be noted that the first component of the mapping exercise was explicitly focused on the existing internal regulations that individual partners abide by when it comes to data protection in general. Although the latter does not target the project activities per se, it allows for the establishment of a complete framework of data protection matters that are applicable to the iDriving context.

Based on the above the following data protection measures were identified as suitable for the iDriving project:

- **Data Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation:** Where possible, data will be anonymised or pseudonymised to reduce risks to individuals.

- **User Consent and Transparency:** Individuals will be fully informed about data collection, processing, and usage through clear privacy notices. If direct consent is required, this will be obtained via transparent consent mechanisms that are easy to withdraw.
- **Data Access Controls:** Access to personal data will be restricted based on role and need. Researchers and developers will have limited access based on the principle of least privilege.
- **Audit Logs:** Audit trails will be maintained to monitor data access and processing activities, helping to detect and respond to unauthorised access attempts.
- **Data Deletion Policies:** Data will be deleted in line with storage limitation principles once it is no longer necessary for project purposes, according to established retention schedules.

By embedding these data protection strategies, the project will uphold GDPR standards, respect individual rights, and demonstrate a commitment to responsible and ethical research practices in the pursuit of iDriving's project goals. Regular audits and reviews will be conducted to assess compliance with data protection requirements.

3.3.2 iDriving Data Security Approach

The overall data security framework of the iDriving project will be structured according to international security standards (such as ISO/IEC 27001) and GDPR security requirements. This will ensure a secure-by-design and by default approach to protect data at every stage, from collection and processing to storage and deletion. Key principles will cover the well-known CIA³⁰ triad defined by the US National Institute of Standards and Technology which are the following:

- **Confidentiality:** Preventing unauthorised access to data by enforcing access controls and encryption.
- **Integrity:** Safeguarding data from unauthorised modifications, ensuring it remains accurate and reliable.
- **Availability:** Ensuring data is accessible to authorised users when needed, especially for real-time safety applications

Similarly, as in point 4.4.1 of the current report, the iDriving project partner was asked to provide relevant information related to data security aspects with the iDriving Data Management Plan Questionnaire. Based on that the following security measures were identified:

- **Risk Assessment and Threat Modelling:** An initial risk assessment and threat modelling exercise will identify specific risks associated with data

³⁰ Data Integrity: Identifying and Protecting Assets Against Ransomware and Other Destructive Events – National Institute of Standards and Technology.

handling in this project, including risks related to sensor data collection, AI processing, and the Digital Twin.

- **Data Encryption:** Stored data, particularly personal and sensitive data, will be encrypted with encryption algorithms. Encryption keys will be managed securely, with restricted access to key management systems.
- **Access Control:** Access to data will be restricted to authorised users based on their specific project role and responsibilities. This minimises exposure of sensitive data to only those who need it.
- **Logging and Monitoring:** Detailed access logs will be maintained to track all data access and modifications. Monitoring systems will alert for any unusual or unauthorised access attempts.
- **Incident Response:** An incident response plan will ensure prompt action in case of security breaches or data leaks. This will include predefined roles, response protocols, and clear communication channels.

Continuous Security Monitoring and Improvement will be conducted periodically to evaluate the effectiveness of security measures and controls, with adjustments made as needed.

4 Intellectual Property

Intellectual Property (IP) refers to the creation of human mind and the results of the creative efforts of the human intellect, while Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) aim to clearly establish IP ownership and protect owner's rights as such. IPR, as exclusive rights, allow organisations and individuals to prevent competitors from using their intangible assets.

IPR is divided into three main categories, namely – copyright and related rights, industrial property (patents, trademarks, industrial design, etc)³¹ and SOFT IP (Trade secrets, know-how, confidential information).

LIF, as the legal and ethical partner of the project, has developed an IPR Registry with the purpose of clearly establishing and managing IP background and foreground within the iDriving project. The registry is to be distributed among partners and updated on a regular basis to ensure proper IPR management within the project.

The main types of IPR arising from the inventions within the iDriving project are copyright, trademarks and, potentially, trade secrets. The following sections of this document will define these IPR and examine the applicable legal framework on international and regional level.

Within the iDriving consortium, IPR between project partners will be managed in accordance with the terms set forth in the GA and the Consortium Agreement (CA). These agreements will serve as the primary frameworks to ensure that all IPR matters, including ownership, access rights, and exploitation of results, are clearly defined, protected, and enforced. Any issues arising around IPR will be addressed through mutual consultation, maintaining alignment with the established guidelines in the GA and CA to ensure a fair and effective resolution process.

4.1 Copyright

Copyright, also known as 'author's right', covers the legal rights of authors over their literary and artistic works.³² According to the Berne Convention, 'literary and artistic works include:

“every production in the literary, scientific and artistic domain, whatever may be the mode or form of its expressions, such as books, pamphlets, and other writings; lectures, addresses, sermons and other works of the same

³¹ Cambridge University Press 978-1-107-02316-1 - A Handbook on the WTO Trips Agreement Edited by Antony Taubman, Hannu Wager and Jayashree Wata, available at: [*A HANDBOOK ON THE WTO TRIPS AGREEMENT](#).

³² Article 1 of the Berne Convention.

*nature; (...) works of drawing, painting, architecture, sculpture (...); photographic works to which are assimilated works expressed by a process analogous to photography; works of applied art; illustrations, maps, plans, sketches and three-dimensional works relative to geography, topography, architecture or science.*³³

In addition, the WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organisation) Copyright Treaty³⁴ (WCT) further clarifies that Article 2 of the Berne Convention extends to computer programs, regardless of their mode or form of expression.³⁵

The iDriving project envisions the production and the development of various artistic and literary works, such as software code, graphics, user interfaces, research reports, technical documents, training materials and simulation scenarios among others.

4.1.1 Applicable Legal Framework

4.1.1.1 International Legal Framework

The most widely ratified international legal instrument on the protection of copyright - the Berne Convention, is applicable in more than 180 states. The Convention's provisions establish the minimum standards around the protection of copyright, covering authors' rights – both moral and economic, over their works, the criteria of eligibility of protection, terms of protection, and possible limitations and restrictions of these rights. The protection offered by the Convention applies to citizens and residents of the State Parties to the Convention, as well as to authors who are not nationals, but whose works are first published in one of these countries, or simultaneously in a non-member country and a member country. The rights protected under the Convention include the rights to translation, reproduction, performance, adaptation and distribution of authors' works.

Authors can enjoy and exercise these rights without needing to complete any formal requirements. These rights apply regardless of whether the work is protected in the country of origin of the work. Therefore, aside from what this Convention specifies, the level of protection and the ways an author can defend their rights are determined solely by the laws of the country where protection is sought.

Furthermore, as mentioned above, the WCT extends the scope of Article 2 of the Berne Convention to computer programs. While the WCT does not provide a definition of "computer program," during the preparation phase of the Treaty, the

³³ Ibid, Article 2.

³⁴ WIPO Copyright Treaty (WCT) (adopted in Geneva on December 20, 1996), available at: [WIPO Copyright Treaty](#).

³⁵ Article 4 of the WCT.

definition adopted by the WIPO Model Provisions on the Protection of Computer Programs was recognised to still be legitimate.³⁶ This definition described a computer program as “a set of instructions capable, when incorporated in a machine-readable medium, of causing a machine having information-processing capabilities to indicate, perform or achieve a particular function, task or result.” Furthermore, the WCT defines databases as “compilations of data or other material, in any form, which by reason of the selection or arrangement of their contents constitute intellectual creations.”³⁷ The provision further clarifies that the protection provided therein does not extend to the data or the material contained in the database.

Finally, alongside the Berne Convention and the WCT, the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, hereafter referred to as the TRIPS Agreement is, to date, the most comprehensive multilateral agreement on intellectual property.³⁸ It addresses all major categories of IPRs, setting forth standards for their protection and outlining rules for their administration and enforcement. It also incorporates the WTO dispute settlement mechanism to handle disputes between member countries regarding adherence to these standards.

4.1.1.2 European Legal Framework

On the EU level, copyright receives extensive protection by various EU documents. For instance, Directive 2009/24/EC³⁹ focuses on the legal protection of computer programs, treating them as literary works under the Berne Convention. It ensures that the expression of a computer program, rather than the underlying ideas, is protected.⁴⁰ In addition to the international definition, the Directive provides that computer programs should include “their preparatory design material.”⁴¹ The Directive grants exclusive rights to authors, including reproduction, adaptation, and distribution, and applies to programs created by individuals or within employment contexts.⁴² Furthermore, Directive 96/9/EC⁴³ provides protection for

³⁶ WIPO, Digital Ecosystem, available at: [DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM:](#)

³⁷ Article 5, WCT.

³⁸ Cambridge University Press 978-1-107-02316-1 - A Handbook on the WTO Trips Agreement Edited by Antony Taubman, Hannu Wager and Jayashree Wata, available at: [*A HANDBOOK ON THE WTO TRIPS AGREEMENT.](#)

³⁹ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs, also known as the ‘Software Directive’, replacing the previous Council Directive 91/250/EEC on the legal protection of computer programs.

⁴⁰ Ibid, Article 1(2).

⁴¹ Ibid, Article 1(1).

⁴² Ibid, Article 2.

⁴³ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A01996L0009-20190606>.

databases, recognising both copyright and sui generis rights for databases that involve substantial investment.⁴⁴ It defines a database as “a systematic collection of independent works or data.”⁴⁵ Directive 2004/48/EC⁴⁶ addresses the enforcement of intellectual property rights, establishing measures and remedies to combat infringement and promote innovation, competitiveness, and consumer protection across the EU.

4.2 Trademarks

Trademarks are used in trade to identify products and, as defined by Article 15 of the TRIPS Agreement,⁴⁷ they constitute “any sign, or any combination of signs, capable of distinguishing the goods or services of one undertaking from those of other undertakings, shall be capable of constituting a trademark.”⁴⁸ The provision further specifies that such signs can include words, letters, numbers, images, colour combinations, or any mix of these elements.

Trademarks in iDriving include project’s name and logo, domain name and slogans among others.

Unlike copyright, trademarks require registration. A trademark can be registered nationally, regionally or internationally.

- To be registered nationally, applications must be filed before the national trademark (TM) office accompanied by a clear reproduction of the mark + Nice classification.
- Community TM – one single application in the EUIPO in Spain – grants a single trademark valid in all MSs.
- To be registered internationally – the Madrid system (through a national TM office, through EUIPO, before WIPO).

4.2.1 Applicable Legal Framework

4.2.1.1 International Legal Framework

The key legislation governing trademarks internationally, include the Madrid System for the International Registration of Marks, namely the Madrid Agreement

⁴⁴ Ibid, Chapter III.

⁴⁵ Ibid, Article 1(2).

⁴⁶ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights, also known as ‘IPRED’ [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0048R\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0048R(01)) .

⁴⁷ Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement).

⁴⁸ Article 15(1).

and the Madrid Protocol, as well as the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property,⁴⁹ and the Nice Agreement.⁵⁰

As mentioned, the Madrid System, administered by WIPO, is governed by two treaties:⁵¹ the Madrid Agreement⁵² and the Protocol relating to that Agreement.⁵³ The Madrid Protocol expanded access to more countries, enabling easier and more flexible management of trademark rights internationally. The System is a centralised framework designed to simplify the international registration and management of trademarks.⁵⁴ It enables businesses and individuals to protect their trademarks in multiple countries by submitting a single international application in one language and paying a standardised set of fees.⁵⁵ Covering 131 member countries, representing over 80% of global trade, the Madrid System offers significant benefits by reducing the administrative and financial complexities associated with registering and maintaining trademarks across various jurisdictions. Applicants can easily modify, renew, or extend their trademark protection through this unified system, avoiding the need to navigate differing processes and regulations in individual countries. By enhancing accessibility and efficiency, the Madrid System aids businesses in establishing and protecting their brand identity on a global scale.

Trademark protection is granted for a limited period, typically 10 years in most countries, with the option to be renewed for an indefinite number of times. However, if the trademark is not used in commerce, the owner may lose their rights to it. In many countries, a trademark registration can be terminated if the trademark is not used genuinely for a continuous period for five years, although this period can vary. Therefore, it is important that the trademark is used for the goods and services it was registered for within the designated territories where protection is sought.

Furthermore, the 1883 Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, hereafter “the Paris Convention” or “the Convention”, covers a broad range of

⁴⁹ Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (as amended on September 28, 1979), WIPO, TRT/PARIS/001, available at: <https://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/text/288514>.

⁵⁰ Nice Agreement Concerning the International Classification of Goods and Services for the Purposes of the Registration of Marks (as amended on September 28, 1979), WIPO, TRT/NICE/001, available at: <https://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/text/287532>.

⁵¹ Anamta Khan, The Madrid System: Madrid Agreement and Madrid Protocol, available at: [The Madrid System: Madrid Agreement and Madrid Protocol](#).

⁵² Madrid Agreement Concerning the International Registration of Marks (as amended on September 28, 1979).

⁵³ Protocol Relating to the Madrid Agreement Concerning the International Registration of Marks adopted at Madrid on June 27, 1989, as amended on October 3, 2006, and on November 12, 2007.

⁵⁴ World Intellectual Property Organisation, “Madrid System – The International Trademark System”, available at: [WIPO Madrid System – International Trademark Protection](#).

⁵⁵ Ibid.

industrial property rights, including patents, trademarks, industrial designs, utility models, and trade names among others.⁵⁶ Specifically, the Convention provides a framework for the international protection of trademarks, establishing principles such as national treatment, the right of priority, and common rules that all Contracting States must follow. These provisions ensure that trademark owners receive consistent protection across member countries, promoting fairness and legal certainty in the global marketplace.

The Paris Convention ensures that each Contracting State grants the same trademark protection to nationals of other Contracting States as it does to its own citizens.⁵⁷ It also allows nationals of non-Contracting States with an effective industrial or commercial presence to receive similar protection. Applicants can claim a six-month priority period for trademarks, allowing them to file in other Contracting States while retaining the original filing date.⁵⁸ Trademark registrations are independent in each country, meaning the annulment of a registration in one state does not affect its validity in others.

Additionally, marks registered in the country of origin must be accepted in other Contracting States, though registration may be refused in cases of infringement or public order concerns. Registration is also prohibited for marks that are reproductions or imitations of well-known marks.

Finally, the Nice Agreement, established in 1957, introduced an international classification system for trademarks to categorise goods and services. This standardisation helps streamline trademark registration across member countries.⁵⁹ The system divides goods and services into 45 classes, making it easier for trademark offices to manage and for applicants to understand. The Nice Classification is periodically updated to ensure it remains relevant and effective.

Importantly, the classification system does not dictate the scope of trademark protection; instead, it offers a structure for organisations to classify the goods and services for which trademarks are being registered.

⁵⁶ WIPO, Summary of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, available at: [Summary of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property \(1883\)](#).

⁵⁷ WIPO, Summary of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, available at: [Summary of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property \(1883\)](#).

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ WIPO, "Nice Agreement Concerning the International Classification of Goods and Services for the Purposes of the Registration of Marks", available at: [Nice Agreement Concerning the International Classification of Goods and Services for the Purposes of the Registration of Marks](#)

4.2.1.2 European Legal Framework

On EU level, trademarks are protected mainly by Regulation (EU) 2017/1001⁶⁰ and Directive (EU) 2015/2436.⁶¹ Firstly, Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 establishes the European Union Trademark (EUTM) system, allowing a single trademark application to provide protection across all EU member states. It outlines the process for registration, examination, and enforcement of trademarks, aiming to enhance efficiency and consistency in trademark protection. Moreover, Directive (EU) 2015/2436 harmonises national trademark laws across EU member states to improve the internal market. It simplifies registration procedures, strengthens protection against deceptive trademarks, and enhances enforcement, ensuring greater consistency and accessibility for businesses seeking trademark protection.

4.3 Trade Secrets

Trade secrets have been defined by the European Commission as ‘a valuable piece of information for an enterprise that is treated as confidential and that gives that enterprise a competitive advantage.’⁶² To qualify as a trade secret, valuable information must meet the following criteria: it should not be publicly available or known to industry experts; it should hold commercial value; and reasonable measures should be taken to maintain its confidentiality. This may include secure storage and the use of non-disclosure agreements with anyone who has access to or has been provided with the information.⁶³ Should trade secrets be present during the implementation of iDriving, the partners must follow the legal framework outlined below.

4.3.1 Applicable Legal Framework

4.3.1.1 International Legal Framework

Although trade secrets are not as extensively or universally protected under the law, they do benefit from several legal safeguards, including those provided by the TRIPS Agreement. For instance, Article 39 of the Agreement mandates that member countries ensure the protection of undisclosed information, requiring that trade secrets be safeguarded against unfair competition and unauthorised disclosure.

⁶⁰ Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2017 on the European Union trademark.

⁶¹ Directive (EU) 2015/2436 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2015 to approximate the laws of the Member States relating to trade marks.

⁶² [Trade secrets - European Commission](#).

⁶³ Directive (EU) 2016/943

4.3.1.2 European Legal Framework

With the digitalisation of information, theft of trade secrets is increasingly being carried out through unauthorised access to computer networks. Cyber theft of trade secrets is estimated to cause losses of about €60 billion in the EU.⁶⁴

To address this issue, the European Parliament has adopted Directive (EU) 2016/943⁶⁵ which establishes measures and remedies that include actions to prevent the disclosure of information to safeguard the confidentiality of trade secrets.⁶⁶ Furthermore, in accordance with the principle of proportionality, the measures, procedures, and remedies designed to protect trade secrets should be specifically adapted to ensure a well-functioning internal market for research and innovation, especially by deterring the unlawful acquisition, use, and disclosure of trade secrets. This adaptation should not compromise fundamental rights and freedoms or the public interest, including public safety, consumer protection, public health, and environmental protection, nor should it hinder the mobility of workers.⁶⁷

4.4 National Legal Frameworks

Aside from the international and regional legal protection for IPR outlined in this document, partners should ensure they are familiar with the specific national laws governing IPR in their respective countries. Given that these national laws coexist with the international legal framework, understanding and aligning with them is essential for achieving harmonisation across jurisdictions. This harmonisation is crucial for consistent IPR protection and enforcement, facilitating smoother collaboration and compliance among project partners.

4.5 Licensing

Licensing in the context of intellectual property refers to the process of IP owners granting rights of use to another legal person.⁶⁸ IPR holders within the iDriving project may permit other entities to use their intellectual property through

⁶⁴ European Commission, Trade secrets, available at: [Trade secrets - European Commission](#).

⁶⁵ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets), available at: [*DIRECTIVE \(EU\) 2016/ 943 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - of 8 June 2016 - on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information \(trade secrets\) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure](#).

⁶⁶ Ibid, Rec 19.

⁶⁷ Ibid, Rec 21.

⁶⁸ European IP Helpdesk, Your Guide to IP and Contracts, available at: [Your guide to IP and contracts - Publications Office of the EU](#).

licensing agreement. These licences may be exclusive, designating a single licensee, or involve multiple licensees. When offering multiple licences, their scope can be restricted to specific industries or geographic areas, allowing for strategic control over how and where the intellectual property is utilised.⁶⁹

4.5.1 Software licensing

Software licensing outlines the legal terms and conditions that govern how software can be used, modified, and distributed.⁷⁰ Licenses are a critical element in protecting the rights of developers while informing users of their permissions and restrictions. This section examines the two key types of software licensing: proprietary software agreements, such as the End-User Licence Agreement (EULA), and open-source software.

Proprietary software limits users' ability to modify, share, or redistribute the software and usually restricts access to source code.⁷¹ This type of software is typically governed by an End-User Licence Agreement (EULA), which is a legal contract detailing usage rights and restrictions. EULAs often define the scope of the licence, such as whether the software can be installed on a single device, used for commercial purposes, or be altered in any way. They may include clauses against reverse engineering or modifying the software, which are designed to protect the software's integrity and prevent unauthorised distribution. In the European Union, these restrictions must comply with regulations such as Directive 2009/24/EC⁷² on the legal protection of computer programs, which ensures that software creators' rights are upheld across Member States.

On the other hand, open-source software contrasts with proprietary software by allowing users more freedom to access, modify, and redistribute the software's source code.⁷³ Open-source software promotes community-driven development and can be freely adapted, though it is typically distributed under specific open-source licences that outline its permitted uses. The term "open" in this context focuses on the freedoms offered rather than implying that the software is free of charge.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Urška Fric, Špela Stres and Blatnik, R. (2022). Software: Protection, Licensing and Rewarding Researchers in Computer Science – An Overview of Challenges in the European Innovation Ecosystem. *Informatica*, 46(9). doi:<https://doi.org/10.31449/inf.v46i9.4481>.

⁷¹ Ibid, p.3.

⁷² of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs, also known as the 'Software Directive', replacing the previous Council Directive 91/250/EEC on the legal protection of computer programs.

⁷³ Urška Fric, Špela Stres and Blatnik, R. (2022). Software: Protection, Licensing and Rewarding Researchers in Computer Science – An Overview of Challenges in the European Innovation Ecosystem. *Informatica*, 46(9). doi:<https://doi.org/10.31449/inf.v46i9.4481>, p.3

Open-source software licences can be broadly categorised into two types: permissive licences and copyleft licences. Permissive open-source licences impose minimal restrictions on how software can be used, modified, and redistributed, allowing users to incorporate the software into proprietary projects without needing to release their own code. In contrast, copyleft licences require that any derivative works or modifications of the software be released under the same open-source terms, ensuring that the software remains freely available and open to the community.⁷⁴

Open-source software in the EU is primarily governed by EU copyright law, with particular emphasis on frameworks that enable both the protection of software as intellectual property and the freedom to modify, use and distribute it. The most significant pieces of legislation are the Software Directive⁷⁵ and the Copyright Directive⁷⁶. These frameworks ensure that open-source software licences are legally enforceable and that the rights of creators are protected, while allowing for the community-driven nature of open-source development.

⁷⁴ [Open Source Licenses - Definition, Types, and Comparison](#)

⁷⁵ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs, also known as the 'Software Directive', replacing the previous Council Directive 91/250/EEC on the legal protection of computer programs.

⁷⁶ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC

5 Trustworthy AI

5.1 AI within iDriving

The iDriving project's AI system is aimed at improving road safety, traffic management and incident management. It leverages advanced data analytics, machine learning, and real-time sensor integration to monitor road conditions, vehicle behaviour, and environmental factors. It processes data from a network of sensors placed on both vehicles and infrastructure, enabling predictive maintenance and hazard detection. The AI also powers warning mechanisms, providing real-time alerts to road users and infrastructure operators about potential dangers like accidents or hazardous conditions. Additionally, the AI supports the creation of Digital Twins, simulating road infrastructure to anticipate and respond to issues before they escalate, ensuring safer and more efficient transportation networks. Table 3 iDriving Pilots and Table 4 AI Development on WP Level below provide an outline of the development and use of AI within the specific iDriving pilots as well as on WP level.

Table 3 iDriving Pilots

Use Case Scenarios
<p>Use Case 1.1</p> <p>In Graz, Austria, urban roads are experiencing increased traffic, including automated and semi-automated vehicles. To manage congestion, UAVs monitor critical intersections and send real-time data to the iDriving system, which predicts congestion and suggests optimal rerouting. Ground-based cameras and vehicle sensors detect traffic violations and safety issues, such as helmet and seatbelt use. The system communicates with road users via smartphone notifications and roadside signs, providing safety reminders and alternative routes. Data analysis identifies frequent violation spots and times, helping traffic authorities improve infrastructure and compliance.</p>
<p>Use Case 1.2</p> <p>In Nevers, France, iDriving addresses increasing traffic and interaction conflicts by deploying integrated cameras and UAVs over critical areas. These devices monitor infractions like incorrect lane usage, violations at zebra crossings, and distractions among bicyclists. The data collected is fed into iDriving's Digital Twin to analyse road user interactions and identify infrastructure improvements. The Communication Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS) warns road users of potential incidents via Variable Message Signs (VMS) and mobile notifications, enhancing safety and compliance.</p>
<p>Use Case 2.1</p> <p>In Karlovac, Croatia, iDriving detects a pothole using sensors and UAVs, creating a 3D representation for quick assessment. Data is sent to local authorities for timely repairs, scheduled during low-traffic times to minimise disruption. Notifications are sent via</p>

mobile apps and Variable Message Signs (VMS). On repair day, safety signs and temporary speed limits are enforced, with UAVs monitoring the site. Post-repair, UAVs ensure quality, reducing future maintenance needs. Efficient rerouting and digital alerts minimise congestion and costs, ensuring smooth traffic flow and community safety.

Use Case 2.2

During heavy rainfall in Thessaloniki, Greece, iDriving’s weather stations detect water accumulation on roads, triggering alerts via in-vehicle systems, digital signs, and mobile apps to advise drivers on safe practices. For gusty winds, specific warnings are sent to two-wheelers. UAVs scan for hazards like fallen trees, and upon detection, notify drivers and update VMS with real-time alerts and alternative routes. Heatmaps from incident data guide users away from danger zones, enhancing overall road safety.

Use Case 3.1

On a major roadway in Romania, iDriving uses advanced sensors and AI-driven cameras to monitor traffic and detect dangerous driving behaviours. The system identifies speeding vehicles, erratic driving, and risky overtaking manoeuvres, sending real-time alerts to drivers and road managers. VMS and in-vehicle notifications warn other road users of potential hazards. Data analysis helps predict accident hotspots, providing heatmaps to authorities for targeted safety measures and infrastructure improvements.

Use Case 3.2

On a rainy evening in Bizkaia, Spain, a two-vehicle collision on ‘Road 1’ was detected by iDriving sensors and cameras. The system immediately alerted local emergency services and managed traffic using UAVs for real-time data and predictive analytics for optimal emergency routes. Electronic signboards and digital alerts advised drivers to reroute and slow down. The system collected comprehensive data, including videos and a 3D accident representation, for future investigations, helping to understand the accident’s causes and prevent similar incidents.

Table 4 AI Development on WP Level

AI Development on WP level	
WP3	Focuses on building a low-latency interoperable network for vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication, creating real-time traffic management and safety alerts, deploying drone surveillance for incident management, and utilising AI-guided UAVs for optimised safety monitoring. ⁷⁷
WP4	Aims to implement real-time edge computing for road monitoring, use AI to analyse road user behaviour, identify maintenance needs, provide

⁷⁷ GA.

	real-time environmental hazard alerts, and create 3D AI-driven representations for enhanced safety and maintenance. ⁷⁸
WP5	Aims to use digital technologies for enhanced road safety and maintenance. It focuses on AI enriched KPI updating SCC, integration activities, Digital Twin for predictive safety and real-time alerts, dynamic management of maintenance activities, and a Digital Twin-based control centre with XR features.

5.2 Legal Framework

5.2.1 The AI Act

5.2.1.1 Objectives

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence,⁷⁹ hereafter referred to as the “AI Act,” aims to enhance the internal market and promote human-centric and trustworthy AI, ensuring the protection of health, safety, and fundamental rights against the harmful effects of AI while fostering innovation. It establishes harmonised rules for the marketing, service, and use of AI systems in the EU, including prohibitions on certain practices and specific requirements for high-risk systems. Additionally, it sets transparency rules, regulates general-purpose AI models, and includes market monitoring provisions, with a focus on supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups, creating a framework for safe and effective AI throughout the EU.

5.2.1.2 Scope

The Regulation applies to providers of AI systems or general-purpose AI models sold or used within the EU, regardless of their location. It also encompasses

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ REGULATION (EU) 2024/1689 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), available at: [*Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations \(EC\) No 300/2008, \(EU\) No 167/2013, \(EU\) No 168/2013, \(EU\) 2018/858, \(EU\) 2018/1139 and \(EU\) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, \(EU\) 2016/797 and \(EU\) 2020/1828 \(Artificial Intelligence Act\)Text with EEA relevance. \(europa.eu\).](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj)

deployers of AI systems located in the EU, as well as providers and deployers from outside the EU whose AI systems are utilised within the Union. Additionally, the Regulation covers importers, distributors, product manufacturers that integrate AI systems, and individuals in the EU who are affected by these systems. Specific articles of the Regulation apply to high-risk AI systems linked to products covered by EU legislation.

Exclusions from the Regulation include national security and military AI systems, personal non-professional use of AI, and free and open-source systems unless classified as high-risk.⁸⁰ The Regulation does not extend to AI used exclusively for scientific research.⁸¹ It maintains existing EU laws on data protection and privacy and permits Member States to implement laws or agreements that provide enhanced protections for workers regarding the use of AI systems by employers.

5.2.2 Risk Assessment Methodology under the AI Act

Figure 1 AI Risk Levels

5.2.2.1 Unacceptable Risk (Prohibited AI systems)

Article 5 of the AI Act prohibits certain AI systems, classifying the risk that they pose to society as unacceptable. Such systems are for examples biometric categorisation systems, social scoring systems, systems assessing the risk of an individual committing criminal offence and systems inferring emotions in workplaces or educational institutions among others. They pose a serious threat to human rights and fundamental EU principles and values and are therefore prohibited.

5.2.2.2 High-Risk AI Systems

High-risk AI systems are the AI systems mostly affected by the AI Act. The developers and deployers of such systems are subject to stringent rules to ensure

⁸⁰ Article 2 of the AI Act.

⁸¹ Ibid.

that the systems will operate safely, in accordance with EU legislation such as the GDPR and the EU Charter. For an AI system to be classified as high-risk, it needs to satisfy the criteria established under Article 6 of the AI Act. The provision defines high-risk AI systems as those that either serve as safety components or are products regulated by EU laws listed in Annex I,⁸² necessitating a third-party conformity assessment under those laws.⁸³ Additionally, AI systems referred to in Annex III are also considered high-risk,⁸⁴ unless they perform specific tasks such as narrow procedural functions, enhance outcomes of previously completed human activities, identify decision-making patterns without influencing prior human assessments, or prepare for assessments relevant to Annex III.⁸⁵

In simpler terms, high-risk AI systems are those integral to safety or regulated products requiring external validation, or those used in critical applications unless they are limited to procedural tasks, assist human activities, analyse decision patterns without altering human decisions, or support assessments in specific contexts.

Furthermore, Articles 8-17 of the AI Act establish strict obligations of high-risk AI providers, including data governance, technical documentation, record keeping, instructions for use, human oversight, as well as the establishment of risk and quality management systems.

5.2.2.3 Limited Risk AI Systems

Limited risk AI systems are those imposing some risk to users.⁸⁶ Such systems must clearly inform users about their nature and purpose, and they must offer users the option to opt out of using them. Examples of such systems are chatbots and AI that generates or modifies content.

5.2.2.4 Minimal or No Risk AI Systems

Currently, there are no regulations on the development and use of minimal risk AI systems, such as video games and spam filters.⁸⁷

5.3 Ethics Framework

This section will begin by outlining the key ethical principles and requirements for trustworthy AI, taking a more general approach. Thereafter, it will outline specific recommendations for the iDriving partners on the actions they should take to align

⁸² Article 6(1)(a) of the AI Act.

⁸³ Ibid, Article 6(1)(b).

⁸⁴ Ibid, Article 6(2).

⁸⁵ Ibid, Article 6(3).

⁸⁶ EU Artificial Intelligence Act, High-level summary of the AI Act, available at: [High-level summary of the AI Act | EU Artificial Intelligence Act](#).

⁸⁷ Ibid.

with these principles and requirements, ensuring the development of AI systems that are trustworthy and promote the core values and principles of the EU.

5.3.1 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (hereinafter “Guidelines”)

The guidelines for trustworthy AI aim to promote the development, deployment and use of transparent and reliable AI systems.⁸⁸ As demonstrated in Figure 2 below, a trustworthy AI is one that is lawful, ethical and technically robust. This entails that AI systems should comply with the applicable laws, uphold ethical principles and values and avoid causing any harm.

Figure 2 Trustworthy AI

⁸⁸ Ethical guidelines for trustworthy.

**Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles
Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies**

5.3.1.1 Ethical Principles in the Context of AI Systems

AI systems developed within the iDriving project should adhere to the following principles outlined in the Guidelines:

Respect for Human Autonomy: Ensuring respect for human freedom and human autonomy requires that AI systems do not coerce, deceive or manipulate people, but rather enhance cognitive, social and cultural skills.⁸⁹ It further demands the adoption of a human-centric approach, where human oversight over work processes is ensured and “meaningful opportunity is left to human choice”.⁹⁰

Prevention of Harm: AI systems should be developed, deployed and used in such way as to avoid causing harm to humans, ensuring the protection of human dignity, mental and physical integrity.⁹¹ This entails that such systems should be safe and secure, technically robust, and safeguarded against malicious use. They must further ensure equality among all by addressing power imbalances and providing special protection to vulnerable individuals.

Fairness: The principle of fairness means that AI systems should ensure equal and just distribution of benefits as well as avoid unfair bias, discrimination and stigmatisation.⁹² It further guarantees that people have the right to challenge AI decisions and get fair remedies.

Explicability: the last principle of trustworthy AI requires that AI processes are transparent. The capabilities, limitations, and purpose of AI systems must be openly communicated, and decisions made by these systems should be understandable to users. This ensures that stakeholders can trust and effectively oversee AI systems, promoting accountability and ethical use.⁹³

5.3.1.2 Requirements for Trustworthy AI

Building on the 4 key principles established above, the Guidelines provide 7 specific requirements to guide developers and other stakeholders in the development, deployments and use of AI systems. While all requirements are equally important and apply to all AI systems, developers should pay special attention to

Human Agency and Oversight

AI systems should respect human autonomy by supporting individuals' decision-making and promoting democratic, equitable societies.⁹⁴ While AI can enhance

⁸⁹ Ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI, p.12.

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ Ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI, p.12.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Ibid, p.13.

⁹⁴ Ibid, p.15.

fundamental rights, it can also potentially harm these rights. In such cases, a fundamental rights impact assessment must be conducted before development, and mechanisms should be in place for external feedback on rights infringements. Users must be empowered to make informed, autonomous decisions and should have tools to assess or challenge AI outputs. To prevent manipulation and ensure human control, systems should allow for **human oversight** through various approaches—whether by direct intervention (HITL), monitoring during system operations (HOTL), or overall governance (HIC). The degree of oversight required depends on the AI's risk level, with higher-risk systems needing more extensive testing and governance.

Technical Robustness and Safety

This requirement is closely related to the principle of prevention of harm, as it demands that AI systems are developed in a way that is resilient to attacks, accurate, reliable and reproducible.⁹⁵ This requires developers to adopt robust security measures against hacking, data poisoning and model leakage to prevent and mitigate abuse by malicious actors. AI systems' results should be reliable, making clear and correct judgments and indicating the likelihood of errors. Finally, the results should be reproducible across various situations to ensure accurate descriptions of AI behaviour and prevent unintended harms.

Privacy and Data Governance

Privacy and data governance in AI systems is crucial to preventing harm and safeguarding fundamental rights. According to the Guidelines, a trustworthy AI system ensures user privacy and prevents unlawful discrimination against users based on sensitive information about them.⁹⁶ This further requires that developers address possibilities of any biases, inaccuracies and errors, prior to training with any given data set and document all processes from planning to deployment. Finally, strict protocols should govern data access within organisations, ensuring only qualified personnel with a legitimate need can handle sensitive data. This limits access and protects individual privacy effectively.

Transparency

Ensuring transparency involves ensuring traceability, explainability and communication throughout the process of AI development and implementation.⁹⁷ Thorough documentation of data sets, and decision processes is essential to enable traceability and transparency, helping identify errors and facilitating audits. Furthermore, AI systems must clearly explain their decision-making processes, providing timely, understandable information tailored to users' expertise. A balance must be struck between explainability and accuracy. Finally, AI systems should be

⁹⁵ Ibid, p. 16.

⁹⁶ Ibid, p.17.

⁹⁷ Ibid, p.18.

clearly identified as such, ensuring users know they are interacting with AI. Users should be informed about the system's capabilities and limitations and have the option for human interaction when necessary.

Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

This three-pillar principles provides for the development and deployment of AI systems that are fair, accessible and universal. It requires that AI systems address and remove biases in data sets and algorithms to prevent discrimination and prejudice. They should be user-centric, accommodating all users regardless of age, gender, abilities, or characteristics. Following Universal Design principles and accessibility standards ensures equitable access and participation. Furthermore, it is crucial that stakeholders are engaged throughout the AI system's life cycle to ensure the system meets the needs and concerns of all affected parties.

Societal and Environmental Well-Being

The development and use of AI systems should prioritise societal and environmental well-being, considering the interests of society and the environment throughout the AI lifecycle. AI should promote sustainability, ecological responsibility, and research into solutions for global issues, like the Sustainable Development Goals, ideally benefiting both present and future generations. Ensuring environmentally friendly AI requires assessing resource use and energy consumption throughout the system's supply chain, favouring sustainable options.⁹⁸

Accountability

The last requirement for trustworthy AI listed in the Guidelines necessitates that developers put mechanisms in place to ensure accountability for AI system's results.⁹⁹ This is to be guaranteed through both independent and external assessment of algorithms, data and design processes as well as clear procedures for minimisation and reporting of negative impacts. Furthermore, in cases of unjust adverse impact, developers should foresee accessible mechanisms for adequate redress.

⁹⁸ [*Ethics Guidelines for AI](#), p.19.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

5.3.2 The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment (hereinafter “ALTAI”).

ALTAI provides the final Assessment List for Trustworthy AI, which is to be used by designers and developers of AI systems for self-evaluation purposes.¹⁰⁰ The list builds on the one outlined in the Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and is grounded in the protection and promotion of fundamental rights and values. The assessment aids developers of AI systems in understanding the risks that such systems might pose to individuals, the environment and the society, and help them minimise those risks, while also maximising the benefits of AI.¹⁰¹

¹⁰⁰ The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment (hereinafter “ALTAI”), available at: <<[The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence \(ALTAI\) for self assessment - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)>>, p.3.

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

6 Ethical Considerations of iDriving Implementation

6.1 Human Participation

The iDriving project envisions the involvement of human participation specifically, in WP2, WP6 and WP7, where workshops and questionnaires with stakeholders, along with training sessions for road users will take place. The participation of individuals in the project brings up several ethical considerations that must be carefully managed to ensure the safety, privacy, and equality of all involved. This section aims to guide the iDriving Consortium in recruiting participants fairly and transparently, as well as ensuring their safe engagement throughout the project.

Table 5 Ethics Assessment for Human Participation

Question	YES/NO
Does this project involve human participants?	Yes
Are they volunteers for non-medical studies (e.g. social or human sciences research)?	Yes
Are they healthy volunteers for medical studies?	No
Are they patients for medical studies?	No
Are they potentially vulnerable individuals or groups?	No
Are they children/minors?	No
Are the other persons unable to give informed consent?	No
Does this project involve interventions (physical also including imaging technology, behavioural treatments, etc.) on the study participants?	No
Does this project involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation (EU 536/2014)? (using pharmaceuticals, biologicals, radiopharmaceuticals, or advanced therapy medicinal products)	No

6.1.1 Recruitment of participants

Participants will be chosen based on their relevant knowledge and experience to ensure the information collected is accurate and pertinent. Additionally, participation will be completely voluntary, with reliance on signed consent forms

and information sheets. To ensure fairness, inclusivity, and respect for participants' rights, iDriving partners should follow several key steps:

6.1.1.1 Informed Consent

As already pointed out, informed consent ensures that individuals voluntarily agree to be part of the project after fully understanding its purpose, methods, potential risks, benefits, and their rights. This process is critical for ethical research and requires several key steps to be taken by the iDriving partners:

- Partners should provide the information sheet and consent form (Annex 1) in language and in terms that can be fully understood by participants.
- Consent must be given freely, without coercion, and participants should be reassured they can withdraw at any time without consequence.
- Information must include how their data will be protected, the degree of confidentiality, and how privacy will be maintained in line with regulations.
- Consent should typically be documented in written form, but depending on the situation, it may also be recorded verbally or electronically.
- Informed consent is not a one-time event but a process, meaning participants should be updated on any changes in the project that could affect their decision to continue participating.

6.1.1.2 Equity, Fairness and Cultural Sensitivity

As outlined in Section 2 of this Handbook, the iDriving project must uphold the EU Charter's principles of equality and non-discrimination, ensuring fair and equitable treatment of all participants. To support this, iDriving partners should:

- Facilitate equal participation from diverse groups.
- Ensure transparency by clearly communicating processes and decisions to all participants.
- Use inclusive language in all communications, ensuring that materials are clear and accessible to a broad audience.

Partners should further promote cultural sensitivity by respecting diverse backgrounds and perspectives.

6.1.2 Incidental Findings Policy

In the iDriving project, the use of advanced technology for monitoring and data collection can lead to unexpected findings, also referred to as "incidental findings," that fall outside the main project goals. Whether predictable or unpredictable, such findings should be handled legally, fairly and transparently.

The iDriving policy on incidental findings is designed to facilitate this process, by providing guidelines for handling any results that arise outside the scope of the original research objectives. Its purpose is to establish a clear framework for managing these findings, addressing aspects such as notification, documentation, follow-up procedures, and ethical considerations. The policy specifies the

responsibilities of those involved and offers guidance on how to appropriately manage and communicate these findings.

Incidental findings may put data collectors within the iDriving project in a position where they need to decide between maintaining confidentiality and sharing information with the relevant authorities. However, should any indication of unlawful activity arise during project tasks, it must be reported to the appropriate authorities, even if this conflicts with privacy policies.

The iDriving policy on incidental findings applies broadly across all project activities, extending beyond those involving direct interactions with individuals.

Table 6 Incidental Findings Policy Procedure

Step Procedure	
Step 1	Partners must always adhere to informed consent requirements. They should outline any potential predictable incidental findings in advance and modify the consent form as necessary, depending on whether the incidental findings pose risks or provide benefits (see Step 3a and consent form in Annex 1).
Step 2	In the event of an incidental finding, partners must notify LIF and the Project Coordinator to seek advice and support. Additional experts may also be consulted as needed.
Step 3a	<p>If research participants are involved, there are two scenarios:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the incidental finding concerns the participant or directly impacts them, it should be disclosed unless prevented by legal requirements or if disclosure could expose the iDriving consortium or relevant partner to liability or serious risks. • If the incidental finding does not directly impact the participant, disclosure is optional. Non-disclosure may be justified if there are valid reasons, such as commercial interests.
Step 3b	<p>If no research participants are involved, incidental findings should generally be shared within the consortium unless there are strong reasons against it, such as data protection issues or intellectual property concerns. Decisions on sharing such findings with third parties rest with the consortium. The decision to disclose should consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reliability and independent verification of the finding • Whether the finding has practical applications • An analysis of the benefits and drawbacks of disclosure • The relevance of the finding to the main project objectives
Step 4	Review research protocols periodically to further reduce the likelihood of incidental findings.
Note	

Incidental findings may not be immediately apparent and could become relevant years after the research, by which time their impact may also have evolved.

6.2 Environmental, health and safety

The iDriving project prioritises environmental considerations in alignment with broader sustainability goals and applicable EU regulations. Partners should comply with relevant EU environmental laws and directives, such as the EU Green Deal, which aims for climate neutrality by 2050, and the Waste Framework Directive,¹⁰² which promotes sustainable waste management practices. The Directive sets out key principles for waste management, ensuring it is carried out in a way that protects human health and the environment. It requires that waste be managed in a manner that does not harm human health, avoids risks to water, air, soil, plants, and animals, minimises nuisances such as noise and odours, and protects the landscape and areas of special interest.

Compliance with these frameworks involves implementing measures that enhance energy efficiency and promote responsible resource management throughout the research lifecycle. The iDriving team is responsible for establishing effective waste management strategies to mitigate electronic and hardware waste generated during the project. This includes ensuring proper disposal and prioritising recycling whenever possible. By adhering to these environmental standards, the iDriving project seeks to minimise its ecological footprint while contributing to broader goals of sustainability and environmental protection at both the EU and global levels.

6.3 Research Integrity

The European Commission regards the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity as the main standard for maintaining research integrity in all EU-funded research projects.¹⁰³ The Code of Conduct, published by ALLEA (All European Academies), provides a framework for responsible research across disciplines in Europe, aiming to uphold trust, accountability, and quality in the research process.

¹⁰² Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives, available at: [Directive - 2008/98 - EN - Waste framework directive - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#).

¹⁰³ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, available at: [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity - ALLEA](#).

This 2023 edition reflects recent developments in data practices, open science, and research assessment.

The Code defines core principles to guide researchers and support an ethical research culture based on inclusivity, transparency, and societal responsibility. In conducting their research, partners should be governed by four central principles: reliability in design and methodology; honesty in conducting and reporting research; respect for participants, society, and the environment; and accountability from research conception to publication.¹⁰⁴

Table 7 Principles of Research Integrity

Four Principles of Research Integrity ¹⁰⁵	
Reliability	in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis and use of resources. This includes aspects related to verifying and reproducing the information produced by the AI for research. It also involves being aware of possible equality and non-discrimination issues in relation to bias and inaccuracies.
Honesty	in developing, carrying out, reviewing, reporting and communicating on research transparently, fairly, thoroughly and impartially. This principle includes disclosing that generative AI has been used.
Respect	for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment. Responsible use of generative AI should take into account the limitations of the technology, its environmental impact and its societal effects (bias, diversity, non-discrimination, fairness and prevention of harm). This includes the proper management of information, respect for privacy, confidentiality and intellectual property rights, and proper citation.
Accountability	for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts. This includes responsibility for all output a researcher produces, underpinned by the notion of human agency and oversight.

¹⁰⁴ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, available at: [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity - ALLEA](#).

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

The Code also outlines good practices in key areas. Partners should promote a supportive, equitable environment that prioritises integrity and ethical conduct. Training in research ethics is essential for all researchers, while transparent and inclusive practices in data management and collaboration are encouraged. Guidelines on publication emphasise accuracy, disclosure of conflicts of interest, and fair peer review to maintain trustworthiness in research outputs.

Research misconduct is categorised as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, alongside other unacceptable practices, such as misuse of influence, concealing AI use, and withholding data.¹⁰⁶ In handling violations, the Code calls for fair and transparent investigations, safeguarding whistleblowers and ensuring a fair process for the accused. Institutions are encouraged to act proportionately on proven violations and support those exonerated.

¹⁰⁶ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, available at: [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity - ALLEA](#).

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1 Information Sheet and Consent Form

Information Sheet

Dear Madam/Sir,

You have been invited to [insert description of the relevant activity here] under the framework of the European project Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies [iDriving]. iDriving aims to transform urban and rural road infrastructure through innovation, targeting improvements in driver behaviour, infrastructure safety, and first responders' effectiveness. Using a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, cutting-edge sensors, AI-driven alerts, and Digital Twins, iDriving is setting new standards for road safety.

With your participation you will make a substantial contribution to the implementation of [please insert:

- detailed explanation of the relevant task for which we invite participants,
- the overall procedure,
- its aim,
- how the outputs will be used and for what purpose afterwards, and
- how the person's participation will feed into the iDriving project implementation].

Your participation will involve:

- Example: questionnaire/ training.
- What will I be required to do? [Example: assessment, policy/ tool development,
- Where will this take place?
- How often will I have to take part, and for how long? [Example: for initial implementation; returning for second assessment]
- When will I have the opportunity to discuss my participation? [Debriefing]

Consent Form

I have been provided with information about the task and my rights as a participant.

In relation to this task:

- I agree to take part in the [specify the task e.g., training] as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end users' needs and objectives, which will be linked to the [e.g.].
- I agree that my personal data which is gathered in the course of and as the result of my participation in this task will be (i) collected and retained for the purpose of this project, and (ii) accessed and analysed by the [insert partner name] researchers for the purpose of conducting this [insert the respective task name].

I acknowledge that:

- My participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.
- My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.
- I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.¹
- I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, however without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.
- I am aware that I have the following rights as a data subject, which I can exercise with the controller:
 - ✓ The right to access.
 - ✓ The right to rectification.
 - ✓ The right to erasure.
 - ✓ The right to restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to be informed about recipients after a request for rectification, erasure or restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to data portability.
 - ✓ The right to object.
 - ✓ The right not to be subjected to automated individual decision-making, including profiling.
 - ✓ To file a complaint to my national Data Protection Authority.
- I am aware that the controller and processor of my personal data provided in the context of this participation is [insert partner name and address]. [Partner name] Data Protection Officer: [Name] (mail to [email address to be added]).
- I am aware that the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data are [insert partners' names]
- I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to [email address to be added].
- I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in this project, namely: [insert the purpose of the respective task here].
- My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by [insert partner name] researchers for the purpose of implementing this project. My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101147004.

In order to exercise your rights, as far as this task is concerned, you may contact the Project Management Office at [email address to be added].

By signing this document, I agree to:

- participate in [insert the relevant task e.g., this workshop] under the terms set out above and**
- the processing of my personal data,**
- appear in pictures taken at the event (for project communication and reporting activities).**

**Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles
Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies**

My signature confirms that I accept and understand these conditions without reservation.

***Date & Place
Signature***

Contact

Name, Surname; Organisation; Role in the project; Email

7.2 Annex 2 – List of criteria for assessing whether processing operations are likely to result in high risks

I. Header	
Name of processing operation	[name]
Controller’s contact point	[function and contact details]
Record of processing operations	[record reference]
DPO consultation	[date of feedback]
Approval	[name and date]
II. Criteria for processing ‘likely to result in high risk’	
Criterion	Applicable? Yes [if so, describe how] / No [if borderline: why not?]
1. Systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects or scoring, including profiling and predicting. Examples: a bank screening transactions in accordance with applicable law to detect possibly fraudulent transactions; profiling staff based on their transactions in a case management system with automatic reassignment of tasks. Counterexamples: standard appraisal interviews, voluntary 360° evaluations for helping staff to develop training plans.	[Y (how?) / N]
2. Automated-decision making with legal or similar significant effect: processing that aims at taking decisions on data subjects Example: automated staff appraisal (‘if you’re in the lowest 10% of the team for the number of cases dealt with, you’ll receive a “unsatisfactory” in your appraisal, no discussion’). Counterexample: a news site showing articles in an order based on past visits of the user.	[Y (how?) / N]
3. Systematic monitoring: processing used to observe, monitor or control data subjects, especially in publicly accessible spaces. This may cover video-surveillance but also other monitoring, e.g. of staff	[Y (how?) / N]

<p>internet use. Examples: covert CCTV, smart CCTV in publicly accessible spaces, data loss prevention tools breaking SSL encryption, tracking movements via location data. Counterexample: open CCTV of garage entry not covering public space.</p>	
<p>4. Sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature: data revealing ethnic or racial origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, genetic data, biometric data for uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or sex life or sexual orientation, criminal convictions or offences and related security measures or data of highly personal nature. Examples: pre-recruitment medical exams and criminal records checks, administrative investigations & disciplinary proceedings, any use of 1:n biometric identification. Counterexample: photos are not sensitive as such (only when coupled with facial recognition / biometrics or used to infer other sensitive data).</p>	<p>[Y (how?) / N]</p>
<p>5. Data processed on a large scale, whether based on number of people concerned and/or amount of data processed about each of them and/or permanence and/or geographical coverage: Example: European databases on disease surveillance. Counterexample: invalidity procedures under Article 78 of the Staff Regulations in a medium-sized EUI.</p>	<p>[Y (how?) / N]</p>
<p>6. Datasets matched or combined from different data processing operations performed for different purposes and/or by different data controllers in a way that would exceed the reasonable expectations of the data subject. Examples: cross-checking access control data and self-declared working hours following a suspicion of fraudulent declarations in an administrative inquiry (following the applicable rules). Counterexample: further use of data processed for a grant application when auditing the grant process.</p>	<p>[Y (how?) / N]</p>
<p>7. Data concerning vulnerable data subjects: situations where an imbalance in the relationship between the position of the data subject and the controller can be identified. Examples: children, asylum seekers. Counterexamples: delegates in a Council Working Party (for attendance lists),</p>	<p>[Y (how?) / N]</p>

members of expert groups (for travel cost reimbursement).	
8. Innovative use or applying technological or organisational solutions that can involve novel forms of data collection and usage. Indeed, the personal and social consequences of the deployment of a new technology may be unknown. Examples: machine learning, connected cars, social media screening of job applicants. Counterexample: 1:1 biometric access control using fingerprints.	[Y (how?) / N]
9. Preventing data subjects from exercising a right or using a service or a contract. Examples: exclusion databases, credit screening. Counterexample: determination of rights upon entry into service (e.g. expatriation or dependent child allowances).	[Y (how?) / N]
III. Conclusion	
Number of 'Yes' ticked above	[n]
Assessment: In general, if you tick two or more of the criteria in the list, you should carry out a DPIA. If you consider that in the specific case at hand, risks are not 'high' even though you have two or more 'yes', explain and justify why you think the processing is in fact not 'high risk'.	[explain]

7.3 Annex 3 - Data Summary

The tables below provide each partner's response to the DMP questionnaire created and distributed by LIF after the start of the project. This is the initial version of the completed questionnaire which reflects the information as found in the GA. As the project progresses, the questionnaire will be updated. The next version of the Data Governance and IPR Handbook will provide partners' updated responses.

The DMP Questionnaire consists of nine tables, each of which requires information regarding a specific category. The table are as follows:

- **General information** - ensuring that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.
- **Making data findable** - ensuring that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable.
- **Making data accessible** - ensuring that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorised users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices.
- **Making data interoperable** - ensuring that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems.
- **Making data re-usable** - ensuring that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public.
- **Data security** - ensuring that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected.
- **Ethical and data protection aspects** - ensuring that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data.
- **Allocation of resources** - outlining and documenting the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project.
- **Data processing overview** – ensuring comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project.

7.3.1 ACCELLIGENCE

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	ACCELLIGENCE
Team	Charalampos Chatzimallis, Martha Papadopoulou, Andreas Lefkatis, Dimitris Perikleous
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensor data (thermal, multispectral, and infrared) collected by drones - Data that will be processed by AI algorithms onboard the drone for incident detection and maintenance tasks - Communication and telemetry data from the UAV systems. <p>-----</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual identity assets (e.g., logos, banners, e-newsletters, promotional material) - Website and social media analytics data (traffic, engagement metrics) - News articles and updates, scientific publications and press releases shared on the iDriving website
Will you re-use any data?	<p>Yes, sensor data and incident detection results may be reused for further analysis and optimization of the AI algorithms and to enhance future missions.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Yes, website and social media analytics data will be reused to track the effectiveness of communication strategies and improve outreach efforts.</p>
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensor data originates from drones equipped with thermal, multispectral, and infrared cameras. - Data obtained for incident detection and maintenance tasks are generated through AI algorithms processed onboard the drone. - Communication data originates from the UAV's wireless systems such as the flight controller. <p>-----</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual identity assets are created by the design team. - Website analytics data is collected from Google Analytics and other web tracking tools. - News updates are generated internally and through project partner contributions.

<p>What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?</p>	<p>Sensor data: Helps in detecting incidents or required maintenance tasks and ensuring accurate aerial surveillance during missions.</p> <p>Incident detection / maintenance tasks data: Provides real-time intelligence for incident and maintenance tasks management as well as decision-making.</p> <p>Communication data: Ensures reliable and secure transmission between drones and the ground control system for rapid mission reconfiguration. (SO.1 Innovative communication protocols (WP3) - SO.2 Efficient and accurate monitoring services (WP3, WP4))</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Visual identity assets: Help in establishing a consistent and recognizable brand for iDriving.</p> <p>Website analytics: Provide insights into the effectiveness of communication and dissemination efforts.</p> <p>News updates: Keep stakeholders and the public informed about project progress and results.</p>
<p>If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?</p>	<p>Data will be reused for further improvement of AI algorithms, mission planning, and system optimization.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Analytics data will be reused to improve future dissemination efforts and refine communication strategies.</p>
<p>How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?</p>	<p>Collection: Data will be collected in real-time by drones and processed onboard using the NVIDIA JETSON platform.</p> <p>Formats: Data will be collected in raw formats (e.g., sensor data) and processed into structured formats like JSON or XML for incident reports.</p> <p>Size: The expected size depends on the mission duration and the amount of video and sensor data collected, likely resulting in a few GBs. ..</p> <p>----</p> <p>Collection: Data will be collected through Google Analytics, social media platforms, and content management systems.</p> <p>Formats: The data will be in structured formats (e.g., CSV) and unstructured formats (e.g., HTML for website content).</p> <p>Size: Data size is expected to be small to moderate, mostly in the range of megabytes for analytics and social media data.</p>
<p>How will you trace the collected data? (For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</p>	<p>Metadata will be collected alongside the data, including timestamps, GPS coordinates, sensor types, and incident classification. A unique identifier will be assigned to each data file for traceability.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Website analytics will include metadata such as timestamps, page URLs, and user engagement metrics. For visual identity assets, version control will be maintained to track revisions.</p>
<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>The data generation process is reproducible as the same mission and sensor setup can be replicated. If data is lost, backup procedures will ensure recovery, and missions can be repeated if necessary.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Data generation (e.g., analytics) is reproducible, and most of it can be re-collected. Regular backups will prevent data loss. Visual identity assets will be stored in multiple locations to ensure accessibility.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>Tools include AI processing platforms (NVIDIA JETSON), software for analyzing sensor data (e.g., infrared analysis), and data visualization platforms.</p> <p>-----</p>

	Tools include design software (e.g., Adobe Photoshop, Illustrator), content management systems, and analytics platforms like Google Analytics.
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	<p>Yes, ACCELI follows internal data protection policies, including encryption for data storage and transmission. The data security measures adhere to GDPR and relevant national regulations.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Yes, ACCELI adheres to data management policies that ensure compliance with GDPR, especially regarding web user data. Data is anonymized, and all analytics comply with privacy regulations.</p>
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	<p>Yes, data will be stored securely on servers with redundant backups. Cloud storage solutions may be used for large datasets. Regular backups will be performed after each mission.</p> <p>----</p> <p>Yes, visual identity assets and web content will be backed up regularly. Analytics data will be stored securely in cloud storage systems.</p>
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	<p>External entities like traffic management authorities and municipalities may benefit from access to processed data for improving incident response and traffic management systems.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Data may be useful for dissemination partners, media outlets, and stakeholders interested in promoting or engaging with the project.</p>

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE

[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]

What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	<p>Unique mission IDs will be assigned to each surveillance operation. Each dataset generated by the drone (e.g., sensor data, incident detection reports) will have a unique identifier based on the mission and sensor type.</p> <p>---</p> <p>A project ID (iDriving) will be used for all dissemination materials. Additional identifiers will include content type (e.g., "logo", "brochure", "website update"), and version control for updates (e.g., iDriving_Logo_v1.0.png).</p>
---	---

<p>What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?</p>	<p>No DOIs will be assigned for internal operational data. However, if research outputs or datasets are published, DOIs may be issued for public datasets through a data repository. For internal use, a unique mission-based identifier system will be employed.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Persistent identifiers such as DOIs will not typically be used for communication and dissemination materials. However, if any scientific outputs are produced (e.g., white papers), DOIs will be assigned through appropriate repositories.</p>
<p>What directory and file naming convention will be used?</p>	<p>A standardized naming convention that includes the mission ID, data type (e.g., thermal, multispectral), and timestamp will be used. For example: MissionID_SensorType_Date_Time.extension (e.g., ID123_Thermal_20241001_1400.raw).</p> <p>---</p> <p>Files will follow the naming convention: iDriving_ContentType_Date_Version.extension (e.g., iDriving_Brochure_20241001_v1.0.pdf).</p>
<p>Will you provide clear version numbers?</p>	<p>Yes, clear version numbers will be included in the filenames for processed data (e.g., ID123_Thermal_v1.0.json).</p> <p>--</p> <p>Yes, version numbers will be clearly indicated in the filenames of all dissemination materials.</p>
<p>Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?</p>	<p>Yes, keywords such as "drone surveillance," "incident detection," "thermal imaging," and "multispectral data" will be provided to improve data discoverability.</p> <p>--</p> <p>Yes, keywords such as "iDriving," "transportation," "smart mobility," "project dissemination," and other relevant terms will be included to optimize discovery and re-use.</p>
<p>What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</p>	<p>Metadata will be automatically generated and include mission details (location, date, time), sensor information, data type, and processing parameters (e.g., AI algorithm used). This metadata will be embedded in the data files and stored in separate metadata files (e.g., JSON).</p> <p>---</p> <p>Metadata for website analytics will be created automatically by platforms like Google Analytics, including details like traffic, bounce rates, and session times. Metadata for materials like brochures and presentations will include creation date, author, and versioning.</p>
<p>What standards will you for the integration of metadata?</p>	<p>The project will adhere to metadata standards for geospatial data to ensure interoperability and proper integration across systems.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Website and social media analytics will follow standard metrics and formats provided by platforms like Google Analytics. For dissemination materials, internal guidelines will be followed to ensure consistency.</p>
<p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p>	<p>Metadata may be structured to allow harvesting by repositories or indexing systems..</p> <p>---</p> <p>Yes, website metadata (SEO metadata such as titles, descriptions, keywords) will be designed to be harvested and indexed by search engines to enhance visibility.</p>

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	<p>Only anonymized or non-sensitive processed data may be made available for public sharing. Raw drone data containing sensitive information, such as location and incident data, will not be openly shared due to privacy and security concerns.</p> <p>--</p> <p>All communication materials (e.g., brochures, banners, website content) will be openly accessible. Analytics data (e.g., web traffic) may be shared in anonymized or aggregate form.</p>
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	<p>Open data, if shared, will be deposited in a secure, trusted repository with restricted access to authorized personnel. Processed and anonymized data may be shared through a data repository for research purposes.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Communication materials will be accessible through the iDriving website and potentially stored in an open repository for long-term access.</p>
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	<p>An institutional or project-specific repository will be used, with public datasets potentially deposited in a general-purpose repository such as Zenodo for broad access.</p> <p>--</p> <p>Data will be stored on the iDriving project website, and promotional materials may also be deposited in public repositories like Zenodo to ensure long-term availability.</p>
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	<p>Yes, data repositories such as Zenodo and institutional repositories are being considered for data deposition. These repositories comply with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and provide long-term storage and metadata management.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Yes, ACCELI has considered platforms like Zenodo and institutional repositories to ensure the deposition of dissemination materials in open and trusted repositories.</p>
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	<p>Users will need software capable of processing sensor data (e.g., thermal imaging software) and standard tools for viewing JSON or XML files for metadata. Specific data analysis tools may also be necessary for AI-processed data.</p> <p>--</p> <p>No specialized tools are needed; standard web browsers will be sufficient to access communication materials.</p>
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual</i>	<p>Yes, raw data containing sensitive or operational information will be restricted due to privacy concerns and security risks. Only authorized users within the consortium will have access to this data.</p> <p>--</p>

<i>restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	No restrictions are planned for communication materials. However, web analytics data may have restrictions based on privacy policies.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Metadata, including sensor specifications, AI processing parameters, timestamps, and location information, will be essential for interpreting the data both during and after the project. -- Basic metadata about publication dates, authorship, and project context will be retained to ensure future users can understand the relevance and purpose of the communication materials.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Data will be available for at least five years post-project, and metadata will be preserved indefinitely to ensure that the data can be interpreted and reused even after the original files are no longer available. -- Data will remain available for the duration of the project and beyond, with materials stored on the website and in repositories for at least five years post-project. Metadata will remain accessible even if the original content is no longer available.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata will be openly available under CC0, allowing it to be harvested and indexed by repositories, with clear links to access the data for authorized users. -- Yes, metadata for promotional materials will be openly available under CC0, providing clear access information.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	The project coordinator and the data management team at ACCELI will oversee the access process, ensuring that access protocols and restrictions are followed. -- ACCELI will oversee the access and dissemination process to ensure that materials are available to the public as intended.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Requests will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. For sensitive data, requests will need to demonstrate compliance with ethical and legal standards. Open data will be accessible through the repository interface. -- Data access for open communication materials will be straightforward, while specific requests for internal analytics data will be evaluated based on privacy concerns.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	For restricted data, identity verification will be done via institutional logins, project-specific credentials, or other authentication methods. Public data will be accessible without the need for verification. -- Public communication materials will not require identity verification. If requests are made for restricted analytics data, verification may be required through institutional or project-related accounts.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

<p>Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.</p>	<p>Yes, the project will follow metadata standards for general data documentation. This ensures compatibility with other datasets and systems, facilitating easier data sharing and integration.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Yes, metadata for website content and communication materials will follow Dublin Core standards to ensure ease of integration with other systems and platforms. For web analytics data, Google Analytics metadata standards will be followed.</p>
<p>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?</p>	<p>Yes, for the majority of the data types, such as sensor data and incident detection data, we will follow established standards. For example, geospatial data will use ISO/OGC standards, and AI-processed data will use standardized formats (e.g., JSON) with consistent labels for metadata.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Yes, all dissemination data, including website content and promotional materials, will use standard vocabularies for easier interoperability.</p>
<p>If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?</p>	<p>If project-specific vocabulary is created (e.g., for AI incident detection parameters or specific drone mission types), it will be openly published for reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers and practitioners.</p> <p>--</p> <p>If project-specific vocabulary is needed, such as for communication outreach strategies or metrics, it will be published and shared openly for others to reuse and improve.</p>
<p>Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?</p>	<p>Yes, all relevant data will be made available in machine-readable formats such as CSV, JSON, and XML, which will enable easy reuse by external stakeholders and systems.</p> <p>--</p> <p>Yes, all communication materials (e.g., logos, banners) and web analytics will be made available in machine-readable formats such as PDF, CSV, and HTML for further reuse by communication teams or external stakeholders.</p>

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

[embargo periods]

<p>Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i></p>	<p>Data may be reused by third parties upon request and approval by the data owner. --- Yes, all communication materials (e.g., logos, brochures, banners) and website content will be openly shareable and reusable. Web analytics data will only be shared in aggregate and anonymized form.</p>
<p>Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?</p>	<p>Data may be reused by third parties upon request and approval by the data owner . Only processed and anonymized data may be made freely available upon request. Raw data and sensitive operational data will have restricted access due to security and privacy restrictions. -- Yes, all communication materials will be made freely available in the public domain to allow the widest possible reuse by stakeholders, media outlets, and the public.</p>
<p>Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?</p>	<p>Yes, comprehensive documentation, including readme files, methodologies, and AI model descriptions, will be provided to validate data analysis and facilitate reuse by other researchers and stakeholders. --- Documentation related to the use of logos, branding guidelines, and dissemination strategies will be provided to facilitate reuse. Web analytics data will include aggregated summaries for validation.</p>
<p>What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)</p>	<p>Potential groups include research institutions working on AI and machine learning, traffic management agencies, public authorities, and disaster response teams interested in incident management. -- Potential groups include communication teams in similar research projects, media outlets, stakeholders in the smart mobility sector, and public engagement organizations.</p>
<p>Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?</p>	<p>Yes, restrictions will apply to sensitive or security-related data. Only authorized users within the consortium or those who meet specific ethical and legal criteria will be allowed to reuse restricted data. -- There are no major restrictions on the reuse of communication materials. Web analytics data will have some restrictions to maintain privacy and comply with GDPR regulations.</p>
<p>When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?</p>	<p>Data will be made available after initial processing and publication of the project results. There may be an embargo period of up to 12 months for certain datasets to allow for project publications. --- Communication materials will be available immediately after publication, with no embargo periods. Aggregated web analytics data may have a slight delay for processing but will be shared shortly after collection.</p>
<p>For what period will data remain re-usable?</p>	<p>Data will remain reusable for at least five years post-project, with certain datasets preserved indefinitely if relevant for future research and operational use. -- Communication materials will remain reusable indefinitely. Web analytics data may be available for five years post-project, depending on privacy policies.</p>

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Data will be licensed under Creative Commons licenses (e.g., CC-BY or CC0) depending on the data type. Processed, anonymized data will likely be licensed under CC0, allowing for unrestricted reuse. -- Communication materials will be licensed under CC-BY or CC0 licenses, allowing for reuse with proper attribution. Aggregated web analytics will be licensed under CC-BY with similar reuse terms.
--	---

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	The primary risks include unauthorized access to sensitive sensor data, data breaches due to the transmission of data between drones and ground control, and loss or corruption of incident detection data during transmission or storage. -- The primary risks include unauthorized access to the website backend, data breaches related to web analytics, and accidental loss or modification of communication materials.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes, a formal risk assessment has been conducted, which outlines potential risks and mitigation strategies such as encryption of communication channels and secure storage of sensitive data. -- Yes, a risk assessment has been prepared, addressing risks such as web-based attacks and data theft. Mitigation strategies include secure web hosting, regular vulnerability scans, and backups.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Technical measures: End-to-end encryption of data transmission between drones and ground control (e.g., using TLS), secure access protocols. Organizational measures: Access to the data is limited to authorized personnel based on the need-to-know principle. Physical security includes controlled access to offices where data is processed or stored. --- Technical measures: SSL certificates for website encryption, strong password policies, and two-factor authentication for accessing the website’s backend. Organizational measures: Access to web content management is limited to authorized personnel. Regular updates and security checks are conducted.

<p>Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?</p>	<p>Any sensitive data that may be collected by drones (e.g., sensor data, incident reports) shall be encrypted during transmission and storage using encryption.</p> <p>--</p> <p>Yes, web traffic data and communication materials stored online will be encrypted using SSL for transmission, and sensitive internal data will be encrypted for storage.</p>
<p>Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?</p>	<p>Additional measures might include regular audits of security protocols and updates to encryption standards to keep up with evolving cybersecurity threats.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Additional measures may include penetration testing of the website and continuous monitoring for potential vulnerabilities.</p>
<p>What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?</p>	<p>Data recovery protocols include regular automated backups to cloud and local servers, with disaster recovery plans in place to retrieve lost or corrupted data within.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Regular backups of the website and communication materials are in place, with the ability to recover data within a 24-hour window in the event of data loss.</p>
<p>Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?</p>	<p>In the event of a data breach immediate reporting to relevant stakeholders, containment of the breach, forensic analysis to determine the cause, and notification to affected parties in compliance with GDPR if personal data shall be carried out.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, a data breach response plan is in place that includes immediate notification to stakeholders, containment of the breach, investigation, and remediation actions. For breaches involving personal data, GDPR-compliant notifications will be issued.</p>
<p>Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?</p>	<p>Operational data and processed incident data will be retained for 5 years post-project for research and reference purposes. Critical data related to project outcomes may be stored for a longer period.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Communication materials will be retained indefinitely to maintain the project's legacy. Web analytics data may be retained for 3-5 years for future dissemination and analysis purposes.</p>
<p>Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?</p>	<p>Data will be maintained in secure institutional archives, as well as trusted cloud-based storage solutions that comply with data protection regulations. Long-term archives will be chosen based on their security and compliance with international standards.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Data will be maintained in the project's website backend and institutional archives. Trusted cloud storage providers will also be used for backup and long-term retention.</p>
<p>Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?</p>	<p>The management board and the DPO of ACCELLI, in collaboration with legal and security experts if required, will decide on data retention based on the nature of the data, security risks, and regulatory requirements.</p> <p>-</p>

	The communications team, in collaboration with the project management, will decide on data retention based on the relevance of the materials and potential reuse for future projects.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	ACCELI's IT and data management departments will maintain the data, ensuring regular backups and security updates for long-term storage. - The communications team at ACCELI, along with IT support, will be responsible for the long-term maintenance of dissemination and communication materials.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	Personal data will be anonymized whenever possible. For identifiable data, we will implement regular reviews to identify data that is no longer needed and ensure its secure deletion in compliance with GDPR Article 17 (Right to Erasure). - Any personal data gathered from web analytics will be anonymized or deleted once it is no longer needed, following GDPR Article 17 guidelines.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Yes, third-party cloud providers will be involved in the storage of encrypted data. They will not have access to the unencrypted content, as encryption keys will be managed internally. - Yes, third-party web hosting and cloud providers will manage encrypted backups and store web analytics data. These providers will adhere to strict data security protocols and GDPR compliance.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:

- Personal data;
- Data on criminal convictions and offences;
- Operational data for LEAs;

- **Personal data:** Potentially, if incident detection data includes identifiable individuals (e.g., through video footage).
- **Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection:** Yes, drone surveillance data may include information related to critical infrastructure during incident management tasks.
- **Commercial confidential information:** No.
- **Other categories (data on criminal convictions, operational data for LEAs, classified information):** No.
- Personal data: Yes, personal data may be collected through web analytics (e.g., IP addresses).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection, classified information, or criminal convictions: No.</p>
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>Protected data (e.g., critical infrastructure surveillance) will be obtained during drone operations. Data will be securely stored, encrypted, and accessed only by authorized personnel. After the project, the data will be archived or deleted, following legal and security requirements.</p> <p>-</p> <p>No such data is expected to be handled in this task.</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>The legal basis for processing personal data will be legitimate interest, as the data will be used for public safety and infrastructure monitoring purposes.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Personal data will be processed under consent (Art. 6(1)(a)) where required, particularly for web analytics data from users visiting the project website.</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>Consent will not always be feasible, as data will be collected in public spaces during incident monitoring. In such cases, legitimate interest will be relied on, and all reasonable steps will be taken to anonymize data where possible.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, explicit consent will be obtained via cookie consent forms for web analytics, ensuring GDPR compliance.</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>The project does not plan to process sensitive personal data as defined by GDPR Art. 9.</p> <p>-</p> <p>No sensitive personal data as defined by GDPR Art. 9 will be processed.</p>
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined</p>	<p>No such data will be processed.</p> <p>-</p>

by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	Not applicable.
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	It is not expected that children or vulnerable groups will be involved in the data collected for the purposes of the project. If any such data is collected inadvertently, it will be anonymized or deleted. - No, the project does not intend to collect data from children or vulnerable groups.
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	Any personal data collected will be anonymized or pseudonymized, ensuring that individuals cannot be identified from the data. - Any personal data collected will be anonymized or pseudonymized, and only aggregate data will be used for analysis.
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	If personal data is shared, it will only be with partners who need it for the project's operational tasks and will be handled according to data protection agreements. - Personal data, such as web analytics, may be shared with consortium partners involved in communication and dissemination tasks. The data will be shared in aggregate form where possible.
Will you engage in big data processing?	Yes, some of the drone-collected data could be classified as big data, especially when aggregated from multiple missions. - No, this task will not involve big data processing.
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	No personal profiling or social scoring will occur as part of this task. - No, profiling or social scoring will not occur in this task.
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	Minimal risk, as personal data will be anonymized or pseudonymized. However, there is a small risk of privacy violations if personal data is inadvertently exposed during incident detection. - Minimal risk is expected as data will be anonymized, and only aggregate web analytics will be used.
Will you engage in web scraping?	No, web scraping will not be involved in this task. - No, web scraping will not be involved in this task.
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data	No, personal data will not be transferred outside of the EU. (There is one partner from Switzerland (MOBILYSIS SARL). Our answer may require modification in the future depending on whether any personal information may be shared with them. It is my understanding that no personal data will be shared with any of the partners and if shared they will be anonymized.) - No, personal data will remain within the EU.

categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	<p>Yes, pseudonymization and anonymization will be used for any personal data collected during incident management. The data will be processed using automated tools to remove or obscure identifying information.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, web analytics data will be pseudonymized, ensuring no direct identification of users.</p>
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	<p>Yes, a review has been conducted, and only the data necessary for incident detection and analysis will be collected.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, only necessary web analytics data will be collected to track project dissemination effectiveness.</p>
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	<p>Yes, once data is anonymized, some datasets (e.g., incident reports without identifying information) may be made available for public sharing.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, anonymized web analytics may be shared to show project impact and dissemination reach.</p>
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	<p>The primary ethical concern is maintaining privacy and security for individuals captured by drone surveillance. All measures will be taken to minimize risks.</p> <p>-</p> <p>No significant issues are anticipated beyond ensuring GDPR compliance for web analytics data.</p>
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	christiana.themistocleous@acceligence.cy

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

<p>What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?</p>	<p>Financial: Budget allocated for data management tools, cloud storage services, and encryption software. Human: A dedicated data management team responsible for handling drone-generated data, data processing, and security measures. Technical: Encrypted cloud storage, servers for data backup, AI processing tools (e.g., NVIDIA JETSON), and software for data analysis and processing.</p> <p>--</p> <p>Financial: Budget for web hosting, analytics tools (e.g., Google Analytics), and external repositories for dissemination materials. Human: A communications team responsible for managing web content, social media, and data analytics. Technical: Web servers, cloud storage for backups, SEO tools for data management, and content management systems (CMS).</p>
<p>Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?</p>	<p>Yes, extra costs related to ensuring the data is interoperable and accessible may arise. These costs include paying for licenses to data management platforms and additional cloud storage. These will be covered by the project's allocated budget for data management.</p> <p>-</p> <p>There may be small costs for ensuring communication materials and analytics data are accessible and reusable (e.g., paying for metadata management tools). These costs will be covered through the dissemination budget.</p>
<p>Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?</p>	<p>Yes, fees for dedicated repositories (e.g., institutional or cloud-based solutions) will be covered through the project's budget under data management. Institutional repositories may offer long-term archival services at a fixed fee.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, fees for long-term storage of dissemination materials (e.g., brochures, logos) in dedicated repositories. These will be covered by the project's dissemination budget.</p>
<p>Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?</p>	<p>Yes, specialized IT support may be required for maintaining secure data storage and facilitating data access. These costs will be accounted for in the project budget and covered as necessary.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Yes, occasional fees for IT specialists to maintain the website and ensure continuous access to dissemination data. This will be covered by the allocated budget for dissemination activities.</p>
<p>What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?</p>	<p>Costs related to anonymizing and processing sensitive data, implementing encryption for secure sharing, and maintaining backups. Human resources will also be necessary for quality checks to ensure the data meets FAIR principles. Time investments will include several hours per mission to process and document data for public or consortium-wide use.</p> <p>-</p> <p>Minimal costs are expected, mainly for preparing materials for online sharing, ensuring data is properly documented with metadata, and maintaining backups of web content. This will involve human resources and regular content audits for accessibility and usability.</p>

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T3.4	Sensor data (thermal, multispectral, and infrared data), incident detection data processed by AI algorithms, and communication data between drones and ground control.	This data is essential for providing aerial surveillance during incident management and maintenance tasks. It enables real-time incident detection, data analysis, and decision-making during missions.	The data is collected directly from drones equipped with sensors and AI processing systems during surveillance missions.	Yes, processed and non-sensitive data will be shared within the consortium for further analysis, decision-making, and reporting as well as to support the other project and WP tasks.	Yes, certain datasets (e.g., anonymized incident detection reports) could be useful for external stakeholders such as traffic management authorities or municipalities. However, raw data and sensitive information may not be shared due to security and privacy concerns.	Technical measures: Data encryption for storage and transmission, secure communication channels (TLS), and regular backups. Organizational measures: Access to data is restricted to authorized personnel within the project, with regular security audits to ensure compliance with data protection policies.
T7.1	Website and social media analytics data, communication materials (e.g., brochures, logos), and content updates shared via the iDriving website.	This data is essential for managing and tracking the effectiveness of iDriving's communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring that the project reaches its intended audience and stakeholders.	Data is collected through web analytics tools (e.g., Google Analytics) and internal systems used for content creation and management (e.g., CMS).	Yes, aggregated analytics data and communication materials will be shared with the consortium to assess outreach effectiveness and improve dissemination strategies.	Yes, communication materials are meant to be publicly accessible, while analytics data could be useful for media or communication teams in other projects. However, web analytics data will be shared in aggregate form to protect user privacy.	Technical measures: SSL encryption for website traffic, secure access to CMS, and regular backups of all online content. Organizational measures: Limited access to web management systems, regular audits of website security, and strict adherence to GDPR for handling web analytics data.

7.3.2 CERTH

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	CERTH
Team	Nikolaos Dourvas, George Rakkas
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<p>Collection of:</p> <p>Visual data: High-resolution images and videos: Captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), roadside cameras, and vehicle-mounted sensors to monitor road conditions, traffic, and incidents.</p> <p>Telemetry data: Includes GPS coordinates, altitude, speed, and other flight parameters from UAVs for mission planning and execution.</p> <p>Production of:</p> <p>Object detection and classification results: Outputs from deep learning models identifying vehicles, pedestrians, road signs, and other relevant objects in real-time.</p> <p>UAV path plans: AI-generated flight paths and schedules for UAVs, optimized based on area size and resource availability.</p> <p>3D radiance field data: Data describing 3D objects that were created by using 2D images</p> <p>Defect quantification metrics: Measurements of road defects to prioritize maintenance activities.</p>
Will you re-use any data?	Yes
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), Roadside cameras and infrastructure sensors, Vehicle-mounted sensors, Existing data sources to be re-used, benchmark data from public datasets used for the evaluation of ML algorithms, Historical maintenance records and infrastructure data
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	<p>Improve AI models: By collecting/ generating/producing detailed visual and sensor data, CERTH trains and validates the performance of the models to cover the following objectives:</p> <p>Optimize maintenance operations: Data on road defects and infrastructure conditions will enable targeted maintenance, reducing costs and disruptions.</p> <p>Improve surveillance efficiency: Mission planning and resource allocation data will ensure that UAVs and sensors are used effectively for maximum coverage in the minimum possible time.</p> <p>Building a Digital Twin: The 3D scene data will contribute to creating a digital twin of the road infrastructure, facilitating early and real-time response strategies.</p>

<p>If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?</p>	<p>Image and video datasets: Incorporating pre-existing datasets of road images and videos from open source databases or our previous testing or public agencies to augment the training data for computer vision models</p> <p>GIS and mapping data: Utilizing geographic information system (GIS) data and digital maps from public sources or previous projects to provide foundational spatial information for mission planning and 3D scene generation</p>
<p>How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?</p>	<p>Visual data: Images in formats like JPEG, PNG, or TIFF; videos in MP4 or AVI. EXIF metadata, including camera pose information (GPS coordinates, focal length, orientation),</p> <p>3D radiance field output: Formats such as PLY, or other volumetric formats.</p> <p>Sensor and telemetry data: Structured in CSV, JSON, or XML files for ease of processing and integration.</p> <p>Processed data outputs: Typically in JSON or XML formats, containing structured results from AI algorithms.</p> <p>Mission planning data: Stored in JSON or XML formats to facilitate interoperability between systems.</p>
<p>How will you trace the collected data? (For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</p>	<p>Every data item (e.g., image, video clip) will be assigned a globally unique identifier using a standardized naming convention. Maintain detailed records of the data's lifecycle, including when, where, and how it was collected, processed, and stored. For UAV-collected data, log flight parameters, mission IDs will be recorded. Provide a clear title and detailed description of the data, including its purpose and contents. Record information about data ownership, licensing, and any usage restrictions. Use version control systems for datasets and code to track changes over time.</p>
<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>Reproducibility: CERTH has developed procedures for all data collection activities. These documents outline step-by-step procedures for operating equipment, configuring sensors, and conducting missions. All sensors and devices, including UAVs and cameras, are calibrated using standardized methods. Configuration settings (e.g., resolution, frame rates, sensor sensitivities) are documented. Metadata is recorded for each dataset, capturing all relevant details that would allow another researcher to understand and replicate the data collection process. CERTH usually utilizes open-source software for data collection and processing, ensuring that tools are accessible for replication. Data is stored in widely accepted formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, JPEG, MP4), facilitating interoperability and ease of re-use.</p> <p>Lost or unusable data: All data collected is backed up regularly, with frequency depending on the data's criticality and volume. CERTH uses multiple storage locations like on-site servers, off-site data centers, and secure cloud storage solutions.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>CERTH's UAV-based flight planning software will be used to visualize and process the missions and the paths produced. For visual analytics and 3D representation NVIDIA Jetpack SDK, TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras, OpenCV and game engines, such as Blender, Unity or Unreal, for the representation of data in interactive environments will be used.</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? (Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/department</p>	<p>CERTH during its broad experience in Horizon Europe projects in different clusters and areas has developed a series of methods to ensure that the data management guidelines are followed, and security policies are applied. Depending on the level of confidentiality CERTH can deploy role-based access controls ensure that only authorized personnel can access sensitive data. Authentication mechanisms, such as strong passwords are enforced. Data at rest and in transit could be encrypted if necessary, using industry-standard and European Commission's official encryption protocols. As CERTH operates within the European Union, GDPR governs the processing of personal data. Personal data will be processed only if there is a clear legal basis, such as informed consent or legitimate interest and anonymization is the first priority. Individuals have rights to access, rectify, erase, or restrict processing of their personal data. CERTH collects only the data</p>

<i>al procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	necessary for the specified purposes. Personal data will not be used for purposes beyond those initially stated without further consent.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	The data will be stored on high-capacity, high-performance storage systems optimized for large multimedia files and will be available only to authorized personnel. CERTH's Data/Server Center is equipped with redundant power supplies, climate control, and physical security measures. Regular backups will ensure data availability at all times.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	Government Agencies and Road Authorities could utilize data that will be produced on road conditions and defects to prioritize maintenance and repair efforts efficiently. They could also optimize allocation of resources for infrastructure projects based on accurate, real-time data. In addition, they could implement targeted interventions to reduce accidents and improve overall road safety. Finally, they could monitor the effectiveness of safety measures and adjust strategies accordingly. Emergency Services could also utilize the outcomes from CERTH to enhance their situational awareness for first responders through detailed visual data.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Those will be identified in the next months of the project.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Following the guidelines of the project (similar approach as in D1.1) and standards identified by the leader of T2.4 (in alignment with T1.4)
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Either directory or files will reflect the nature of the data but it will be decided in the next months of the project. It could be something like the following iDriving_NAME_Infrastructure_Images_v0.1 and iDriving_NAME_Infrastructure_Images_001.jpg
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	If requested, yes
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	CERTH: Metadata will be created like camera, UAV information, timestamp and details regarding the AI processing parameters (e.g. size of the bounding box, location of the bounding box etc).

What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	No specific metadata standard will be utilized
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	If required, yes

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	This will be clarified in the next months of the project after the definition of technical requirements.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Depending on the architecture, either from a direct access to storage location or asynchronous using message bus technologies
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	CERTH: (i) Data/metadata will not be stored in a PC during the execution of the trials. For the training and offline validation, the data will be stored locally on a PC/Server. (ii) Documentations will be stored on the project's repository, Sharepoint. (iii) Code and model's development will be stored locally in a PC/Server where development activities are performed. External access could be granted upon request and following the CA Background Annex
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	No
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Embedded tools of the operating system
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Most likely, such restrictions will derive from limitations and IPR. This will be defined in the next months of the project.

What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	The dataset as a whole should be retained to ensure efficient and effective processes
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	According to Article 20 in GA and in Data Sheet, the records of the project should be kept at least 5 years after the final payment.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	This will be decided in the next months of the project
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	CERTH's IT department and trained personnel.
How will you handle requests for data access?	CERTH will analyse the request and will decide for each different case how and if access will be provided.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	The person that asks access to data will send an official request with all the necessary details and after an internal examination and discussion with our legal department, we will verify her/his identity.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	
[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	No. Instead, a specific data model will be used
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	One unified data model for the project will be designed and developed to support various types of data
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes

Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes
---	-----

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Image/Video datasets
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	In cases that is required, yes
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Researchers, Traffic managers, Technological Companies
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	No such restrictions are foreseen
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	The data will be made available as soon as the model's reach their final implementation stage. There is no embargo period for upholding the data
For what period will data remain re-usable?	According to Article 20 of the GA, at least for 5 years after the final payment
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	This will be decided during the next months of the project

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	The major risks to the security of our data include unauthorized access due to weak access controls, potential cyberattacks such as ransomware or hacking attempts, accidental data loss or corruption during transfers or storage, and vulnerabilities in third-party tools or cloud storage providers.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	CERTH has a risk assessment that identifies the major risks to our data security, such as unauthorized access, cyberattacks, data loss, and physical threats to storage facilities. This risk assessment is reviewed and updated regularly to adapt to new threats and ensure the ongoing protection of our data throughout the project.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Access to data to authorized personnel through CERTH's VPN and password protection activities.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	No
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	Not at this stage of the project
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	RAID protocols will be used for data recovery
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Not at this stage
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	CERTH follows the guidelines from the EC regarding availability of data
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	They are going to be maintained in the project's server or cloud storage. This will be decided after definition of the requirements

Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	The organization follows national and EC legislation
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	-
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	To comply with GDPR requirements, CERTH uses anonymization techniques to all the data that processes and when they are no longer needed will securely delete the relevant data.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	CERTH: No

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; 	No.
--	-----

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	NA
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	NA
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	NA
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	NA
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	
<p>Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?</p>	No

How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	In case of images and videos collection, blurring of faces will be applied to hide the identity of the people involved
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	No
Will you engage in big data processing?	No
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	No
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	No personal data will be collected
Will you engage in web scraping?	No
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	No
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	No
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	-
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying	-

the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	m4d_ethics@iti.gr

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Human resources to handle the data and equipment to process the data.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	No
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	This is not defined yet

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T1.1	Names, contact details (e-mails) of partners and occupation.	For the purposes of communication, proper tracking, management, and dissemination of results.	Directly from the partners in the consortium.	Yes.	No.	Password protected accounts for sharepoint, server access, and mailing lists.
T1.3	No Data needs to be collected	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
T3.5	Telemetry data: Includes GPS coordinates, altitude, speed, and other flight parameters from UAVs for mission planning and execution.	For the tool and algorithms regarding the path planning of the UAVs for monitoring activities	From the UAV autopilot and their relevant software or publicly available sources i.e. google maps through APIs	The data that are required by the consortium will be discussed during the next months and CERTH will decide on the types of data that will be shared	Yes, probably the data will be useful for other research centers or technology companies. IPR issues might be a restriction in sharing those data but will be decided in each case.	CERTH's policies on storage/equipment and access control
T4.1	Visual data: High-resolution images and videos:	For the detection of objects that will be defined in the next months by user requirements	Captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), roadside cameras, and vehicle-mounted sensors to monitor road conditions, traffic, and incidents.	The data that are required by the consortium will be discussed during the next months and CERTH will decide on the types of data that will be shared	Yes, probably the data will be useful for other research centers or technology companies. IPR issues might be a restriction in sharing those data but will be decided in each case.	CERTH's policies on storage/equipment and access control
T4.3	Visual and optical data, as well as metadata from digital capturing sources, such as telemetry and EXIF data, will be used.	For the identification of road maintenance requirements and road infrastructure deficiencies	Captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), roadside cameras, and vehicle-mounted sensors to monitor road conditions, traffic, and incidents. Additionally, publicly available datasets of road defects and pre-existing data will be incorporated to improve and evaluate our models.	The data that are required by the consortium will be discussed during the next months and CERTH will decide on the types of data that will be shared	Yes, probably the data will be useful for other research centers or technology companies. IPR issues might be a restriction in sharing those data but will be decided in each case.	CERTH's policies on storage/equipment and access control

<p>T4.5</p>	<p>Visual data: High-resolution images / videos: Captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), roadside cameras, and vehicle-mounted optical sensors to monitor road conditions, traffic, and incidents. LiDAR and depth data will also be used, if available.</p>	<p>For the 3D generation of scenes for enhances safety and maintenance monitoring highlighting potential risks with greater accuracy</p>	<p>Captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), roadside cameras, and vehicle-mounted optical sensors to monitor road conditions, traffic, and incidents. Also, benchmark data from public datasets such as Replica, GO-SLAM, HI-SLAM will be used.</p>	<p>The data that are required by the consortium will be discussed during the next months and CERTH will decide on the types of data that will be shared</p>	<p>This is not yet something that can be answered</p>	<p>CERTH's policies on storage/equipment and access control</p>
--------------------	---	--	---	---	---	---

7.3.3 DREVEN

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	DREVEN
Team	Zoi Dimitriadou
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	We will generate and collect raw data, text, numerical data, code, and maps.
Will you re-use any data?	We will re-use global model data (ECMWF) from open-source weather forecast models.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	The data will originate from open databases, published papers, data from literature, and meteorological station data.
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	The collection of real-time data from existing and newly placed meteorological stations will support the project's objectives by providing current conditions. High-resolution data will be generated for the areas of interest to enhance accuracy. Additionally, algorithms and AI-generated meteorological warnings will be developed to improve forecasting and decision-making.
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	We will re-use the meteorological forecast data for initializing and setting boundary conditions, used for weather forecasting within the project.
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	We will collect and process data from weather stations, open-source servers, and online repositories. The data will be in formats such as .nc, .txt, .csv, .grib, .pdf, and .tiff, with an expected size likely in the order of gigabytes (GBs).
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	We will trace the collected data according to project guidelines using appropriate logs, annotations, tags, and identifiers to ensure proper provenance and metadata tracking.

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Yes, the process of data generation will be reproducible. In the event that collected data is lost or becomes unusable, we have stable sources, data backups, and redundancy measures in place according to SharePoint and project timelines to ensure data integrity.
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	Yes, the tools will include WRF, Python, and the hardware for meteorological stations.
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	Yes, our institution adheres to data management guidelines that include compliance with GDPR and project policies. We ensure explicit consent is obtained, provide data subjects with the right to access their personal data, and implement consent management practices. Additionally, our data security policy encompasses authentication, encryption, and access control to protect both personal and non-personal data, in accordance with relevant national, funder, sectorial, and departmental procedures.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	We follow SharePoint guidelines for storage and maintain backups on in-house servers.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	To be decided

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Identifiers will be assigned according to Zenodo guidelines.

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Data will be deposited in Zenodo, with appropriate DOI assignments for documentation.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Naming conventions will follow project guidelines or Zenodo standards if published, with self-descriptive versioning for file names.
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes. Starting from V0.1.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Keywords will be provided with appropriate metadata to optimize discovery and re-use.
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	Metadata will be created according to Zenodo guidelines.
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	Standards for the integration of metadata will follow Zenodo guidelines.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Metadata will be offered in a manner that allows for harvesting and indexing, in line with Zenodo guidelines.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	The data produced and/or used in the project is not expected to be publicly available; however, deliverables and other project outcomes will be made public.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	If released, data will be accessible through Zenodo or other appropriate depositories.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	If released, it will be through Zenodo.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted	If released, depositing data in a trusted repository like Zenodo does not require any special arrangements.

repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Access to the data will follow Zenodo guidelines.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	If published openly, data will be accessible to everyone; however, data in SharePoint will be available only to authorized users.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Metadata and appropriate documentation need to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Data availability and findability will be maintained per project and Zenodo guidelines.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Available in Zenodo with adequate information.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	Data management officer.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Per project, Zenodo and data specific guidelines.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	In SharePoint, only authorized users can access the data, while access in Zenodo will follow Zenodo guidelines for identity verification.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE
[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	To be decided.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	To be decided.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	To be decided.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes, if possible.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	As much as possible.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	As much as possible.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	To be decided (readme, codebooks and appropriate documentations will be provided).
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Interested groups include researchers, meteorologists, and regional/local authorities.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	To be decided.

When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Data will be made available for re-use according to the project process.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	It will remain re-usable for as long as possible.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CCO)?	The data will be licensed for re-use as openly as possible or as closed as necessary, depending on the circumstances.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Major risks to the security of the data include potential attacks, data breaches, or hardware malfunctions; however, the specific risks are not fully known.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	n/a
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Technical measures include data protection policies, access control encryption, and secure backup. Organizational measures consist of multifactor authentication, single sign-on, and an incident response plan with a dedicated team.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	n/a
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	n/a
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Data recovery protocols include regular backups per SharePoint guidelines, both on-site and in the cloud, along with critical data identification.

Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Recovery protocols are outlined for different instances, such as file-level and system-level breaches.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	Decisions on long-term preservation and retention duration have not yet been made.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Data maintenance will likely be in Zenodo or SharePoint, with appropriate data archives to be determined.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	Decisions regarding what data will be kept and for how long will be made per project agreement.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	The IT and technical team will maintain the data for the long term.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	To ensure compliance with GDPR, a clear data retention policy will be established, along with an automated data deletion procedure for personal data that is no longer required.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	No

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>yes</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR,</p>	<p>n/a</p>

which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	n/a
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	n/a
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	The identity of project participants will be protected according to the project protection plan, which includes measures such as anonymization, removal of identifiers, and encryption.
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	n/a
Will you engage in big data processing?	yes
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	no
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	no
Will you engage in web scraping?	no
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment	n/a

and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Per project guidelines.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	no
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	n/a
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	n/a
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	The contact for the organization's Data Protection Officer (DPO) is Stavros Tekes. (stavros@draxis.gr)

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

DREVEN will generate, produce and collect only operational data (no personal data). As such, the same answers apply to all types of data.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	They will be allocated as per the project agreement, including financial, human, and technical resources.

Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	As per cost agreements.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	As per cost agreements.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	Still to be determined.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	Still to be determined.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T4.4	Meteorological data, raw data, text, numerical data, code, and maps	To support real-time analysis, generate high-resolution data, and develop algorithms for forecasting	Collected from meteorological stations, open databases, and online repositories	Yes	Yes, excluding certain data that will only be available to project members due to project constraints.	Data protection policies, access control encryption, anonymization, removal of identifiers, encryption, multifactor authentication, incident response plan

7.3.4 Netcompany-Intrasoft

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	INTRA
Team	INTRA team
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Netcompany-Intrasoft will primarily collect logs generated from system interactions between partners. These logs will contain operational data and possibly metadata about the systems involved in the integration process. If needed, additional JSON, CSV, XML or PDF formatted system data may also be collected.
Will you re-use any data?	Not currently planned, but if system logs or metadata are required for further analysis or troubleshooting, they may be reused for monitoring, debugging, or verifying integration steps.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Logs will be generated by the systems of various project partners during the integration and communication processes. If applicable, system metadata will be collected from the respective systems of the project partners involved in the integration tasks
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Logs serve as a means to validate communication between integrated systems and to identify any integration issues or errors. System metadata, if collected, would aid in understanding the configuration and capabilities of the partner systems during the integration process.
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	Reused data (logs or system metadata) would be for debugging, verifying integration correctness, and continuous monitoring of the system-to-system interactions
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Data will be collected in text, JSON, CSV or XML format from system logs and interaction records. As for the expected size it will depend on the volume of interactions
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	The provenance of the data will be traced using timestamps, system identifiers, and interaction IDs included in the logs

<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>Yes, the process of data generation should be reproducible by re-running the system interactions. Logs can be re-generated by initiating the same system communications again. In the case of data loss or if the logs become unusable, Netcompany-Intrasoft could lose valuable insight for debugging or understanding the system interactions, which could delay problem resolution or affect performance checks. To prevent this, secure storage will be implemented, regular backups, and version control of log files to ensure that the data is preserved and easily accessible.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>Netcompany-Intrasoft expects to use several tools for data creation, processing, and visualization. These include log management tools such as the ELK Stack (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana) or similar for collecting and analyzing logs. Also, custom scripts, likely in Python or other languages may be used to parse and process the JSON, CSV, XML or text-based logs. If visualization is required, Kibana or Grafana may be used to make analyzing trends easier or identify issues in the data.</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i></p>	<p>Yes, Netcompany-Intrasoft adheres to strict data management and security policies. These include GDPR compliance for any personal data handling, though it is not expected to handle personal data at this stage of the project. Netcompany-Intrasoft follows internal data security policies that enforce secure data transmission, encryption, and access control for both personal and non-personal data. The company also adheres to national and sectorial data guidelines, ensuring compliance with EU data protection regulations and other relevant cybersecurity standards. Any policies specific to the project's funding authority or governing body will also be followed as they become available. Security measures include data encryption during transmission and storage, role-based access control to ensure only authorized personnel can view sensitive data, and incident reporting protocols in case of data breaches or unauthorized access.</p>
<p>Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?</p>	<p>Details on these strategies and processes will be defined during the task life cycle and will become agreed among the consortium</p>
<p>Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?</p>	<p>INTRA is not the data owner, and to our knowledge it is not foreseen at this stage. At this stage, there is no planned third-party access to the collected data. However, partners within the project might benefit from the shared logs to help troubleshoot their own system integrations. The logs and system metadata would only be shared with partners directly involved in the specific integration efforts. If the data proves valuable for broader research or technical improvements, it may be shared within the consortium under strict confidentiality agreements, though this will depend on the evolving needs of the project.</p>

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE

[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]

What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Project and data will be identified by unique system-generated IDs, including timestamps, system names, and interaction identifiers.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	No persistent identifiers like DOIs will be used, as the data consists mostly of logs. However, internal tracking will use system identifiers and timestamps.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Files will follow a structured naming convention: <system-name>_<timestamp>_<interaction-ID>.log or similar formats for clarity and consistency.
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes, all files and logs will have version numbers for tracking updates or changes.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Search keywords may not be relevant for logs, but internal metadata such as system names and interaction IDs will assist in searches.
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	Metadata will include system origin, timestamps, and interaction details, created automatically during log generation.
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	We will follow internal standards for log formatting and metadata tagging, ensuring consistency across all logs.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Metadata will not be designed for public indexing but will be accessible internally for search and analysis purposes.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	At this stage, no data is planned to be made openly available due to the sensitive nature of system logs.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Data will primarily be accessible internally to project partners through a shared platform. No public repository is planned as of now.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Data and metadata will be stored in the project's internal server or cloud infrastructure, accessible only to relevant partners.

Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	In case of a requirement to have the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository, as a first step we would have arranged for a Data Processing Agreement along with a list of technical and security requirements that should be confirmed among all interested parties.
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Data will require log management tools such as ELK Stack, as well as basic tools for handling text, JSON, CSV or XML files.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Yes, access will be restricted to project partners due to contractual obligations and confidentiality agreements.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	System metadata, including timestamps, system IDs, and interaction context, must be retained to properly interpret the logs.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Data will remain accessible for the project's duration and beyond, based on legal and contractual obligations. Metadata will remain accessible as long as required for audits or analysis.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	No, metadata will not be openly available due to the restricted nature of the data.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	Details on this matter will be defined later and will be commonly agreed among the consortium partners.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Requests will be reviewed on a case-by-case basis by project leadership, ensuring compliance with legal and contractual terms.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	Identity verification will be managed through secure logins, and access controls will be enforced within the project's system infrastructure.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	Netcompany-Intrasoft will follow internal standards for logs and metadata, which include system IDs, timestamps, and interaction context. No external vocabulary standards will be used at this stage.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	No, Netcompany-Intrasoft will use internally defined formats and metadata for logs and system data. These formats are project-specific but ensure consistency within the project.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	If any project-specific vocabulary is created, it will not be openly published due to the confidential nature of the project. Reuse may be permitted within the consortium.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes, the data (logs and system interactions) will be available in machine-readable formats like JSON, CSV or XML which allows for further processing and analysis.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Re-use will be limited to project partners. Logs and system metadata are not planned to be openly shared.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	No, the data will not be made available in the public domain due to confidentiality and contractual obligations.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Documentation for internal use, such as methodology and log structure, will be provided to project partners but not made publicly available.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Potential users include project partners who need to troubleshoot or improve system integrations. No external groups are currently expected to re-use the data.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Yes, only project partners can re-use the data for integration and debugging purposes. These restrictions apply for the duration of the project and beyond, based on confidentiality agreements.

When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Data will be available to partners as soon as it is generated. No embargo periods are planned.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	Data will be re-usable for the duration of the project and for as long as necessary afterward to meet contractual obligations or for system audits.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CCO)?	No formal licensing for re-use will be applied since data re-use is restricted to project partners under existing agreements.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	The major risks include unauthorized access to logs, data breaches, and accidental data loss due to system failures or cyberattacks.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	A formal risk assessment will be conducted, outlining mitigation strategies like access controls, encryption, and regular system audits.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Details on this matter will be defined at later stages of the project and will be mutually agreed upon by the consortium.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	Details on this matter will be defined at later stages of the project and will be mutually agreed upon by the consortium.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	Ongoing monitoring of security protocols and additional measures, like regular security audits and staff training, will be implemented as the project progresses.
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Details on this matter will be defined at later stages of the project and will be mutually agreed upon by the consortium.

Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Details on this matter will be defined at later stages of the project and will be mutually agreed upon by the consortium.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	Data will be retained for 3-5 years after the project’s completion, in line with project guidelines and contractual requirements.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Data will be stored in secure cloud infrastructure provided by the organization or partner institutions, and possibly in institutional archives.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	The project’s data management team will decide, based on contractual, legal, and operational needs.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	The organization responsible for managing the project infrastructure will handle long-term data maintenance.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	GDPR-compliant protocols will be in place to ensure personal data is deleted securely after it is no longer needed, including automated deletion where applicable.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Yes, trusted cloud providers may store project data, ensuring they meet required security standards. Specific details about the third party will be defined by the project’s cloud provider.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS
To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer
[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>Not defined at the moment since the elaborated discussions that need to take place within WPs 3,4 and 5 have not been initiated yet due to the timeline of the project. Our role within the project as the integrator is not to define the type of data to be collected.</p> <p>Until the architecture is defined (D2.3 Technical Requirements and Digital Ecosystem Architecture - M12) the integration scheme cannot be confirmed. Thus, nor if any type of data will be hosted by INTRA or if any responsible partner bringing in data will be hosting its own data.</p> <p>More information will be provided in the next DMP.</p>
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>Not defined at the moment</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>Not defined at the moment</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>Not defined at the moment</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR,</p>	<p>Not defined at the moment</p>

which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	No, it is not
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	No
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	Not defined at the moment
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	Not defined at the moment
Will you engage in big data processing?	Not defined at the moment
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	Not defined at the moment
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	Not defined at the moment
Will you engage in web scraping?	No
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment	Not defined at the moment

and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Not defined at the moment
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Not defined at the moment
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	Not defined at the moment
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	Not defined at the moment
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	Not defined at the moment

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Netcompany-Intrasoft allocates human resources, including data management and IT staff, as well as technical resources such as cloud infrastructure and data security tools. Financial resources are allocated for storage, backups, and security measures.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for	Any extra costs, such as for data storage or tools to ensure data accessibility and FAIR compliance, will be covered through the project's budget, which includes provisions for data management.

making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	Yes, fees may be incurred for secure data storage in cloud repositories. These fees will be covered by the project's allocated budget for data management.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	It is possible that specialized services may be needed for repository management or ensuring secure access. If so, these costs will also be covered by the project's budget.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	The main costs will involve time and effort in preparing data for sharing and long-term preservation, including formatting, documentation, and ensuring compliance with project guidelines. These efforts are expected to be managed within the existing project team.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T2.5	This task doesn't refer to personal data. Technical specifications, system architecture diagrams, and integration documentation will be used.	To define technical requirements and establish a clear architecture for the project ecosystem, ensuring all partners have a common understanding.	The data will be generated internally through team discussions, design sessions, and documentation reviews with project partners.	Yes, this data will be shared with all consortium partners to ensure alignment and collaboration on technical requirements.	The data could be useful for similar projects or stakeholders interested in ecosystem architecture. However, sharing may be restricted due to proprietary information and confidentiality agreements within the consortium.	Data will be protected through access controls, encryption, and secure document sharing platforms. Organizationally, all team members will adhere to confidentiality protocols.
T5.2	Logs generated from the integration of various systems and interfaces between partner systems.	To facilitate the integration of services, track system interactions, and ensure effective communication between different components of the ecosystem.	Data will be collected from the various systems implemented by project partners as part of the integration efforts.	Yes, log data will be shared within the consortium to troubleshoot issues and enhance integration.	The logs could be beneficial for other organizations involved in road safety or system integration projects. However, sharing may be limited due to privacy concerns or contractual obligations.	The logs will be secured through encryption and controlled access. Organizationally, data sharing will follow strict guidelines to protect sensitive information

7.3.5 MobiLysis

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	MobiLysis
Team	Manos Barmpounakis
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Multimodal vehicles trajectories collected by swarm of drones
Will you re-use any data?	No
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Drones
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	it will provide insights on vehicle interactions to enhance safety
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Drones will fly over specific areas and will record aerial footage. Then, the videos will be processed by a Computer Vision algorithm that will detect and track vehicles and provide their detailed trajectories. The size of the data collected depends on the number of drones used and the recording time. Trajectories will be anonymised and described in UTM or WGS84 coordinates. They will be saved in csv files.
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	The data and associated metadata will be collected, processed and stored by MobiLysis.

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	The collection of the aerial video footage is reproducible by flying drones in the same locations at any time as weather conditions allow it. However, the processing of these videos in order to produce multimodal video trajectories can be reproduced only by MobilLysis as it is part of our IP.
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	An internal computer vision algorithm that processes the aerial video footage to detect and track vehicles. The vehicle trajectories are then described in the WGS-84 system.
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	In case of online storing data, MobilLysis is saving its data using all the security protocols provided by such services. Any other data are saved in password protected and encrypted HDDs.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	The collected videos will be saved in our (password protected) HDDs. Same for trajectories. The trajectories though can be stored in an iDriving repository for use from the rest of the partners. In case of opening the dataset for research purposes in a database like Zenodo or similar.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	No third party can benefit from such data.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Trajectories will be described with a unique numerical ID, UTM/WGS84 coordinates, date in IS8601 format and the type of vehicle.

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	YYYY-MM-DD/DX/trajectories_YYYY-MM-DD_DX_AM/PMY (YYYY-MM-DD refers to the date, DX to the drone number, AM/PMY to the flight session)
Will you provide clear version numbers?	No
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	No
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	No
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	-
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Location of the flying of the drones, explanation of headers at the csv file with the trajectories

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Trajectories will be shared with partners on request.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Data will be shared through OneDrive. In case of an open dataset for research purposes, we will use existing repositories like Zenodo.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Videos and trajectories will be saved in encrypted and password-protected HDDs. Only trajectories will be shared online with partners on request.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	We have previously uploaded data in Zenodo and we are fully aware of the process and requirements.

What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Trajectories will be saved in csv files, so any csv reader can be used.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	The aerial video footage that can be collected by the drones will be accessible only by MobiLysis. The trajectories will be accessible by all partners after request.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	The files will be self-explanatory (for example, column name will describe the contents of the file) so no extra information is needed. In either case, the associated metadata file will include an explanation of the column names.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	According to Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA).
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, part of the data can be shared online according to CA agreement.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	Through log in credentials in Zenodo.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Trajectories will be shared on request using OneDrive.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	Through log in credentials in Zenodo.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to	Trajectories will be described in the WGS84 coordinate system, with longitude and latitude coordinates. The time will follow the ISO8601 format.
--	--

facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	-
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes. The formats we previously described are machine-readable.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes, the vehicle trajectories.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes, the vehicle trajectories.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, with the metadata of the dataset.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Traffic engineers, Transport engineers, data scientists
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	No restrictions.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	At the end of the project. No embargo periods.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	Forever – according to Zenodo guidelines.

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes, CC BY-NC 4.0.
--	--------------------

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	HDDs being lost or destroyed.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes, we keep a back-up for every dataset.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	All our HDDs are password-protected and encrypted.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	Data are saved in password protected and encrypted HDDs.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	-
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	-
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	-
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long	According to GA and CA agreements.

should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Trajectories in Zenodo and Videos in the HDDs.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	Swiss law for videos and GA and CA agreements for trajectories.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	MobilLysis CEO.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	No personal data are associated with our data.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	No third party is involved.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:

- Personal data;
- Data on criminal convictions and offences;
- Operational data for LEAs;

No

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>Drones collect anonymized data. With their oblique view no faces or vehicle plate numbers are visible, such any information we collect is cannot related to personal data. The videos are processed by a Computer Vision algorithm which is trained to identify solely vehicles and other moving objects (such as pedestrians, bicycles, etc.)</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	<p>-</p>

Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	-
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	We do not know the ID of any of the participants. It's anonymous from the collection point.
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	-
Will you engage in big data processing?	-
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	No.
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	No.
Will you engage in web scraping?	No.
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	No.
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	The data we collect are already anonymised as due to the vertical view, the altitude and the no-zoom capabilities no facial characteristics can be identified, nor can we see the vehicle plate number. Thus, the information we collect cannot in any way relate to any personal information.

	The trajectories that will be produced and shared will include a unique vehicle ID, the type of vehicle, and its trajectory in UTM/WGS-84 coordinates. Their speed and accelerations can also be provided as derivatives of the location information. Thus no (pseudo)anonymisation is needed.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Yes.
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	No de-identification is needed.
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No.
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	Manos Barmounakis (manos@mobilysis.ch)

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Acquisition of HDDs, processing of data by PC which is operated by data scientists.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Our data follow the FAIR principles.

Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	The data we produce are ready to be shared and preserved. No additional efforts is needed.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T3.2	Sensor data such as data cameras, GPS and drones	To identify a range of traffic conditions that pose safety risks, including accidents, high congestion, and maintenance activities.	Camera and GPS data from local partners. Drone data from drone experiments.	Yes, upon request.	TBD later in the project	Data are stored locally (password protected) and in online services using their standardized safety protocols.

7.3.6 Université Gustave Eiffel

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	Université Gustave Eiffel
Team	Latifa Oukhellou (Leader), Mahdi Zargayouna, Mostafa Ameli, Laurent Bouillaut, Mustapha Tendjaoui
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from UAVs and ground cameras (video feeds) capturing traffic patterns, road user behavior, and safety incidents. - Traffic data, including vehicular speeds, congestion levels, and flow rates. - Road user behavior data, such as lane violations, zebra crossing compliance, and use of hand signals by bicyclists, extracted from camera and UAV feeds. - Data from UAVs and ground cameras (video feeds) capturing traffic patterns, road user behavior, and safety incidents. - Traffic data, including vehicular speeds, congestion levels, and flow rates. - Road user behavior data, such as lane violations, zebra crossing compliance, and use of hand signals by bicyclists, extracted from camera and UAV feeds.
Will you re-use any data?	Yes, previously collected traffic data and road user behavior data will be re-used to benchmark changes and improvements in infrastructure sharing.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New data: Collected from UAVs and ground cameras deployed in Nevers. - Pre-existing traffic data: Expected from the City of Nevers (pending confirmation). - Pre-existing road user behavior data: Provided through partner repositories or previous project datasets.
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UAV and camera data: To monitor infrastructure sharing across diverse users (vehicles, bicycles, pedestrians) and to infer safety indicators by identifying behaviors, violations, and risky situations. - Traffic data: To analyze congestion patterns, optimize infrastructure, and improve traffic flow through predictive models and simulations.
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-used traffic data: Benchmark improvements in traffic flow and infrastructure sharing over time, assessing the effectiveness of interventions. - Re-used road user behavior data: Compare pre- and post-intervention road-sharing behaviors to evaluate safety improvements in multi-user environments (vehicles, bicycles, pedestrians).
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UAV and camera data: Collected as video feeds (MP4 format), with an expected total data size of ~1 TB. - Traffic data: Collected in CSV format (~500 MB). - Processed Data Outputs: Analytical data and predictive safety indicators derived from AI models and traffic simulations in various formats (CSV, JSON, MP4).

<p>How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i></p>	<p>- Each data point will be tagged with relevant metadata, including time, location, source device ID, sensor type, UAV/camera ID, and collection timestamp. A unique identifier will be assigned to each dataset for traceability, and version control will be implemented to monitor updates.</p>
<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>Yes, data collection protocols will be documented to ensure reproducibility. In the event of data loss, daily backups stored on secure servers with cloud redundancy will be used to restore the data. The detailed documentation and backup strategy minimize the risk of irrecoverable data loss.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualise the data?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-based video processing software: For extracting road user behavior data from video feeds. - QGIS and Digital Twin platforms: For geospatial data visualization and predictive analytics. - SUMO traffic simulation tools: For scenario modeling and testing infrastructure improvements.
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departement al procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i></p>	<p>Yes, Université Gustave Eiffel complies with GDPR for personal data handling and has robust data security protocols for secure data storage and management. Data protection is overseen by the Data Protection Officer, who ensures compliance with institutional, national, and C-ITS data policies.</p>
<p>Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?</p>	<p>Yes, all data will be stored on secure servers with daily automated backups and additional cloud-based redundancy to prevent data loss. A structured data storage hierarchy will ensure organized data access and retrieval.</p>
<p>Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?</p>	<p>The raw data will remain within Université Gustave Eiffel, but processed insights and results will be shared with the local government of Nevers and relevant transportation authorities. These stakeholders could use the results to enhance traffic management, optimize infrastructure, and improve road safety.</p> <p>Potential third-party beneficiaries may include EU regulatory bodies, academic institutions, and policy-making organisations. These entities could use the data for research purposes, regulatory alignment, or improving security protocols in similar projects, etc. The latter information refers to cases where Université Gustave Eiffel produces public deliverables. In the iDriving project, all deliverables that Université Gustave Eiffel will produce and contribute to will be publicly available.</p>

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	- A unique project identifier (iDriving-NEVERS-2025) for all datasets. - Data files will have specific identifiers such as NEVERS_UAV_Video_01, Traffic_Camera_Intersection_A01, etc.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	- Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to final datasets intended for publication. DOIs will follow the standard data repository protocols, such as Zenodo or Dataverse.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	- Directories will follow the convention: iDriving/UseCase1.2/City_NEVERS/Date. - Files will be named based on the data source, location, and timestamp, such as UAV_Nevers_Mar2025_LaneViolation.mp4.
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes, all datasets will have version numbers (e.g., v1.0, v1.1) to track updates and revisions. Each new version will maintain clear documentation on changes.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Yes, keywords such as traffic data, road safety, UAV video, lane violations, Nevers, and urban mobility will be used to enhance findability and reusability.
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	- Metadata will include dataset name, description, location, timestamp, data collection method, data type, and responsible organization. - Automated logging tools will capture metadata for sensor-based data and UAV footage.
What standards will you apply for the integration of metadata?	- Dublin Core metadata standards will be used for general datasets. - For geospatial data, ISO 19115 will be applied to ensure compatibility with Geographic Information Systems (GIS).
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes, metadata will be made available through machine-readable formats (e.g., XML, JSON) to allow indexing by repositories and search engines.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorised users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
<u>Error! Reference source not found.</u> [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	- Data that does not involve personal identifiers, such as aggregated traffic patterns, road user behavior trends, and simulation results, will be available openly.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	- The data will be deposited in trusted repositories like Zenodo or Dataverse. Additionally, it will be accessible through the iDriving project’s official portal.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	- The data, along with associated metadata, documentation, and code, will be deposited in repositories such as Zenodo, Dataverse, and institutional repositories of Université Gustave Eiffel. In addition, we are planning to publish a subset of the data in the journal "Data in Brief".
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	- Yes, discussions have taken place with repositories to ensure data storage capacity, metadata compatibility, and long-term accessibility. Data will comply with repository guidelines for open access.
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	- Data will be accessible through standard tools like Excel, Python, R, and specialized tools such as QGIS (for geospatial data) and VLC (for video data). Some datasets may require specific API access for retrieval.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	- Yes, data from UAVs and ground cameras containing identifiable road user information will have restricted access due to privacy concerns (GDPR). Contractual restrictions also apply to data from vehicle manufacturers. Aggregated and anonymized data will be shared openly.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	- Metadata including time, location, data collection method, sensor ID, and format specifications will be retained to ensure the data can be interpreted correctly in the future.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	- Data will remain available for at least 5 years after project completion. Metadata will be preserved beyond the data lifecycle and will remain accessible indefinitely.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	- Possibly, yes, metadata will be openly available under a CCO license and will include information needed to access the corresponding datasets.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	- The Principal Investigator (PI) and Université Gustave Eiffel's data management team will oversee the access process and ensure compliance with access protocols.
How will you handle requests for data access?	- Data access requests will be processed through a formal application procedure where users must specify their purpose for accessing the data. Requests will be reviewed by the data management team.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	- Identity verification will be done through institutional credentials, email verification, and possibly two-factor authentication (2FA) for sensitive data.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Error! Reference source not found. **[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]**

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	- Yes, we will follow the Dublin Core standard for general metadata and ISO 19115 for geospatial data. We will also adopt IEEE standards for traffic-related data.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	- Yes, standard vocabularies for traffic data, such as DATEX II for real-time traffic information, and GeoJSON for geospatial data, will be used across all relevant data types.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	- If any project-specific vocabularies or ontologies are developed, they will be published openly, and we will encourage re-use, refinement, and extension under a CC BY license.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	- Yes, all data will be made available in machine-readable formats such as CSV, JSON, GeoJSON, and XML, enabling further reuse by external parties.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

Error! Reference source not found. **[embargo periods]**

Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	- Yes, non-sensitive data, such as aggregated traffic data, road safety violations, and anonymized user behavior, will be re-usable. Personal data will not be re-usable.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	- Yes, anonymized and non-sensitive data will be made freely available in trusted data repositories like Zenodo or Dataverse for maximum reusability.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	- Yes, complete documentation, including readme files, methodology descriptions, and codebooks, will be provided to validate data analysis and support reusability.

What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	- Potential users include transportation authorities, urban planners, researchers in mobility and traffic analysis, and smart city developers.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	- Yes, personal data will be restricted due to GDPR regulations. All other data will be openly accessible with no major restrictions, except for sensitive traffic data shared with specific stakeholders.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	- Data will be made available for re-use after project completion. Sensitive data may have an embargo period of up to 1 year.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	- Data will remain re-usable for at least 5 years after project completion. Metadata will be retained for long-term use.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	- Yes, data will be licensed under CC BY 4.0, allowing re-use with proper attribution.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	- Unauthorized access to personal or sensitive data, data breaches, loss of data during transfer, or system failures during UAV or camera data collection.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	- Yes, a risk assessment has been prepared, identifying potential risks and including mitigation strategies such as encryption, access controls, and regular audits.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	- Technical measures: Encryption (AES-256) for all sensitive data, password protection, VPNs, firewalls. - Organizational measures: Access control via PINs, CCTV in critical areas, data access limited to authorized personnel only.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	- Yes, personal and sensitive data will be encrypted using AES-256 encryption during storage and transmission.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	- Yes, multi-factor authentication (MFA) will be introduced for key personnel and periodic penetration testing to assess security vulnerabilities.

What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	- Daily automated backups to secure servers and cloud-based redundancy to ensure data recovery in case of data loss.
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	- Yes, a formal data breach response plan is in place, including notification to affected parties within 72 hours and prompt incident reporting to authorities.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	- Anonymized data will be preserved for at least 5 years. Certain high-value datasets may be retained for 10 years for future research and policy-making.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	- Data will be maintained in institutional repositories at Université Gustave Eiffel and trusted external repositories like Zenodo for long-term preservation.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	- The decision will be made by the PI and data management team, based on data value, reusability, and legal retention requirements.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	- Long-term data will be maintained by Université Gustave Eiffel and the respective data repositories where the data is archived.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	- A data minimization protocol will ensure personal data is deleted after a set retention period (based on GDPR requirements), with regular audits to confirm compliance.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	- Cloud storage providers may be used for encrypted backups. Local transport authorities (Nevers) may access specific traffic data for operational purposes.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:

- Personal data;
- Data on criminal convictions and offences;
- Operational data for LEAs;
- Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection;
- Classified information on national and/or international grounds;
- Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret).

Please answer as comprehensively as possible.

- Université Gustave Eiffel will process the personal data of our employees working on the project, as well as the personal data of project partners, including contact details and roles within the consortium, for internal project management and communication purposes. Additionally, the project will collect and process the personal data of road users as part of the research activities. This includes:

- Road user behavior data, such as lane violations, compliance with zebra crossing rules, and use of hand signals by bicyclists, which will be extracted from UAV and ground camera video feeds.
- Location data, which may involve identifying patterns of road user movements and vehicular trajectories to analyze traffic flow and safety incidents.
- Traffic incident details, including vehicle speeds, congestion levels, and flow rates, which may indirectly relate to identifiable individuals under specific circumstances.

Personal data of stakeholders may also be collected during the implementation of certain project tasks, specifically those requiring input from external experts or stakeholders involved in traffic and road safety. All data collection and processing activities will comply with applicable data protection regulations and ethical standards.

Université Gustave Eiffel does not plan to collect, generate, or process any of the following data categories in the iDriving context:

- Data on Criminal Convictions and Offenses: Université Gustave Eiffel will not manage any data related to criminal convictions or offenses within the scope of this project.
- Operational Data for Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs): Université Gustave Eiffel will not collect or process any operational data related to law enforcement activities.
- Sensitive Information Related to Critical Infrastructure Protection: Université Gustave Eiffel will not handle sensitive infrastructure-related data directly. Should our work require access to this type of information for specific tasks, we will rely on project partners to manage it according to all applicable legal and security protocols. Any sensitive data or confidential information shared within the project will be protected under the strict confidentiality obligations outlined in the Consortium Agreement (CA), ensuring it is managed in compliance with these terms.
- Classified Information on National and International Grounds: Université Gustave Eiffel will not process any classified information related to national or international security within this project.
- Commercial Confidential Information (e.g., Company Secrets): Université Gustave Eiffel does not intend to collect or process commercial confidential information. However, if such information is encountered during compliance assessments or while reviewing project-related documents, we will adhere strictly to the confidentiality obligations outlined in the Consortium Agreement (CA), ensuring that any accessed information is handled in full compliance with these terms.

If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the

- Traffic data from city authorities (Nevers) will be handled under a formal data-sharing agreement. Data will be anonymized and only shared for project purposes, with strict terms of use.

process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.	
If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?	- The legal basis for processing personal data will be legitimate interest (Art. 6 GDPR), as it pertains to improving road safety.
Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.	- Explicit consent will be obtained where applicable, especially for any experimental participants in controlled trials. Data collected via public road monitoring will be anonymized.
If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	- No sensitive personal data as defined by Art. 9 GDPR will be processed.
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	- Not applicable, as no data on criminal convictions and offenses will be processed.
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	- No children or vulnerable groups will be specifically targeted. However, public road users may include individuals from these groups, and privacy safeguards will be in place.
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	- Personal data will be anonymized, and pseudonymization techniques will be applied where needed to protect participants' identities.
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	- Personal data (if applicable) will only be shared after anonymization. Partners will need access to analyze traffic patterns and safety compliance, and proper data-sharing agreements will be in place.
Will you engage in big data processing?	- Yes, the project will engage in big data processing related to traffic patterns and road user behavior, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.

<p>Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?</p>	<p>- No personal profiling will be conducted. Data will be used for road safety improvements and infrastructure planning, not for profiling or scoring individuals.</p>
<p>Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?</p>	<p>- No adverse effects are expected as data will be anonymized and processed strictly for public safety and urban mobility improvements.</p>
<p>Will you engage in web scraping?</p>	<p>- No web scraping is planned in the project.</p>
<p>Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.</p>	<p>- No engagement with entities outside of the EU for personal data transfer is planned.</p>
<p>Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?</p>	<p>- Yes, pseudonymization and anonymization will be used for all personal data. Anonymization will be applied at the data collection stage, ensuring GDPR compliance.</p>
<p>Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?</p>	<p>- Yes, a data minimization review has been conducted to ensure only essential data for road safety and traffic analysis is collected and processed.</p>
<p>Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.</p>	<p>- Yes, de-identified data (anonymized or pseudonymized) will be openly shareable. This includes traffic behavior data and road safety compliance data.</p>
<p>Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data</p>	<p>- No additional issues are foreseen. Data sharing will be in compliance with GDPR and other applicable regulations.</p>

sharing as envisaged within the project?	
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	TBD

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial: Budget allocated for hardware, data management software, cloud storage, and backup systems. - Human: Dedicated data management team, including data scientists and IT specialists, overseeing data collection, processing, and storage. - Technical: Cloud storage infrastructure, secured servers, software for data encryption, anonymization tools, and FAIR data repository tools. - Legal: a Data Protection Officer for the Université Gustave Eiffel is in charge of the all the GDPR issues and its services will be deployed for iDriving project.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	- Yes, there may be extra costs for data formatting, metadata creation, and repository fees. These costs will be covered by the project budget, specifically allocated for data collection and management activities.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	- Possibly yes, some trusted repositories (e.g., Zenodo) may charge fees for long-term storage. These will be covered by the project's data management budget, and external grants may also be pursued to offset costs.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	- Possibly yes, there may be a need to hire IT specialists to maintain data repositories and ensure continuous access. These service fees will be included in the data management and technical support budget.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	- Time and effort costs include personnel time for data cleaning, metadata creation, encryption, and documentation. Estimated effort is around 15-20% of the total data management team's time.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T5.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traffic data (vehicular speed, acceleration curves, congestion levels) - Road safety data (incident logs, non-compliance events) - Infrastructure data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To dynamically update KPIs related to traffic management, safety, and infrastructure maintenance - To build a dynamic monitoring tool with AI-based predictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cameras, drones, and radars deployed in Nevers - Existing datasets from OpenStreetMap - ClaireSITI platform from GRETIA Lab 	Yes, data will be shared with consortium partners to assist in the development of safety criteria and KPI updates	Yes, the data could be useful for road safety researchers and local governments. However, sensitive traffic data might not be shared due to privacy or contractual limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical: Data will be encrypted (AES-256) and stored in secure repositories - Organizational: Limited access granted to authorized personnel, GDPR compliance ensured
T5.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi-source data from cameras, drones, radars - GPS signals - Vehicular speed and acceleration data - Cartographic data from OpenStreetMap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To characterize risky situations on roadways - To predict traffic incidents using AI-based models and create a dashboard to monitor KPIs - To simulate transportation network dynamics using SUMO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UAVs, traffic cameras, radars, and GPS devices in Nevers - OpenStreetMap - SUMO traffic simulation data 	Yes, consortium partners will use the data to integrate predictive safety measures into their own tools	Yes, transportation authorities and urban planners could use this data. Sensitive or personal data (e.g., GPS traces) will be restricted due to privacy regulations (GDPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical: Access to sensitive data will be limited through secure APIs and encrypted repositories - Organizational: GDPR-compliant processes, regular audits of data access and usage

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	[Law and Internet Foundation]
Team	[Rada Stoilova]
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<p>As part of the iDriving project, the Law and Internet Foundation (LIF) is responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and IPR management (Task 1.4) • Privacy, ethics, and legal monitoring (Task T1.5), • Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance (Task 2.4) • Policy impact and recommendations at EU level (Task T7.3). <p>To fulfil its obligations within the project, LIF will produce legal assessments, compliance reports, and policy recommendations. LIF will further collect data in the form of questionnaires and forms from partners, specifically related to compliance practices within the project, as well as security and privacy policies to support our organisation’s work in these areas and ensure the activities within the project are carried out ethically, and in compliance with international, regional and domestic laws and regulations.</p> <p>Additionally, LIF collects and processes personal data in two forms: the personal data of its employees working on the project and the personal data of project partners, including contact details and roles within the consortium. LIF also processes publicly available data, such as open data related to current legislation, policies, and literature, which is used as reference points in our legal assessments and compliance reviews.</p>
Will you re-use any data?	Yes, LIF will re-use data from previous legal research, performed in previous projects the organisation has participated. The data which will be reused is the intellectual property of LIF.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	The data LIF will generate originates from LIF’s intellectual work, based on legal analysis, compliance reviews, and policy assessments conducted within the project. LIF will also use responses from questionnaires and correspondence provided by partners, as well as their existing legal and other relevant internal policies to inform our analysis.
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	<p>The purpose of collecting and generating data varies based on the objectives of each task LIF leads within the iDriving project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.4 Data and IPR management - The data collected within this task is related to data handling practices and internal policies from partners. It will be used to establish and monitor the project’s data management

	<p>framework, ensuring that all consortium partners adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and ensure data quality and security within the project.</p> <p>Furthermore, LIF will collect data related to the management of partner’s intellectual property within the project with the purpose of developing clear guidelines for managing intellectual property, ensuring legal compliance, and safeguarding the intellectual property rights of all partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.5 Privacy, ethics, and legal monitoring – The collected data on compliance practices and organisational security and privacy policies will be used to evaluate and ensure that project activities are in line with EU privacy regulations, ethical standards, and legal obligations. This data will support the development of legal and ethical management strategies for the consortium. • Task 2.4 Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance – During the implementation of this task, LIF will collect various types of data. Compliance monitoring data will be gathered to track project activities and ensure adherence to European traffic laws, including speed limits, road signals, and other legal requirements for urban and secondary roads. Risk assessment data will be collected to identify and evaluate potential risks, helping to create annual risk assessments and mitigation plans. Ethical and safety data will focus on safety, reliability, and user privacy, ensuring that ethical standards are maintained, with an emphasis on avoiding discrimination and ensuring transparency in data usage. Additionally, data related to user privacy and transparency will be collected, detailing how user information is handled to ensure compliance with privacy laws. <p>The purpose of collecting this data is to guarantee legal and regulatory compliance, manage risks effectively, uphold ethical principles such as safety, fairness, and transparency, and facilitate collaboration with regulatory bodies to stay aligned with evolving legal and ethical standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 7.3 Policy impact and recommendations at EU level - the purpose of collecting data on policy implementation and compliance measures is to analyse the project’s impact on relevant policies and develop a Recommendation for Policy framework. This framework will guide EU policymakers and legislators by providing actionable insights to ensure alignment with EU policy frameworks in the European Security Data Space. The data will focus on social, ethical, legal, and privacy aspects to promote cooperation between stakeholders, facilitate cross-border exchanges, and safeguard fundamental rights, including freedom of expression, data protection, and non-discrimination.
<p>If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?</p>	<p>Re-used data will help ensure high-quality delivery of tasks and alignment with previously established legal and ethical standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Task T1.4 (Data and IPR Management), re-used data will provide a foundation for establishing data governance principles, guiding the management of project data according to FAIR principles, as well as the management of IPR. • In Task T1.5 (Privacy, ethics and legal monitoring), the re-used data will support the development of legal analysis, ethical reviews, and compliance strategies, ensuring that project activities meet regulatory and ethical requirements. • For Task T2.4 (Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance), the re-used data will serve as a reference to monitor existing policies and develop recommendations to improve alignment with EU regulations and data protection standards

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Task 7.3 Policy impact and recommendations at EU level - the re-used data will serve as a reference to monitor existing policies and develop recommendations to improve alignment with EU regulations and data protection standards
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	LIF will collect and process data through electronic submissions via email, forms and questionnaires. The data will be processed to produce reports, assessments, and legal opinions as part of our compliance and policy monitoring tasks. The resulting data will be in textual formats such as PDF, DOCX, and Excel sheets for structured compliance tables. The expected data size is moderate.
How will you trace the collected data? (For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)	All collected data will be accompanied by metadata, including timestamps, source details, and unique identifiers for each document. Version control will be implemented to ensure traceability and transparency throughout the project lifecycle.
Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Since the data produced by LIF is the result of LIF'S intellectual work, such as reports, assessments, and legal opinions, the process of data generation is not fully reproducible. These outputs are based on context-specific analyses and interpretations, making it challenging to recreate them exactly in the same way. If the collected data or drafts got lost or became unusable, it would impact the ability to recreate the same outcomes, as they depend on subjective expertise and nuanced evaluation.
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	LIF primarily uses Microsoft Word and Excel for creating and processing reports, assessments, and compliance documents. Excel is specifically used as a Compliance Data Collector to organise and manage compliance-related data. Forms and questionnaires are used for data collection. No specialised software is required, as LIF's focus is on compliance and legal analysis rather than data visualisation or technical processing.
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? (Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures that you are bound to follow.)	<p>LIF has detailed internal data protection policies and a comprehensive data security framework as outlined in our Personal Data Processing Rules and guided by our ISO/IEC 27001 certification.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Protection Policies: LIF's data protection policies include physical, organisational, and technical measures to ensure secure handling of sensitive data. Access to personal data is restricted to authorised personnel, and every staff member signs a confidentiality agreement. LIF implements pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques where necessary to protect data, and all processing activities are documented and monitored to ensure compliance with legal obligations. • Data Security Policy: Our data security measures include physical protection, such as restricted access to office spaces, and secure storage of both physical and digital data. Office premises are equipped with SOT security systems, and sensitive documents are stored in locked cabinets. For digital data, Microsoft SharePoint is used for secure storage, with access control measures ensuring that only authorized staff can access the data. In the event of a data breach, LIF has a clear incident response process to handle the situation and mitigate risks. <p>These policies and procedures, combined with regular staff training and adherence to ISO/IEC 27001 standards, ensure that all data is handled securely and in compliance with both national and EU regulations.</p>

Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	Yes, data will be stored securely on Microsoft SharePoint and backed up regularly.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	Potential third-party beneficiaries may include EU regulatory bodies, academic institutions, and policy-making organisations. These entities could use the data for research purposes, regulatory alignment, or improving security protocols in similar projects, etc. The latter information refers to cases where LIF produces public deliverables. In the iDriving project, all deliverables that LIF will produce and contribute to will be publicly available.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	LIF generates information in the form of publications, reports, and legal assessments. Each of these outputs will be assigned unique project identifiers, such as iDriving_Report_ID or iDriving_Publication_ID, to ensure distinct identification. LIF will use a clear file naming convention (e.g., iDriving_Report_LegalReview_v1.pdf) to track versions and maintain consistency. Additionally, standardised identifiers such as DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) will be assigned to publicly available reports and publications to facilitate referencing and re-use within the research community.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) will be assigned to LIF's publications and reports that are publicly shared and intended for long-term archiving, ensuring they are easily citable and accessible. For internal documentation, we will use standards like ISO 8601 for date and time formatting to maintain consistency in file management.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	File naming conventions will follow a structured approach: [Project Name] [Data Type] [Date]_[Version].ext Example: iDriving_OPdata_LEA_20240415_v1.csv This will ensure clarity and ease of identification across versions and data categories. Directories will be organized by data type and project milestones.
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes, each publication, report, and legal assessment includes a version number using the vX.Y format, where X represents major changes (e.g., new data added) and Y represents minor changes (e.g., updates or corrections). Version control will be embedded in both the file names and metadata.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Yes, publications, reports, and legal assessments will be assigned relevant search keywords to facilitate discovery and re-use. Keywords will reflect the data type, project objectives, and key thematic areas (e.g., "GDPR compliance", etc.).
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on	Metadata will include information on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data source • Collection date

automated processes as well, if such are used.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data format • Version • Author(s) or data originator(s) • Keywords • Rights and access conditions
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	LIF will advise on using widely recognised standards such as the Dublin Core Metadata Standard to ensure that metadata is consistently structured and easily understandable. While LIF is not responsible for the technical integration, we will ensure that these standards support compliance and accessibility goals for the project.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes, metadata will be organised in a clear and structured format to ensure easy access and indexing by external repositories or relevant authorities.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Error! Reference source not found. [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Legal analysis, compliance reports, project publications, and general project documentation that are classified as non-sensitive will be made openly available, provided there are no legal restrictions. LIF reserves the right to publish public information and project results on our website to enhance transparency and dissemination in accordance with the Consortium Agreement (CA). However, any data containing personal information or sensitive content linked to the project will be subject to access restrictions to protect privacy and ensure compliance with legal and contractual obligations as defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA).
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Open data, such as publications, reports, and project documentation, will be accessible through secure and trusted repositories like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website to ensure wide dissemination and easy access. For internal use, non-public data will be stored and managed through Microsoft SharePoint, which ensures secure and controlled access within the consortium.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	The data, along with associated metadata and documentation, will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint for internal use and compliance management. For publicly shareable data, trusted repositories like Zenodo or other platforms aligned with EU Open Data policies will be used. LIF also reserves the right to post public information and project results directly on the project website to increase visibility and accessibility. As LIF is not involved in code development, there will be no code to deposit.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted	LIF has reviewed the requirements for depositing data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo, which ensures compliance with EU data management and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). This

<p>repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.</p>	<p>involves establishing metadata standards, verifying compliance with GDPR, and determining which datasets can be shared publicly.</p>
<p>What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?</p>	<p>For internal data, Microsoft SharePoint will be used for secure storage and management. For publicly accessible data, common web-based platforms like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website will be sufficient. As LIF is the Legal and Ethical lead, no specialised technical software will be needed, as our role is focused on compliance and ethical guidance rather than technical implementation.</p>
<p>Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i></p>	<p>Due to the nature of LIF’s role and the sensitivity of the information handled in the iDriving project, there will be strict data access restrictions. These can be grouped into two main categories: legal/contractual and intentional restrictions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal/Contractual Restrictions - For T1.4 Data and IPR management, T1.5 Privacy, ethics, and legal monitoring, and T2.4 Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance, LIF will handle compliance-related information, along with internal security and privacy policies. Sharing such data openly could conflict with EU privacy regulations and the conditions set out in the GA (Grant Agreement) and CA (Consortium Agreement). Therefore, access will be limited to authorised personnel within the consortium. Any data sharing with third parties will require a thorough legal and contractual review to ensure compliance. • Intentional Restrictions - Some data, like internal compliance assessments is intentionally restricted because it plays a key role in shaping project strategies and ensuring compliance. Making this information widely available could compromise the project’s integrity or pose legal and reputational risks for consortium partners. As a result, such data will only be shared with the European Commission or other authorised entities, as defined by the Grant Agreement, and will not be publicly accessible. <p>Overall, these restrictions are designed to protect data holders' rights, uphold compliance with legal frameworks, and preserve the confidentiality of sensitive project information.</p>
<p>What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?</p>	<p>For the data generated and collected by LIF in T1.4 Data and IPR management, T1.5 Privacy, ethics, and legal monitoring, T2.4 Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance and T7.3 Policy impact and recommendations at EU level, to be properly read and interpreted both during and after the project, the following information will need to be retained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextual Information - Detailed descriptions of the legal and ethical frameworks that were applied during the project. This includes references to relevant EU privacy regulations, compliance standards, and ethical guidelines that formed the basis of our analyses and recommendations. • Methodology - Clear documentation of how data was collected, processed, and analysed, including the questionnaires and electronic submissions used to gather information from partners. This will provide transparency into how compliance practices and policies were assessed. <p>Metadata - Information about the source of the data, collection dates, version control, and any updates made during the project. This will be essential for understanding the data’s context and ensuring that any updates or changes are tracked and traceable.</p>
<p>How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data: Project publications and reports will be available following the project’s final reporting. Metadata for these outputs will be maintained even after the data itself is no longer accessible to ensure traceability and reuse.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal data: Internal documentation and non-public records will follow the project’s data retention policy, typically for five years after the final reporting of the project, with metadata retained for long-term archival purposes.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata will be made openly available, and licensed under a public domain dedication (CC0) to ensure it can be freely accessed and reused. The metadata will include essential information, such as descriptions and access conditions, to enable users to find and use the data appropriately. As LIF is responsible for compliance and ethical oversight, we will ensure that the metadata is clear and supports proper access while adhering to legal and ethical standards.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	Oversight of the correct execution of the access process will be provided by the Law and Internet Foundation (LIF) in its capacity as the Legal and Ethical lead. LIF will work closely with the iDriving project coordinator and relevant partners to ensure that all data access procedures comply with legal, ethical, and privacy regulations. Any access to sensitive or restricted data will be carefully monitored to ensure compliance with the project's legal and ethical standards.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Requests for data access will be handled through an official request system, managed via email where applicants will need to submit their credentials and purpose for data access. Sensitive data will require appropriate approvals.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	For internal SharePoint access, identity verification will be managed via Microsoft authentication. For external repository access, identity verification will depend on the repository's policies (e.g., login credentials, and institutional affiliations).

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	LIF will follow Dublin Core Metadata Standards for organising the metadata of our publications, legal reports, and policy assessments. This standard provides a clear and consistent framework for describing different types of content, ensuring that the information is easy to locate, interpret, and integrate. In addition, where applicable, we will use standard legal and compliance vocabularies to enhance the clarity and interoperability of our outputs, making them easier to use and understand for a broader audience, including stakeholders and future researchers.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes, we will use standard vocabularies where applicable for the data types relevant to our role in the iDriving project. For Task T1.4 Data and IPR Management, Task T1.5 Privacy, Ethics and Legal Monitoring, and Task T2.4 Legal and ethical framework and iDriving compliance, T7.3 Policy impact and recommendations at EU level we will apply recognised vocabularies such as the Dublin Core Metadata Standard to describe and categorise our outputs, which include documents, reports, analyses, and other advisory materials. Since our data is the result of intellectual work rather than technical data generation, our focus is on using terminologies aligned with EU privacy regulations and legal standards to ensure consistency and compliance.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish	Not applicable for LIFs role in the project.

them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes, the data generated or collected throughout the project will be made available in structured formats that are easy to access and reuse. LIF will ensure that any publicly shareable data produced by us adheres to accessibility standards, allowing for further reuse where appropriate. However, the responsibility for providing machine-readable formats will primarily lie with the technical partners in the project.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes, we will permit the re-use of certain non-sensitive legal and compliance data, such as reports, legal research, and non-personal data analyses. The deliverables that LIF will produce within the iDriving project are public, and therefore, they will be openly shared and re-used.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes , legal research data that does not contain personal or sensitive information will be made freely available in the public domain, adhering to open data principles . However, sensitive and operational data will not be publicly available to protect confidentiality and security.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, we will provide readme files , methodology documentation , and any necessary codebooks , where it is appropriate given the context , alongside the re-usable data to ensure proper understanding and validation of the data analysis. This will include details on data structure, sources, and any processing steps taken.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	<p>Potential groups interested in re-using the data may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics and researchers in the field of law, ethics, and AI. • Policymakers focused on improving data protection and legal compliance. • EU and national regulatory bodies working on AI compliance. <p>NGOs and civil society organizations working on digital rights and AI.</p>
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Sensitive or personal data will have stricter restrictions, limiting access to authorised personnel or organisations, with a clear legal basis and ethical guidelines governing its use. These restrictions will remain for as long as necessary to protect privacy and comply with GDPR. Sensitive data will be shared with the Consortium only on a need-to-know basis.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Data, including publications and academic papers authored by the LIF team, will be made available for re-use immediately after major project milestones are achieved or at the end of the project, depending on the output type. For academic papers, availability will depend on the publication timelines and any embargo periods imposed by journals or publishers, typically ranging from 6 to 12 months. This ensures that all documentation is finalised and fully compliant with legal and academic standards before being openly shared.

For what period will data remain re-usable?	Data will remain re-usable for a minimum of 5 years after the project ends, in alignment with EU open data policies. This timeframe allows for adequate re-use and sharing of the project’s outcomes.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes, re-usable data will be licensed under an open license such as CC-BY 4.0 ensuring that users can freely share, adapt, and re-use the data as long as they provide appropriate credit to the original source. Sensitive data, if shared at all, will have more restrictive licenses to ensure compliance with GDPR and security protocols.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	<p>The primary risks to data security in the iDriving project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unauthorised Access: Because we handle sensitive documents, reports, and analyses, there’s a chance that someone without proper clearance could gain access, potentially compromising the confidentiality and integrity of the data. • Data Leakage: Accidental or intentional sharing of confidential legal assessments or compliance documents without the right permissions could lead to unauthorized disclosures and data leakage. • Data Breach or Cyberattack: External threats, such as hacking attempts or malware, pose a risk to our internal storage systems (e.g., SharePoint). If successful, these could result in a data breach, exposing sensitive information. • Misuse of Sensitive Information: Some of our data contains compliance insights coming from the partner organisations, which could be misinterpreted or misused if accessed inappropriately, potentially impacting the project’s outcomes or the respective partner. • Data Loss: Without strong backup and recovery processes, there’s a risk of permanently losing critical information, which could hinder our ability to deliver accurate legal and ethical guidance. <p>To mitigate these risks, LIF uses secure storage methods, enforces strict access controls, and conducts regular data security reviews to ensure that all sensitive information is thoroughly protected.</p>
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	LIF has identified potential risks related to unauthorised access, data breaches, and data loss, and we mitigate these through secure storage practices, regular backups, access controls, and adherence to internal data security policies. As part of our role in the project, we continue to evaluate these risks and implement necessary safeguards to ensure data protection.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.)	<p>LIF has implemented a range of technical and organizational measures to mitigate data security risks. These include:</p> <p>Technical Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Password Protection: Strong, regularly updated passwords are enforced for all digital systems. • Access Control: Digital access is managed through role-based permissions, ensuring that only authorized personnel can access sensitive data.

<p>measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secure Cloud Storage: Personal and compliance-related data is stored in a secure cloud platform (Microsoft SharePoint) with access control mechanisms. <p>Organisational Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Premises Security: The LIF office is equipped with controlled access, using chip cards and keys to limit entry to designated personnel. <p>Document Protection: Paper documents are stored in locked cabinets, and sensitive information is destroyed using shredders when no longer needed.</p>
<p>Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?</p>	<p>LIF does not use encryption for data protection. Instead, we rely on other technical and organizational measures to safeguard sensitive data, such as password protection, two-factor authentication, secure cloud storage, and access control mechanisms to ensure that only authorized personnel has access.</p>
<p>Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?</p>	<p>We will ensure the storage platforms, such as SharePoint, are kept updated with the latest security patches.</p>
<p>What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?</p>	<p>LIF doesn't have developed specific data recovery protocols at this stage. However, we implement regular backup procedures and secure storage practices to safeguard our data and mitigate potential data loss risks.</p>
<p>Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?</p>	<p>The following procedures are in place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immediate reporting: Any detected breach will be reported within 24 hours to relevant authorities. Containment measures: Immediate action will be taken to isolate and contain the breach. Notification: Affected individuals and relevant authorities will be informed of the breach. <p>Post-incident review: A full review will be conducted to prevent future incidents.</p>
<p>Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?</p>	<p>LIF does not intend to preserve personal data long-term, as we are not directly processing such data in the iDriving project. However, we will retain legal and compliance-related data, including reports and policy assessments generated as part of T1.4, T1.5 T2.2, and T7.3 for a minimum of 5 years after the project's completion. This is in line with project requirements and to ensure that the information remains accessible for future reference, audits, and compliance purposes.</p>
<p>Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?</p>	<p>Data will be maintained on SharePoint for internal storage. Public data will be archived in trusted repositories like Zenodo or institutional repositories, adhering to EU Open Data policies.</p>
<p>Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?</p>	<p>LIF will act in line with the general obligation to retain it for 5 years after the final project payment and national legislation in relation to the employment data. The decision is made in compliance with national legislation, particularly for data related to employment contracts and other legal obligations.</p>
<p>Who will maintain the data for the long term?</p>	<p>LIF's system administrator will oversee the long-term storage and security of the data. In the case of public data, trusted repositories will manage the long-term archival and access to data.</p>

<p>There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?</p>	<p>LIF will implement a data minimisation and deletion policy in compliance with GDPR. Personal data that is no longer necessary will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flagged for deletion based on predefined retention periods. • Permanently deleted from all systems, with logs kept for compliance.
<p>Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?</p>	<p>Microsoft SharePoint will be used for data storage and management, specifically for internal documents and sensitive data. SharePoint is compliant with GDPR and other data protection regulations. Public data may also be stored in trusted external repositories such as Zenodo, which adheres to EU data management standards.</p>

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Data: LIF will process the personal data of our employees working on the project and the personal data of project partners, including contact details and roles within the consortium, for internal project management purposes. Personal data of stakeholders may also be collected during the implementation of T7.3. <p>LIF does not plan to collect, generate, or process any of the following data categories in the iDriving context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on Criminal Convictions and Offences: LIF will not be involved in managing any data related to criminal convictions or offences. • Operational Data for Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs): LIF will not collect or process operational data. • Sensitive Information Related to Critical Infrastructure Protection: LIF will not handle this type of sensitive data directly. If our legal assessments require it, LIF will rely on project partners to manage this information, ensuring that all legal and security protocols are followed. Any sensitive data or confidential information shared within the project is protected under strict confidentiality obligations as outlined in the CA. This means that any such information accessed by LIF must be handled in compliance with the CA's terms. • Classified Information on National and International Grounds: No classified data will be processed by LIF in any capacity. • Commercial Confidential Information (e.g., Company Secrets): LIF does not intend to collect or process commercial confidential information. However, if LIF comes across such information during compliance assessments or when
--	--

	reviewing project-related contracts, LIF will strictly adhere to the Consortium Agreement. Any sensitive data or confidential information shared within the project is protected under strict confidentiality obligations as outlined in the CA. This means that any such information accessed by LIF must be handled in compliance with the CA's terms.
If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.	N/A
If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?	LIF intends to rely on Legitimate Interest (Article 6(1)(f) of the GDPR) as the lawful basis for processing personal data.
Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.	As part of our role in the iDriving project, LIF won't be collecting directly any personal data. Because of this, there's no need to obtain explicit consent from data subjects. Our focus is strictly on providing legal and ethical guidance to support compliance across the project, without being involved in any direct data collection or management activities.
If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	LIF will not process such a data.
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	LIF does not intend to collect or process data related to criminal convictions and offences.
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	LIF does not plan to collect data from children or other vulnerable groups.
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	LIF will use pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques to protect the identities of project participants (e.g. omit any names from public deliverables). These methods will ensure that personal identifiers are not accessible to unauthorised individuals, and only key personnel will have access to the identification codes.

Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	LIF will not share personal data with consortium partners. However, contact details of LIF personnel related to the iDriving project will be shared when necessary for project coordination.
Will you engage in big data processing?	No, LIF will not engage in big data processing.
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	No, LIF does not engage in personal profiling.
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	No adverse effects are anticipated for data subjects, as LIF will process personal data strictly within legal and ethical boundaries, ensuring that privacy and data protection rights are fully respected.
Will you engage in web scraping?	No, LIF will not engage in web scraping.
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	LIF does not plan to engage in data transfers outside the EU.
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Yes, pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques will be used for personal data. Personal identifiers will be replaced with pseudonyms or removed entirely, and sensitive data will be anonymised wherever possible to ensure privacy protection.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Yes, we will conduct a data minimisation review to ensure that only the data strictly necessary for achieving the project's objectives is collected and processed.
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in	Yes, anonymised data can be made openly shareable, if personal identifiers and sensitive information are removed. This ensures compliance with privacy regulations while allowing for data sharing and re-use.

new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No additional legal or ethical issues are currently foreseen. However, LIF will remain vigilant and ensure ongoing compliance with all relevant regulations and ethical guidelines as the project progresses.
Please provide the contacts of your organisation’s DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	LIF does not have a designated Data Protection Officer (DPO); however, we have a team of legal experts specialising in data privacy who oversee GDPR compliance and data protection matters.

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources: LIF has a team of legal experts in data privacy, ethics, and GDPR compliance who will be responsible for ensuring proper data management. Additionally, LIF has IT support personnel managing the technical aspects, including data storage and security. • Technical resources: The primary data storage platform is Microsoft SharePoint, which will be used for secure data storage and management. Regular backups, encryption, and access control systems will be part of the technical resources allocated for data management. • Financial resources: A portion of the project’s budget is allocated to cover any legal and technical costs associated with data management, including data security measures and compliance with FAIR principles.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	There might be additional costs associated with ensuring the data is fully FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), such as setting up metadata standards and ensuring interoperability with external repositories. These costs will be covered by the allocated project budget for data management activities.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	LIF uses SharePoint for internal data storage, which does not incur extra fees beyond the existing service agreement.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	At this stage, we do not anticipate the need for external specialists. The LIF IT and legal teams will handle data management internally. If unforeseen technical issues arise requiring external expertise, the costs will be managed through the project’s contingency funds.

What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	<p>The costs will mainly refer to staff time for preparing the data, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring proper metadata creation and adherence to FAIR principles. • Conducting legal reviews to ensure compliance with GDPR before sharing any personal or sensitive data. • IT efforts to maintain secure backups and manage access controls. <p>These efforts will be managed within the allocated project hours for data management, with no significant additional costs anticipated.</p>
--	---

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T1.4	LIF will not collect or generate data in strict sense. Data used will come from legal texts, ethics guidelines, policies, soft law, as well as data internally shared within the consortium for consultancy purposes as well as data related to the management of partner's intellectual property.	To oversee and ensure that all data within the project is managed in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), as well as EU privacy regulations and other relevant laws. Ensure the development of clear guidelines for managing intellectual property, ensuring legal compliance, and safeguarding the intellectual property rights of all partners.	Open sources and publicly available information, including official legal sources like state gazettes, etc.; Consortium partners – for internal usage only.	Yes, the data management processes, and best practices will be shared across the consortium to ensure uniformity in compliance and data handling.	Yes, some of the data included in the relevant public deliverables.	Data will be stored securely using Microsoft SharePoint, accessible only to authorized personnel. Strict access control measures and regular security audits will ensure the data remains protected.
T1.5	Legal and compliance-related data, including existing regulations, policy documents, and internal project documentation related to data protection and ethical considerations.	To ensure the project complies with privacy regulations, ethical standards, and legal requirements across all partners. The data is needed to identify any potential legal risks or	The data will be collected from project partners, publicly available legal and policy databases, and existing documentation within the consortium.	Yes, legal guidance and compliance assessments will be shared within the consortium to support compliance and ethical management throughout the project. However, personal data will not be shared, except for the contact details of LIF	Yes, some of the data such as the data on ethical and legal guidance provided in the relevant public deliverables.	Data will be stored securely using Microsoft SharePoint, accessible only to authorized personnel. Strict access control measures and regular security audits will ensure the data remains protected.

		ethical concerns and address them within the consortium.		personnel when necessary for coordination.		
T2.4	Data on traffic law compliance, risk assessments, ethical standards, and user privacy.	This data will support safety, reliability, and adherence to privacy regulations throughout the project.	The data will be collected from project partners, publicly available legal and policy databases, and existing documentation within the consortium.	Yes, legal guidance and compliance assessments will be shared within the consortium to support compliance and ethical management throughout the project. However, personal data will not be shared, except for the contact details of LIF personnel when necessary for coordination.	Yes, some of the data such as the data on ethical and legal guidance provided in the relevant public deliverables.	Data will be stored securely using Microsoft SharePoint, accessible only to authorized personnel. Strict access control measures and regular security audits will ensure the data remains protected.
T7.3	Policy documents, legal frameworks, compliance reports, potential personal data of stakeholders.	Ensuring stakeholder reach out and addressing open issues on security and data.	Data will be sourced from consortium partners, external legal and policy databases, and relevant stakeholders.	Yes, policy impact and recommendations will be shared with consortium partners.	Yes, this data may be valuable to regulatory bodies, policymakers, and academic researchers. Sharing will be limited where confidentiality or sensitivity is involved.	Data will be protected through encryption, access control, and compliance with EU privacy regulations and EU law. Policy-related documents will be securely stored in SharePoint and accessible only to authorized consortium members.

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	[TUC]
Team	[Ioannis Papamichail, Vasileios Markantonakis]
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	We are not collecting data. We will produce some data within T3.2 and T5.3.
Will you re-use any data?	Yes.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Simulation platform.
What purpose does the collection/generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Evaluation of developed methodologies.
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	Evaluation purposes.
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Text files. Not sure about the format and size yet.
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	Appropriate filing system will be used.

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Yes. We will be able to reproduce them.
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	Yes.
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	Yes, TUC has each own repository.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	Yes, we are going to use the TUC repository/cloud for storing the data during the lifecycle of the project.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	Not sure at the moment.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Not sure yet.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Not sure yet.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Not sure yet.

Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Yes.
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	Not sure yet.
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	Not sure yet.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Not sure yet.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Part of data produced within T3.2 and T5.3.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Deposition in a repository.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Deposition in a repository which is mirrored on our PC.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	No, we are using the TUC repository.
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Windows, MATLAB, EXCEL or SQL.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g.</i>	Not sure yet.

overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).	
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Settings used to produce the data.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	5 years after the end of the project. Not sure about metadata.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Not sure yet.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	PI
How will you handle requests for data access?	Data will be available initially only to partners of the project.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	Communication with the corresponding partner.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	Not sure yet.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes.

Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes.
---	------

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	TBD.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Other researchers and stakeholders.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	No restrictions for partners and TBD for other possible users.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	TBD.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	TBD.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	No decision has been taken yet.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY

[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Hack attacks. Otherwise, low risk of losing data.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	The use of passwords.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	No.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No.
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	None.
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Yes, reproduction of data.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	5 years
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	TUC repository.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	PI and his team.

Who will maintain the data for the long term?	TUC.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	We are not collecting, processing or producing personal data.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	No.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS
To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	No.
--	-----

<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	
<p>Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?</p>	
<p>How will you protect the identity of the project participants?</p>	
<p>Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?</p>	

Will you engage in big data processing?	-
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	-
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	-
Will you engage in web scraping?	-
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	-
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	-
Have you conducted a data-minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	-
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	-
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data	-

sharing as envisaged within the project?	
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	dpo@tuc.gr

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Financial and human.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	No, included in the Overhead.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No, included in the Overhead.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	Not sure yet.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes,	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to
------	-------------------------	----------------------------	---------------------------------	--	--	--

				are there reasons not to share?	protect the data?
T1.2	No data will be produced or used. This is a management task.	-	-	-	-

7.3.9 City of Karlovac

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	City of Karlovac
Team	Marino Ivasić
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Videos, images, traffic data, maintenance and interventions data
Will you re-use any data?	Yes
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	City of Karlovac (all data types)
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	The data will help monitor road safety, assess infrastructure conditions, optimize maintenance schedules, and improve traffic flow for urban and secondary roads
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	Same as above
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Data will be collected via cameras, UAVs, and environmental sensors. The formats will include video files, sensor logs, and image data, expected to range in the size of gigabytes per trial session depending on resolution and sampling frequency
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	Provenance will be traced through metadata that records the source, time, and conditions of data collection. Each dataset will be tagged with identifiers, ensuring traceability

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Yes, the process of data generation will be reproducible using the same sensor and data collection methods described in the project. If the data were lost or unusable, data recovery protocols and backup strategies outlined in the Data Management Plan (DMP) would be used to restore the data, ensuring continuity
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualise the data?	GIS-based risk asset management tools, UAV systems for surveillance, and AI-powered analysis software
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	GDPR and other European and national legal requirements for management personal data. Internal procedure specification for handling of video data containing personal information.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	yes
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	yes

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Date, time and type of the data. Data will be georeferenced when possible

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Standards defined by the partners
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Standardized file naming conventions will be followed to ensure easy identification and access to datasets, including metadata tags for provenance
Will you provide clear version numbers?	yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for discovery and re-use?	No
What metadata will be created? How? (<i>Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.</i>)	When applicable, metadata will include origin, geolocation, date, time, resolution, encoding format and other information regarding data type
What standards will you apply for the integration of metadata?	Industry standard
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	No

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorised users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Will be determined by the partners throughout the project
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	TBD
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	TBD
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	no

What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Web browser
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Restrictions will follow consortium agreement and GDPR, TDB during the project
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Same as the metadata, answered above
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Will be determined
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	No
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	TBD
How will you handle requests for data access?	Via official request procedures through Data Protection Officer
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	By the DPO and the official procedure

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	
[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to	Yes, to be determined

facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	No
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

[embargo periods]

Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Re-use of the data will follow Consortium agreement, GDPR and any other request will be analysed separately
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Will depend on the type of data (example. Meteorological data will be openly available, video data will not)
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	No
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Research, public
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Yes, sensitive data will be restricted to protect confidentiality, and the data will comply with GDPR regulations
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	N/A at this point
For what period will data remain re-usable?	Data will remain re-usable as long as it is hosted in trusted repositories

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	No
--	----

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Phishing, Cyber Attacks
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	All of the examples mentioned
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	Yes, sensitive data will be encrypted using industry-standard encryption methods
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Yes, Backup
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Yes
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long	Yes, according to local policies and laws

should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Online repositories, Local Servers
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	City authorities
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	City of Karlovac
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	Personal data will be deleted following GDPR requirements
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	TBD If yes, the involvement of the third party will follow standard data management procedure

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS <i>To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer</i>	
[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]	
Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; 	N/A

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	N/A
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	N/A
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	N/A

Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	N/A
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	N/A
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	N/A
Will you engage in big data processing?	N/A
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	N/A
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	N/A
Will you engage in web scraping?	no
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	N/A
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	N/A

Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	N/A
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	N/A
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	N/A
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	N/A

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Financial, human, and technical resources are allocated to ensure effective data management throughout the project, including storage, processing, and ensuring data security and accessibility
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Yes, there may be extra costs for cloud services and storage to make the data FAIR. These will be covered by the allocated project budget
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	The primary costs will be related to time and effort spent ensuring data is properly anonymized, formatted, and documented for sharing and preservation. These efforts are accounted for in the project's resource allocation

7.3.10 ALP.Lab

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	ALP.Lab GmbH
Team	Mohamed Berrazouane; Christoph Knauder; Martin Aichholzer; Darjan Kozic
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Technical Data: Object list data from the iDriving region of interest at Graz
Will you re-use any data?	No
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Optical sensors mounted on-site
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Provide insights on different traffic statistics
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	-
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	The data from the sensors is processed in real time and will not be stored. Only the resulted objects list will be recorded in a csv format. The data size approximation heavily depends on the amount of traffic in that location and could range from 1 to 20MB per minute.
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	The data is collected through a peer-to-peer communication setup from the edge computer to the server

<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>The data generation process is reproducible. However, since the system is monitoring real time movements of random road users passing through, the scenarios newly monitored may differ. We store the data in a NAS with redundant array of independent disks, which minimize the risks of corrupted data. However, if the data is lost, it cannot be re-generated, but another measurement would be needed</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i></p>	<p>Yes, our institution adheres to a set of comprehensive data management guidelines and maintains policies for data protection and data security to ensure the proper handling of traffic monitoring data. These guidelines are aligned with international standards and best practices for data management, as well as local regulations. E.g. we comply with the data protection regulations regarding GDPR in the European Union, ensuring that any personal data collected is handled responsibly. Data anonymization techniques are not necessary, because the collected data is anonymized per design. However, we have a data retention policy to specify the time period for retaining data. Finally, the data is processed, analyzed, and stored in a standardized format to ensure data consistency and usability for future analysis.</p>
<p>Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?</p>	<p>Local NAS with RAID system</p>
<p>Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?</p>	<p>Yes, the city of Graz should directly benefit from this data and the results that should come from it</p>

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE

[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]

What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Naturalistic driving object list data
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Will be specified after use case concretization
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Will be specified after use case concretization
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Naturalistic driving data; Multiple Objects Tracking (MOT)
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	Metadata will cover the description of the different attributes present in the data and give a general overview on what is contained within this data
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	Not specified
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Currently not, but this can be defined through the project

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Metadata and a sample from the collected data
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Repository
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	GitHub could be an option

Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	No We exchange data directly through a dedicated shared drive that only the respective party can access
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Through web browsers or any SFTP solution
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Data access is granted only to authorized personnel based on their role in the project.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	All the information included in the metadata
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Metadata can be made available after data is no longer available.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata will be made available. Information about access will be contained and how to proceed communication to the data owner on how to get access to the data.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	Project team
How will you handle requests for data access?	Peer-to-peer communication
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	Each person will have to fill a formal request to access the public data for the first time.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	No specific vocabulary standard is being used
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Not necessarily, but as best as possible. This will also depend on the data requirements defined in the specific use case.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Not specified yet, but possibly, yes.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	During the project duration for all partners that require the data for activities. After the project metadata with sample data will be made available in such a way.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	The metadata and sample data could be used and shared openly. The full data could only be used for the specific approved aim when it was delivered and nothing else without further agreement.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Metadata and sample data, yes Otherwise, no
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Researchers, Developers, Road operators

Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Yes
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	To be define upon agreement between the different parties
For what period will data remain re-usable?	- To be define upon agreement between the different parties
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes Licence type in development

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Data loss or corruption; Data Breaches
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	A formal risk assessment is being prepared as part of the current TISAX (ISO/IEC 27001) certification process. We are using RAID2 systems as well as a strict access process using multiple parallel security layers
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need- to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Access token Credentials Whitelisting
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	No
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	None

Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Our IT department have provided specific guidelines to following in such a case This guideline defines the necessary reporting steps, and further rules of conduct
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	3 to 5 years
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Subject-based
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	Management
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	If applicable, ALP.Lab will
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	No personal data is stored in the first place for the data category described in this questionnaire
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	TU Graz (as we are using the campus network) Nothing stored or accessed by the third party

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>If any of the categories of non- personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>

If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	Not applicable
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	Not applicable
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	Not applicable
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	Not applicable
Will you engage in big data processing?	
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	Not applicable
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	Not applicable
Will you engage in web scraping?	No
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	No

Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Not applicable
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	No
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	Not applicable
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	Not applicable

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Hardware: Local data broker; Human resources: respective employees working on the data
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Not applicable

Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	Yes. This is currently covered by ALP.Lab GmbH
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	To be defined

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T6.4	Technical Data: Object list data from the iDriving region of interest at Graz	Traffic Situation assessment	ALP.Lab Traffic Monitoring System	The data can be used by the iDriving system in general	Yes, It can be but only upon agreement with the city authority in alignment with the granted permission	Redundancy and backup plans, as well as different security measures with restricted access.

7.3.11 SIMAVI

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	SIMAVI
Team	Diana Gornea (PM), Daniel Gherghiceanu (TL), Catalin Petrea (DPO)
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Username Licence plate Location data and Behavioural data will only be displayed to users during the use of the application
Will you re-use any data?	Yes
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Username, Licence plate – set by the user or assigned by the admin
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Username, Licence plate – authentication, data management
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	During the project, only the username and licence plate will be reused for the purpose of testing the application
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Username, Licence plate – will be stored locally and on the server, in string format, foreseen size max. 100-200 characters
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	Username, Licence plate – will be collected based on the user’s device ID

<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>We foresee to have a token that will be active for a limited period. In case the username and licence plate will not be usable anymore, a new username and licence plate will be provided, together with an associated token</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i></p>	<p>Yes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage of all personal data in the SIMAVI Intranet network. This network cannot all be accessed directly from the Internet, it is protected with firewall systems, anti-virus, malware and anti-spam protection systems. - Access to personal data is allowed only to persons employed in the performance of the contract and only after an instruction regarding the security measures necessary for the performance of the contract. Training will be provided by the SIMAVI DPO at the start of the project and/or whenever there are changes in security measures or project team composition. Each employee involved in carrying out the activities specific to the contract will sign a confidentiality agreement that also includes clauses regarding personal data. - Granting the rights assigned to the project team for access to the project resources only during the participation in the project activities. The Project Manager is responsible for requesting from the IT department the granting, modification or revocation of access rights. - Prohibition of disclosing credentials (user and password) to other users - Compliance with the obligation to minimize the processing of personal data: cf art.5 par.(1) letter (a) GDPR which requires that the processed data be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purpose of the processing. Thus, the data transferred by the Operator to the Authorized Representative for the resolution of technical problems reported by the Operator will be minimized so as to refer strictly to the reported problem (the Operator will not transfer to the Authorized Representative an entire database, in the context in which the reported technical problem is can solve with a single record). - The processing and use of personal data belonging to the Operator will be done only for the purpose of fulfilling the assumed contractual obligations and will not use or reuse this personal data for any other purpose, neither in its own interest, nor in the interest of any third party - Processing of personal data, to which the Authorized Person has access only at the request of the Operator, except for the cases of Union law and internal law - Safe data processing (controlled access to information on the server, access groups) - Application of administrative and technical measures against destruction, loss, damage, alteration, disclosure or unauthorized access (e.g. controlled access measures to project locations) - Remote access to the project files, located at the Client (through secure connections over the internet: VPN, screen connect) configured according to the needs of the contract and only for the purpose of the project. - Auditing remote connections (secure over the Internet), to check, among other things, that they contain information about the session name (client), the period, the person who used the connection. - Accessing the client's servers only if a specific clause is included in the contract or as a result of a written request from the client.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The use for specific purposes of personal data sets from the client's databases, for a limited time, for the creation of test environments, the creation of development environments necessary for the client's activities, these will be deleted at the client's request or at the end of the period for which they were requested - The archiving of personal data used in the project is carried out starting from the moment of the completion of the contract and after the retention period (eg: 5 years) the archives are deleted, unless otherwise requested by the operator - Mandatory deletion by employees of emails containing personal data, provided that the employees are not part of the work team or are not directly involved in carrying out specific activities. They must also notify the person from whom they received the email. - Sending e-mails from employees to other third parties (either external or SIMAVI employee) must contain only the data necessary to solve certain situations and with the assurance that the personal data in the e-mails is minimal and strictly necessary. - Avoiding the disclosure of confidential information over the phone or by e-mail, if the identity of the person requesting this data cannot be verified.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	At database level there will be a periodic backup performed
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	No

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Username, device ID, licence plate
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	N/A

What directory and file naming convention will be used?	N/A
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	N/A
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	Device ID, Licence plate
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	The integration with the server will be done through communication with an API
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	There will be no data from the project available publicly
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Within a database
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	On the server of the project
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	The data will be stored in a database that will not be accessible to users outside the project. The documentation will also be shared only within the project partners, on local protected devices or on the project SharePoint.
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Database management system tools, according to the specific technology

Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Yes, in accordance with the applicable rules in implementing EU research projects.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	N/A
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	For the duration of the project
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	No
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	N/A
How will you handle requests for data access?	Through the data management system of the server
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	Depending on what will be included in the detailed specifications of the application, only authorized partners in the project will have access to the data, if necessary, method to be discussed.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Error! Reference source not found. **[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]**

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	JSON format messages will be used to communicate with the other components
--	--

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	N/A
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	If needed

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	If needed
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	If needed
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, through the deliverables foreseen in the project
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	N/A
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	As per the confidentiality rules of the project
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Upon request
For what period will data remain re-usable?	For the period of the project

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	N/A
--	-----

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	The server being compromised, either by a severe technical issue or by a cyber attack
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	At project level, this has not been performed yet At organization level (SIMAVI) we have the abovementioned risk assessed and mitigated through specific measures
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Encryption, passwords, antivirus, firewall, VPN access, CCTV, need-to-know principle for personnel
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	The username, password, licence plate will be encrypted using AES methods
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Backup protocol
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Yes – full scanning of the impacted systems, impact assessment, quarantine and cleaning of the infected files, backup of the files
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long	No

should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	On the server of the project, for the duration of the project
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	At Consortium level we will store and use only the necessary data, for the duration of the project
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	It will be up to the Coordinator
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	N/A The data will be used only for the duration of the project
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	No

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; 	No
--	----

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	N/A
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	There is no need for an explicit written consent as the target group will be part of the project
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	N/A

Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	N/A
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	N/A - The username, licence plate will not represent a specific person or vehicle
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	N/A – there will not be personal data to share
Will you engage in big data processing?	N/A
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project’s results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	N/A
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	No
Will you engage in web scraping?	No
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project’s duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	No
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	No

Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	To be further discussed within the Consortium if additional data will be necessary
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	N/A
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	At organization level: Catalin Petrea (catalin.petrea@simavi.ro)

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Financial, human, technical
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	No
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated	No

repositories? How will they be covered?	
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	No costs The sharing/preservation will be done automatically and will not involve additional costs or effort.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. Please, fill out the information **only about the tasks you lead**.

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T3.3	Username Licence plate	Authentication, management	data From the end user	The data will be used in a centralized way (server) by the technical partners	No	Encryption, passwords, antivirus, firewall, VPN
T5.5	Username Licence plate	Authentication, management	data From the end user	The data will be used in a centralized way (server) by the technical partners	No	Encryption, passwords, antivirus, firewall, VPN
T6.6	Username Licence plate	Authentication, management	data From the end user	The data will be used in a centralized way (server) by the technical partners	No	Encryption, passwords, antivirus, firewall, VPN

7.3.12 INFRA

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	Infra Plan
Team	Marko Pađen, Irina Stipanović
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Videos, images, traffic data
Will you re-use any data?	Yes
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	City of Karlovac, open-source
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	The data will help monitor road safety, assess infrastructure conditions, optimize maintenance schedules, and improve traffic flow for urban and secondary roads
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	Re-used data will help validate models, improve monitoring systems, and benchmark new results against previous data for optimizing road safety
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Data will be collected via cameras, UAVs, and environmental sensors. The formats will include video files, sensor logs, and image data, expected to range in the size of gigabytes per trial session depending on resolution and sampling frequency
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	Provenance will be traced through metadata that records the source, time, and conditions of data collection. Each dataset will be tagged with identifiers, ensuring traceability

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Yes, the process of data generation will be reproducible using the same sensor and data collection methods described in the project. If the data were lost or unusable, data recovery protocols and backup strategies outlined in the Data Management Plan (DMP) would be used to restore the data, ensuring continuity
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualise the data?	GIS-based risk asset management tools, UAV systems for surveillance, and AI-powered analysis software
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	Infra Plan adheres to the guidelines outlined in the iDriving Data Management Plan, which aligns with GDPR and other legal requirements for personal data. Measures for securing both personal and non-personal data, such as data encryption and access control will be used
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	yes
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	yes

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	Date, time and type of the data

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	Standards defined by the partners
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Standardized file naming conventions will be followed to ensure easy identification and access to datasets, including metadata tags for provenance
Will you provide clear version numbers?	yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for discovery and re-use?	no
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	Metadata will describe the dataset's origin, structure, creators, encoding formats, and data collection methods. Metadata will be created manually
What standards will you apply for the integration of metadata?	Usual file standards for the file types
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	No,

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorised users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Will be determined by the partners throughout the project
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Microsoft sharepoint
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Microsoft sharepoint, Github
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	no

What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Web browser
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Restrictions will follow consortium agreement and GDPR
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Nothing that isn't clear from the data itself
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Will be determined
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	no
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	TBD
How will you handle requests for data access?	Via email or other channels
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	email

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Error! Reference source not found. [standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to	Yes, to be determined
--	-----------------------

facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	No
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE

Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Will depend on the type of data
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Researchers
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Yes, sensitive data will be restricted to protect confidentiality, and the data will comply with GDPR regulations
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Yes
For what period will data remain re-usable?	Data will remain re-usable as long as it is hosted in trusted repositories

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes, data will be licensed under a public domain dedication like CC0
--	--

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Phishing
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Passwords, PIN, Bitlocker
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	Yes, sensitive data will be encrypted using industry-standard encryption methods
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Backup
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Yes
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long	Yes

should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Online repositories
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	Project leader
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	Personal data will be deleted following GDPR requirements once it is no longer necessary for the project
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Yes, Microsoft Sharepoint, Github

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS
To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; 	N/A
--	-----

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	N/A
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	N/A
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	N/A
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	N/A

Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	N/A
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	N/A
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	N/A
Will you engage in big data processing?	N/A
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	N/A
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	N/A
Will you engage in web scraping?	N/A
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	N/A
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	N/A

Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	N/A
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	N/A
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	N/A
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	N/A

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Financial, human, and technical resources are allocated to ensure effective data management throughout the project, including storage, processing, and ensuring data security and accessibility
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Yes, there may be extra costs for cloud services and storage to make the data FAIR. These will be covered by the allocated project budget
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No

Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	The primary costs will be related to time and effort spent ensuring data is properly anonymized, formatted, and documented for sharing and preservation. These efforts are accounted for in the project's resource allocation

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T2.1	Open-source data	To be able to complete the task	Other partners, open source	Yes	Yes, for research purposes	All the industry standards
T2.3	Open-source data	To be able to complete the task	Other partners, open source	Yes	Yes, for research purposes	All the industry standards
T6.1	Open-source data	To be able to complete the task	Other partners, open source	Yes	Yes, for research purposes	All the industry standards
T6.3	Video data, traffic data	To be able to complete the task	Other partners	Yes	Yes, for research purposes	All the industry standards

7.3.13 AUSTRIATECH

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	Austriatech
Team	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<p>Evaluation Data for different Use Cases to evaluate the iDriving Platform, no further details known so far. The details will be available once the Task 6.1 is finished, and its corresponding deliverable is final. Information on the evaluation data, which will be collected, analysed and generated will probably be found in this deliverable.</p> <p>For the tasks 2.2 data will be collected related to user requirements, which will include information on user groups and needs for these users. These data will be collected from the responsible partners by AustriaTech and will maybe be analysed reworked for the Task 2.2 and its inputs.</p>
Will you re-use any data?	<p>Requires more knowledge on which data will be processed.</p> <p>For User Requirements no data will be re-used as the user requirements are dependent on the developed system and change accordingly.</p> <p>AustriaTech will not reuse any evaluation data as this does not support the evaluation of the project.</p> <p>In case that C-ITS is used in the project AustriaTech can provide data for several C-ITS messages already available and collected in previous projects and deployments. Currently the decision was not made to use C-ITS in any of the pilot use cases though, once it is planned to be used it will be described in more detail.</p> <p>It may reuse data from previous C-ITS test drives to confirm the functionality of the mobile Lab tool.</p>
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Evaluation data and survey data may be generated by each use Case partner and will be used to enhance the Deliverables.
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Evaluation of the project and results, as well as inputs for deliverables.

<p>If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?</p>	<p>See previous question where re-use was asked.</p>
<p>How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?</p>	<p>Evaluation data: Still needs to be defined. C-ITS Data: will be described in detail once clear that data will be used.</p>
<p>How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i></p>	<p>Requires more knowledge on which data will be processed</p>
<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>Requires more knowledge on which data will be processed C-ITS Data usually not as timestamps are part of the data.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?</p>	<p>Yes.</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i></p>	<p>There is a data management guideline available for personnel data as required by the GDPR and its national implementation in Austria.</p>
<p>Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?</p>	<p>Evaluation Data: Probably, as this data will be related to the project results for Platform Evaluation.</p>

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	For iDriving Data iDriving will be added in the data name other than that depending on the form of data more elaborate naming conventions may be used. For publications in papers a DOI will be assigned.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	DOIs will be used for publicly available information.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	File naming conventions will follow a structure approach: For example: [datatype/documenttype]_[projectname]_YYYYMMDD.xls
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Documents will have clear version numbers with final documents including _final in the end name. While other Versions of the document will have any number assigned as a version such as v01 to v1 or v2, ...
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	On publicly available data yes. On internal documents project guidelines will be used.
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	Metadata may include information on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data source • Collection date • Data format • Version • Author(s) or data originator(s) • Keywords • Rights and access conditions
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	AustriaTech will follow the Project guidelines.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	unknown

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	Project publications, and general project documentation that are classified as non-sensitive will be made openly available, provided there are no legal restrictions. Data which was used to compile the deliverables in form of raw data will be made publicly available if it was determined by the project that this data is of public interest.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Open data, such as publications, reports, and project documentation, will be accessible through secure and trusted repositories like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website to ensure wide dissemination and easy access. For internal use, non-public data will be stored and managed through Microsoft SharePoint, which ensures secure and controlled access within the consortium.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	The data, along with associated metadata and documentation, will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint for internal use and compliance management. For publicly shareable data, trusted repositories like Zenodo or other platforms aligned with EU Open Data policies will be used. LIF also reserves the right to post public information and project results directly on the project website to increase visibility and accessibility. As ATE is not involved in code development, there will be no code to deposit.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	AustriaTech has reviewed the requirements for depositing data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo, which ensures compliance with EU data management and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). This involves establishing metadata standards, verifying compliance with GDPR, and determining which datasets can be shared publicly.
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	For internal data, Microsoft SharePoint will be used for secure storage and management. For publicly accessible data, common web-based platforms like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website will be sufficient. AustriaTech may use for C-ITS data .blf and .pcap files, these files need the appropriate tools to open fore .pcap tools like Wireshark are required for .blf files the Vector CANoe tool. Both formats will include the same information.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).	For .blf files the Vector CANoe Tool will be needed. This tool requires licensing fees to be paid. The same data will also be available as .pcap file, which can be accessed with free available tools.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	For T2.2. and T6.5: Methodology - Clear documentation of how data was collected, processed, and analysed, including the questionnaires and electronic submissions used to gather information from partners. This will provide transparency into how compliance practices and policies were assessed.

	Metadata - Information about the source of the data, collection dates, version control, and any updates made during the project. This will be essential for understanding the data's context and ensuring that any updates or changes are tracked and traceable.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	Open data: Project publications and reports will be available following the project's final reporting. Metadata for these outputs will be maintained even after the data itself is no longer accessible to ensure traceability and reuse. Internal data will be stored and deleted at the earliest after some years of the project end. The data may be retained for quite some time depending on the importance of information.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Not known for now
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	AustriaTech's IT and DPO for internal processes
How will you handle requests for data access?	Requests for data access will be handled through an official request system, managed via email where applicants will need to submit their credentials and purpose for data access. Sensitive data will require appropriate approvals.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	For internal SharePoint access, identity verification will be managed via Microsoft authentication. For external repository access, identity verification will depend on the repository's policies (e.g., login credentials, and institutional affiliations).

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	AustriaTech will follow the guidelines outlined in the Data Management plan if they exist.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Not applicable

Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	yes
---	-----

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes, public data will be permitted. Private or GDPR sensitive information will be restricted.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Academics, Experts for CCAM, Traffic Managers, Policy makers, ...
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	No
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	At the latest at the end of the Project. There are no embargo periods
For what period will data remain re-usable?	
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	<p>The primary risks to data security in the iDriving project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unauthorised Access: Because we handle sensitive documents, reports, and analyses, there's a chance that someone without proper clearance could gain access, potentially compromising the confidentiality and integrity of the data. • Data Leakage: Accidental or intentional sharing of confidential legal assessments or compliance documents without the right permissions could lead to unauthorized disclosures and data leakage. • Data Breach or Cyberattack: External threats, such as hacking attempts or malware, pose a risk to our internal storage systems (e.g., SharePoint). If successful, these could result in a data breach, exposing sensitive information. • Misuse of Sensitive Information: Some of our data contains compliance insights coming from the partner organisations, which could be misinterpreted or misused if accessed inappropriately, potentially impacting the project's outcomes or the respective partner. • Data Loss: Without strong backup and recovery processes, there's a risk of permanently losing critical information, which could hinder our ability to deliver accurate legal and ethical guidance.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Office) Premises secured with (physical key) locks, separate keys for our server room only for relevant personnel, no CCTV, Fortigate firewall managed by external 2nd level support • User logins managed by internal IT and external 2nd level support, MFA enforced, apps accessing/syncing MS365 data allowed only on company device work profile (e.g. outlook, onedrive, teams) • ESET antivirus on client Windows devices/endpoints • Security Awareness Trainings provided by Hornet Security to simulate phishing attacks via email • Segmented Network/VLAN managed by 2nd level support
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	Yes if applicable security certificates and other access data will be stored encrypted.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	no

What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Off-site backups according to our Backup Schedule, managed by external 2nd level support • Backup restore tests conducted regularly
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Incident Response Plan (IRP) implemented, private emergency contact data for relevant key users available as part of the IRP
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	Maybe. Depending on the data.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Yes
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	AustriaTech will take the decision for deleting the data after some time after the project end. Data is usually stored on a long-term basis but may be deleted if the need arises. The data will be available at least for 5 years after the projects end.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	AustriaTech's System Administrator will be responsible for maintaining data long term.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data stored in MS365 is GDPR-compliant as the platform is GDPR compliant • User Accounts + Data of former Employees archived and deleted after 3 months from termination of employment • Last year: IT-Security (& Processes - offboarding, etc.) audit conducted by EY consultants
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Data is stored in the secure infrastructure of AustriaTech, depending on the type of data either on-premise, or in our Microsoft cloud environment

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>Personal Data: AustriaTech will process the personal data of our employees working on the project and the personal data of project partners, including contact details and roles within the consortium, for internal project management purposes. Personal data of stakeholders may also be collected during the implementation of T2.2 and within WP6.</p> <p>AustriaTech does not plan to collect, generate, or process any of the following data categories in the iDriving context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret).
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>AustriaTech intends to rely on Legitimate Interest (Article 6(1)(f) of the GDPR) as the lawful basis for processing personal data.</p>

If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	N/A
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	Not known
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	AustriaTech will use pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques to protect the identities of project participants (e.g. omit any names from public deliverables). These methods will ensure that personal identifiers are not accessible to unauthorised individuals, and only key personnel will have access to the identification codes
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	No
Will you engage in big data processing?	No
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	Depending on the Evaluation Data.
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	This is not foreseen.
Will you engage in web scraping?	No
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If	No

yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Yes, Personal Identifiers will be removed.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Yes, we will conduct a data minimisation review to ensure that only the data strictly necessary for achieving the project's objectives is collected and processed.
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	Yes, anonymised data can be made openly shareable, if personal identifiers and sensitive information are removed. This ensures compliance with privacy regulations while allowing for data sharing and re-use.
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	You can in touch with our data protection officer via: AustriaTech - Federal Agency for Technological Measures Ltd. Raimundgasse 1/6 1020 Wien, Österreich E-Mail: datenschutzbeauftragter@austriatech.at

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	<p>Human resources: AustriaTech has data protection officer who is responsible for ensuring proper data management. Additionally, AustriaTech has an IT first level support, managing technical aspects including data storage and security as well as an external second level IT support for further assistance.</p> <p>Technical resources: The primary data storage platform is on-premises and Microsoft SharePoint, which will be used for secure data storage and management. Regular backups, encryption, and access control systems will be part of the technical resources allocated for data management. Access to sensitive data sets is restricted by an internal permission strategy.</p>
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	From today's perspective there is no need for extra actions regarding making Project data FAIR.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	AustriaTech uses SharePoint for internal data storage, which does not incur extra fees beyond the existing service agreement.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	AustriaTech uses for iDriving general IT infrastructure. The AustriaTech IT first and second level support, data protection officer and legal team will handle data management internally.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T2.2	User Requirements Contact Data	Contact data for questionnaires to collect possible Use Requirements.	Project Partners	User Requirements yes Contact data only If necessary	no	Standard AustriaTech Data Security measures
T6.5	No detailed data available yet. Depending on the					

	methodology and Use Case descriptions					
--	---------------------------------------	--	--	--	--	--

7.3.14 INGARTEK

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	Ingartek
Team	Eneko Elizondo
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Contact information, standardization processes, market status, stakeholder interactions, competition analysis, business model frameworks.
Will you re-use any data?	The following data may be reused, although its re-use is not expected within the project’s defined work packages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization Documentation: Guidelines, best practices, and meeting notes with standardization bodies to aid interoperability. Collaboration Data: Aggregated insights from partnerships (e.g., C-Roads, C-Mobile) and stakeholder feedback for network-building. Market Analysis Data: Anonymized market trends, user needs, and competitive insights. Business Models: General exploitation strategies and frameworks for sustainable approaches. Impact and Sustainability Metrics: Benchmarks for evaluating long-term project viability.
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Data will come from consortium members, stakeholders, and other contacts through market surveys.
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Contact information: To communicate with stakeholders and standardization bodies. Technical specifications: To contribute to standardization processes. Market trends and stakeholder interactions: To analyse the market and support project objectives.
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	No data re-use is expected within the project’s defined work packages.

How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Contact data will be stored in our CRM software, while market data will be collected via reports, online resources, and interviews. Formats will include text files and CSVs; size is expected to be small.
How will you trace the collected data?(<i>For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data</i>)	CRM software will maintain metadata about the contacts and their interactions.
Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	Yes, data can be re-collected or sourced again if lost.
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	CRM software for contacts and general office software for data analysis (e.g., Excel).
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? (<i>Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.</i>)	Personal Data: We will comply with GDPR for handling personal data. This includes obtaining consent from data subjects when necessary, ensuring data minimization, and applying security measures like access control where necessary. Non-Personal Data: For non-personal data, we follow best practices to ensure data integrity and confidentiality, including regular backups, secure storage, and restricted access based on roles.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	Contact data will be stored and backed up in CRM software. Other types of data will be stored in third-party storage with industry-standard encryption and access control measures.
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	Potential third-party beneficiaries may include EU regulatory bodies, academic institutions, and policy-making organisations. These entities could use the data for research purposes, regulatory alignment, or improving security protocols in similar projects, etc.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	The project has an internal code, 2023_139. No internal data identifiers are expected at this time, and will be assigned as required.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	N/A
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	Internal guidelines derived from ISO 9001 will be followed.
Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	No, the data is for internal use and discovery is not contemplated at this time.
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	Metadata will be created automatically by CRM and third party storage systems.
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	Metadata will be created automatically by CRM and third party storage systems.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Data and metadata sharing are not expected at this time.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]

<p>Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?</p>	<p>Standardization Documentation: Guidelines, best practices, and meeting notes with standardization bodies to aid interoperability. Collaboration Data: Aggregated insights from partnerships (e.g., C-Roads, C-Mobile) and stakeholder feedback for network-building. Market Analysis Data: Anonymized market trends, user needs, and competitive insights. Business Models: General exploitation strategies and frameworks for sustainable approaches. Impact and Sustainability Metrics: Benchmarks for evaluating long-term project viability.</p> <p>Ingartek reserves the right to publish public information and project results on our website to enhance transparency and dissemination in accordance with the Consortium Agreement (CA).</p>
<p>How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?</p>	<p>Open data, such as publications, reports, and project documentation, will be accessible through secure and trusted repositories like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website to ensure wide dissemination and easy access. For internal use, non-public data will be stored and managed through Microsoft SharePoint, which ensures secure and controlled access within the consortium.</p>
<p>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?</p>	<p>The data, along with associated metadata and documentation, will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint for internal use and compliance management. For publicly shareable data, trusted repositories like Zenodo or other platforms aligned with EU Open Data policies will be used.</p> <p>Ingartek also reserves the right to post public information and project results directly on the project website to increase visibility and accessibility. As Ingartek is not involved in code development, there will be no code to deposit.</p>
<p>Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.</p>	<p>Ingartek has reviewed the requirements for depositing data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo, which ensures compliance with EU data management and FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). This involves establishing metadata standards, verifying compliance with GDPR, determining which datasets can be shared publicly and ensuring proper access credential verification where applicable.</p>
<p>What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?</p>	<p>For internal data, Microsoft SharePoint will be used for secure storage and management. For publicly accessible data, common web-based platforms like Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository (Pilot), and the project website will be sufficient. If any technical datasets are produced, generic ofimatic software will be sufficient to access the data.</p>
<p>Will there be any restrictions on data access?<i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i></p>	<p>Due to the nature of Ingartek’s work, the following data access restrictions will be applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal/contractual restrictions: no personal contact details will be published, unless express consent is obtained. The adequacy of personal contact detail access by other consortium members will be reviewed in a case by case basis to ensure legal compliance. • Intentional Restrictions: no intentional restrictions are expected at this stage.
<p>What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?</p>	<p>For the data generated and collected by Ingartek to be properly read and interpreted both during and after the project, the following information will need to be retained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextual information: references to relevant legislation and standards will be kept, as well as detailed explanations of any assumptions and hypothesis used in the data analysis. • Methodology: Clear documentation of how data was collected, processed, and analysed, including the

	<p>questionnaires and electronic submissions used to gather information from partners. This will provide transparency into how compliance practices and policies were assessed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata: Information about the source of the data, collection dates, version control, and any updates made during the project. This will be essential for understanding the data's context and ensuring that any updates or changes are tracked and traceable.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	<p>In compliance with GDPR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data: Project publications and reports will be available following the project's final reporting. Metadata for these outputs will be maintained even after the data itself is no longer accessible to ensure traceability and reuse. • Internal data: Internal documentation and non-public records will follow the project's data retention policy, typically for five years after the final reporting of the project, with metadata retained for long-term archival purposes.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	<p>Yes, metadata will be made openly available, and licensed under a public domain dedication (CC0) to ensure it can be freely accessed and reused. The metadata will include essential information, such as descriptions and access conditions, to enable users to find and use the data appropriately.</p>
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	<p>Oversight of the correct execution of the access process will be provided by the Law and Internet Foundation (LIF) in its capacity as the Legal and Ethical lead. LIF will work closely with the iDriving project coordinator and relevant partners to ensure that all data access procedures comply with legal, ethical, and privacy regulations. Any access to sensitive or restricted data will be carefully monitored to ensure compliance with the project's legal and ethical standards.</p>
How will you handle requests for data access?	<p>Requests for data access will be handled through an official request system, managed via email where applicants will need to submit their credentials and purpose for data access. Sensitive data will require appropriate approvals.</p>
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	<p>For internal SharePoint access, identity verification will be managed via Microsoft authentication. For external repository access, identity verification will depend on the repository's policies (e.g., login credentials, and institutional affiliations).</p>

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	Where applicable, we will use standard legal and compliance vocabularies to enhance the clarity and interoperability of our outputs, making them easier to use and understand for a broader audience, including stakeholders and future researchers. Ingartek will adhere to the Dublin Core Metadata Standards where practical, to provide a clear and consistent framework for describing different types of content.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes, we will use standard vocabularies where applicable.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Although not expected, if necessary Ingartek will create glossaries for any terms that are deemed non standard and include them in the relevant documents. These glossaries, when part of publicly published documents, will be allowed to be reused, refined and extended.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Ingartek does not expect to produce technical data that would require machine-readable formatting, but if that were the case adequate machine-readable formats will be chosen to make the appropriate data available.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	<p>Standardization Documentation: Guidelines, best practices, and meeting notes with standardization bodies to aid interoperability.</p> <p>Collaboration Data: Aggregated insights from partnerships (e.g., C-Roads, C-Mobile) and stakeholder feedback for network-building.</p> <p>Market Analysis Data: Anonymized market trends, user needs, and competitive insights.</p> <p>Business Models: General exploitation strategies and frameworks for sustainable approaches.</p> <p>Impact and Sustainability Metrics: Benchmarks for evaluating long-term project viability.</p>
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes, legal research data that does not contain personal or sensitive information will be made freely available in the public domain, adhering to open data principles. However, sensitive and operational data will not be publicly available to protect confidentiality and security.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, we will provide readme files, methodology documentation, and any necessary codebooks, where it is appropriate given the context, alongside the re-usable data to ensure proper understanding and validation of the data analysis. This will include details on data structure, sources, and any processing steps taken.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardization organisms: standardization documents, guidelines and best practices. • Other research projects: aggregated insights of partnerships and stakeholder feedback. • Transport authorities and policy makers: anonymized market analysis data like market trends, user needs and competitive insights.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies in the transport and automotive sector: general business models and frameworks.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Sensitive or personal data will have stricter restrictions, limiting access to authorised personnel or organisations, with a clear legal basis and ethical guidelines governing its use. These restrictions will remain for as long as necessary to protect privacy and comply with GDPR. Sensitive data will be shared with the Consortium only on a need-to-know basis.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	Data, including publications and academic papers authored by the LIF team, will be made available for re-use immediately after major project milestones are achieved or at the end of the project, depending on the output type. For academic papers, availability will depend on the publication timelines and any embargo periods imposed by journals or publishers, typically ranging from 6 to 12 months. This ensures that all documentation is finalised and fully compliant with legal and academic standards before being openly shared.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	Data will remain re-usable for a minimum of 5 years after the project ends, in alignment with EU open data policies. This timeframe allows for adequate re-use and sharing of the project's outcomes.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes, re-usable data will be licensed under an open license such as CC-BY 4.0 ensuring that users can freely share, adapt, and re-use the data as long as they provide appropriate credit to the original source. Sensitive data, if shared at all, will have more restrictive licenses to ensure compliance with GDPR and security protocols.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Breach of our IT systems.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	No formal risk assessment has been completed, but industry-standard security measures will be applied.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Access controls, and standard IT security measures are in place.

Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	No, encryption will not be applied to the data.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No.
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Automatic backups of our CRM software and within third party storage.
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	Incidents would be handled in a case-by-case basis.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	Data will only be retained for the duration of the project, although this may be extended to comply with any regulatory obligations.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Our CRM software and third party storage.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	Project manager based on regulatory requirements and project needs.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	No long term retention is expected at this time.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	Data will be deleted if required as part of the project closure meeting.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Third party storage solutions by Google and/or AWS will be used for any files produced.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:

- Personal data;
- Data on criminal convictions and offences;
- Operational data for LEAs;
- Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection;
- Classified information on national and/or international grounds;
- Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret).

Please answer as comprehensively as possible.

Personal data: Yes (contact details of stakeholders)

If any of the categories of non- personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.

N/A

<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>We will rely on legitimate interests (GDPR Article 6(1)(f)) for processing personal data, such as contact details of stakeholders. This processing is necessary to fulfil our project tasks related to communication, collaboration, and market analysis, and does not override the fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Where applicable, explicit consent (GDPR Article 6(1)(a)) will be obtained for personal data.</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>Yes, explicit consent will be obtained when applicable.</p>
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>We do not intend to process any sensitive personal data as outlined in GDPR Article 9. If this changes, we will ensure that we rely on explicit consent (Article 9(2)(a)).</p>
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	<p>We do not plan to process any data related to criminal convictions or offences.</p>
<p>Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?</p>	<p>No, we do not anticipate processing personal data from children or vulnerable groups as part of this project.</p>
<p>How will you protect the identity of the project participants?</p>	<p>We will implement encryption and access control measures to protect the confidentiality and identity of project participants, if necessary.</p>
<p>Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?</p>	<p>No, personal data sharing is not expected at this time.</p>
<p>Will you engage in big data processing?</p>	<p>No, we do not plan to engage in big data processing as part of this project.</p>
<p>Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?</p>	<p>No, our data processing will not involve personal profiling, and the results will not be used for profiling or social scoring.</p>

Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	No significant adverse effects are anticipated, as we are primarily processing basic contact information. Data is handled in compliance with GDPR, with appropriate safeguards to protect the rights and freedoms of data subjects.
Will you engage in web scraping?	No, web scraping is not expected at this time.
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	No, there are no plans to transfer personal data outside of the EU during the project.
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Yes, pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques will be used for personal data where required. Personal identifiers will be replaced with pseudonyms or removed entirely, and sensitive data will be anonymised wherever possible to ensure privacy protection.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Yes, we will conduct a data minimisation review to ensure that only the data strictly necessary for achieving the project's objectives is collected and processed.
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	No data sharing is expected for this project.
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No additional legal or ethical issues are foreseen at this time.
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	Ingartek is not required to appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO) under GDPR, as the organization does not engage in large-scale processing of sensitive data, regular and systematic monitoring of individuals, or function as a public authority. However, any GDPR-related concerns may be addressed by the project manager, who will consult with external legal counsel if necessary.

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	Ingartek has allocated human resources for data management, primarily through project team members responsible for overseeing data collection, storage, and protection. Additionally, technical resources such as CRM software are used to securely store and manage data. No specific financial resources are dedicated solely to data management, as existing tools and personnel are used for this purpose.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	No extra costs are anticipated for making the project data FAIR, as the necessary systems (CRM) and practices are already in place.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	No, no additional fees associated with the storage of data are expected.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No service fees are expected for specialist assistance, as existing tools and personnel within the organization will manage the data.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	No significant additional costs are anticipated. The data will be stored and managed using existing tools, with minimal time and effort required for preparation and preservation, as data sharing is not expected.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
------	-------------------------	----------------------------	---------------------------------	--	--	--

T7.2	Contact information, stakeholder interactions, technical specifications, market trends.	To communicate with stakeholders, analyze the market, support standardization processes, and collect market study insights.	Consortium members, stakeholders, market surveys, and standardization bodies.	No.	No, the data is primarily project-specific and not intended for external use.	Industry standard security systems.
T7.4	Market trends and stakeholder interactions.	To analyse market trends and generate business models.	Market analysis and stakeholder consultations.	No.	No, the data is primarily project-specific and not intended for external use.	Industry standard security systems.

7.3.15 TEKNIKER

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	FUNDACIÓN TEKNIKER
Team	Susana Ferreiro; Joseba Izaguirre
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? (Deliverables are not included in this question)	<p>Data collected: As responsible for WP3 we consider the collection and processing of data, personal or otherwise, to be part of the responsibility of the respective partner and Tekniker is only responsible for providing the necessary data space connection and interoperability mechanisms to facilitate communication and data exchange. As such, this involves only the use of <u>meta-data</u> related to the data sharing policies (e.g. authorization, denial) of processed events between the tools and systems provided by the consortium partners and the technical data, that encompasses operational vehicle data, infrastructure sensor data, maintenance data, and environmental data (also provided by iDriving partners).</p> <p>Regarding T4.2 and the data that will be used for that task, we consider that some may be of a personal nature like GPS location data for drivers and road users, user-provided information on road conditions or behavioral data related to driving patterns. However, identifiable images are not considered as raw input for the developed algorithms; we will consider the results obtained after these images are already processed by other consortium members. As far as non-personal data is concerned, we might consider aggregated traffic flow, road conditions, environmental factors, and operational details from UAV path planning and resource allocation.</p> <p>Data generated/produced: This consists of analytical data and events, which will be derived from data collected. This includes anomaly events, trends, patterns and statistics generated by the algorithms. Also, Interoperability and Shareability data, ontologies designed for easy sharing and integrated across different systems within iDriving project.</p> <p>In addition, we specify that the algorithms to be developed in this R&D project and the results obtained from them do not contemplate the possibility of personal identification. That part may be reserved for a later phase involving the deployment of such algorithms and only for the purpose of increasing security measures.</p>
Will you re-use any data?	Open-source datasets could be used.

<p>What is the origin of the data? (<i>Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.</i>)</p>	<p>Data collected is mainly data coming from other consortium partners. It could be also obtained from public services, like weather data, or open-source and public datasets. iDriving partners are expected to contribute data collected from their acquisition and monitoring systems.</p> <p>Data generated/produced is mainly Analytical data that will be generated by ML algorithms from Data collected. And Interoperability and Shareability data, ontologies that will be created to facilitate information sharing among iDriving partners.</p>
<p>What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?</p>	<p>Technical information is necessary to feed and train data-driven models aimed at anomaly detection and the development of predictive maintenance algorithms. Technical information is crucial for the project.</p> <p>Analytical data is the foundation for generating the alert system aimed at serving end users.</p> <p>Interoperability and Shareability Data is necessary for all iDriving systems to share information and communicate with each other in a standardized a control way and to ensure seamless collaboration among different stakeholders.</p>
<p>If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?</p>	<p>Open-source datasets, if available, to develop analytical models in case no additional data is obtained from iDriving partners during the project.</p>
<p>How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?</p>	<p>The data will come from different iDriving partners in the format determined during the project and partners, and the volume will be set by them, aiming for simple formats like .csv, .json or .mpeg-4.</p>
<p>How will you trace the collected data? (<i>For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data</i>)</p>	<p>Each data point will have metadata, including date and time of collection, sensor type, and source. And unique identifiers (UUIDs) will be assigned to each dataset to ensure traceability from collection to analysis.</p>
<p>Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?</p>	<p>Yes. Analytical data will be reproducible using version control and the development of pipelines that follow a workflow where each stage is well-defined (data cleaning, data transformation, data analysis). Reproducible environments can also be implemented using Docker containers.</p>
<p>Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualise the data?</p>	<p>Yes. Machine learning software like python libraries (e.g., TensorFlow, Scikit-Learn), data management software (e.g., databases for storing data) and data visualization tools (e.g., Tableau, Grafana, Tkinter) to create dashboards for visualizing and presenting results.</p>
<p>Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? (<i>Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-</i></p>	<p>Tekniker has internal procedures for handling personal data and for managing the protection and security of information in ICTs.</p>

<i>personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departamental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	The data will be stored on secure internal or cloud servers that comply with security regulations. This will determine during the execution among the iDriving partners (those who have the data and those who use it).
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	No.

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	For the project and dataset identification, we will assign persistent unique identifiers (UUIDs) for all datasets to ensure traceability and uniqueness throughout the project lifecycle.
What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	For internal datasets, UUIDs will be used for traceability purposes.
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	<p>A structured and consistent naming convention will be followed to facilitate data management, which includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of data (e.g., OP for operational vehicle data, IS for infrastructure sensor data) • Collection date in YYYYMMDD format. • Version number of the dataset. • Location or specific source of data if applicable. <p>For example, a file name could be: OP_20240401_v1_Bilbao.csv. This convention ensures that each file is unique, easily identifiable, and searchable.</p> <p>In any case, it will be determined among the project members.</p>

Will you provide clear version numbers?	Yes, version numbers will be assigned to all datasets. The convention used will be vX.Y, where X indicates a major change (e.g., new data collection campaign) and Y represents minor updates (e.g., data cleaning or processing adjustments). This will facilitate tracking changes and maintaining an orderly version history for the data.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for discovery and re-use?	Yes
What metadata will be created? How? (Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)	Metadata must be agreed among iDriving partners, as they are part of the interoperability, and could include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic descriptors: dataset title, description, creation date, data type. • Technical information: sensor type, data collection frequency, geographical location, and data formats. • Administrative metadata: contributors, project reference, version number. • Provenance: source of the data, data quality, and methods used for data collection.
What standards will you apply for the integration of metadata?	It will be determined by iDriving partners during the project.
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	No.

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorised users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Error! Reference source not found. **[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]**

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	This will need to be determined by the iDriving partners who own the data. In the case of Analytical Data generated by Tekniker, there are no plans to make the data accessible, unless required between consortium members. Interoperability and Sharing data, along with the generated ontologies, will be available in OWL (Web Ontology Language) format, allowing further extension and use by others in the community.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	Access to restricted datasets will be managed through a secure repository with defined access control policies, requiring authorization for data access.
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	In Tekniker’s secure cloud infrastructure, which complies with relevant data protection regulations.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted	No.

repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	For restricted data, users will need to authenticate via an institutional VPN or use specific tools.
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	For the Collected Data, the restrictions will be established by the consortium members who own the data. For the Generated/produced Data, access to the Analytical data will be for consortium members only, while the ontologies will be made public so other developers can use and extend them in the future.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Some metadatata and documentation.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	TBD
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	No.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	IT staff at Tekniker.
How will you handle requests for data access?	For Analytical Data, interested parties must complete a data access form detailing their research objectives and planned use of the data. Tekniker will review each request to ensure compliance with ethical and legal standards before granting access.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	TBD

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Error! Reference source not found. [standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	Yes. TBD during the project.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	No.
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes. Openly publish them under a Creative Commons license (CC BY 4.0) to allow others to reuse, refine, and extend them but not commercialized.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes, all data generated or collected during the project will be made available in machine-readable formats to ensure ease of reuse and interoperability as tabular data or .JSON format.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes, licensed under Creative Commons CC BY-NC 4.0
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, providing documentation to ensure data reusability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • README files that explain the data collection methodology, data structure, and specific instructions for use. • Jupyter Notebooks or similar documentation detailing the data analysis pipeline, including the code used to process and analyze the data.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Members of the consortium and companies like them. Academic researchers in the fields of machine learning, transport engineering, and urban planning could use the data to improve algorithms for anomaly detection, optimize road safety measures, and develop predictive models.

Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Yes.
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	TBD
For what period will data remain re-usable?	TBD
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CCO)?	Yes. Creative Commons CC BY-NC 4.0

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	Unauthorized Access.
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	Yes. Mitigated using authentication measures and role-based access control.
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	Technical Measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong passwords are required, and two-factor authentication is enforced for all data access. • A combination of firewalls and anti-virus programs are employed to prevent unauthorized access and mitigate cyber threats. Organizational Measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access Control, restricting access to data to only those personnel required for specific tasks.
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	No.
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	No.

What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	Backups on secure cloud servers to prevent data loss.
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	No.
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	Yes. TBD.
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	Server or cloud within the Tekniker infrastructure.
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	The PI of the project, along with the agreement of the other team members and IT staff.
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	IT personnel.
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	Tekniker will not create data with personal information. Other consortium members must set the rules for the data they collect and share.
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	No.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Personal data: GPS location data, user-provided information on road conditions and behavioral data related to driving patterns.</p>
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>TEKNIKER intends to rely on Legitimate Interest (Article 6(1)(f) of the GDPR) as the lawful basis for processing personal data.</p>
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	<p>As part of our role in the iDriving project, TEKNIKER won't be collecting directly any personal data. Because of this, there's no need to obtain explicit consent from data subjects.</p>

<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	<p>The algorithms to be developed in this R&D project with such data and the results obtained from them do not contemplate the possibility of personal identification. That part may be reserved for a later phase involving the deployment of such algorithms – maybe with the the purpose of increasing security measures – but this is off the limits of the project results.</p>
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>How will you protect the identity of the project participants?</p>	<p>TEKNIKER will use pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques *if needed* to protect the identities of project participants (e.g. omit any names from public deliverables). These methods will ensure that personal identifiers are not accessible to unauthorised individuals, and only key personnel will have access to the identification codes.</p>
<p>Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?</p>	<p>TEKNIKER will not share personal data with consortium partners. However, contact details of TEKNIKER personnel related to the iDriving project will be shared when necessary for project coordination.</p>
<p>Will you engage in big data processing?</p>	<p>No, TEKNIKER will not engage in big data processing.</p>
<p>Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?</p>	<p>No, TEKNIKER does not engage in personal profiling.</p>
<p>Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?</p>	<p>No adverse effects are anticipated for data subjects, as TEKNIKER will process personal data strictly within legal and ethical boundaries, ensuring that privacy and data protection rights are fully respected.</p>
<p>Will you engage in web scraping?</p>	<p>No, TEKNIKER will not engage in web scraping.</p>
<p>Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If</p>	<p>TEKNIKER does not plan to engage in data transfers outside the EU.</p>

yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	Tekniker does not envisage the need to use pseudo- or anonymisation techniques as not does not plan to process any personal or sensitive data. However TEKNIKER will reevaluate along the project and *If needed* will use these techniques: Personal identifiers will be replaced with pseudonyms or removed entirely, and sensitive data will be anonymised wherever possible to ensure privacy protection.
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	Yes, we will conduct a data minimisation review to ensure that only the data strictly necessary for achieving the project's objectives is collected and processed.
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	N/A
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	No additional legal or ethical issues are currently foreseen. However, TEKNIKER will remain vigilant and ensure ongoing compliance with all relevant regulations and ethical guidelines as the project progresses.
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	TEKNIKER does not have a designated Data Protection Officer (DPO); Any contact will be done though our TEKNIKER project coordinator.

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data	Financial Resources: a dedicated budget for data management activities, and costs for cloud storage services. Human Resources: data engineers, machine learning specialists and research assistants. Technical Resources: servers and storage infrastructure, software for data management and analysis.

management within your organisation?	
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	No.
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	Cloud Storage Costs: cloud-based storage services for storing data. These fees are included in the project's financial planning.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	No.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	Significant time and effort costs are expected for data curation, cleaning, metadata creation, and required documentation. A team equivalent to one or two full-time positions will be needed for several months, depending on the volume and complexity of the data.

Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T3.1	Relevant information related to the application domain.	Necessary to develop structured representations of knowledge and concepts in the project domain.	From sources within the consortium and previous research.	Yes.	Yes. No reasons not to share.	N/A
T4.2	Technical data provided through tools developed by consortium partners (e.g., sensor readings, traffic patterns, environmental conditions,	This data is essential for detecting and anticipating dangerous situations to prevent incidents.	The data will be sourced from consortium members.	Yes.	Yes, the data could be beneficial for external stakeholders, such as traffic management agencies or urban planners. Not reasons not to share.	Access controls, along with organizational measures such as confidentiality agreements among consortium members.

	historical data, etc.)					
T5.4	Technical data and Analytical Data provided through tools developed by consortium partners (e.g., maintenance history, operational protocols, records of past incidents or failures, maintenance costs, and predictive models)	Needed to develop the dynamic risk management systems that optimizes maintenance based on risk, cost, and health condition modelling.	The data will be sourced from consortium members.	Yes.	Yes, the data could be valuable for external stakeholders, such as maintenance service providers and regulatory bodies. Not reasons not to share.	Secure access protocols, and monitoring, along with organizational measures such as confidentiality agreements and compliance with data protection regulations.
T6.2	Technical data provided through tools developed by consortium partners. Operational or personal data in case of request for permissions and for trial workshop arrangement and organization	Data is needed to setup and host de trial UC3.2 of the iDriving project.	From consortium partners	Yes, as part of the development and testing activities, and results and information visualized as part of the trial execution	Yes, it can be useful but not specific details or technical data used for the trial, but the consortium decides to show during the trial execution.	Every partner involved should individually apply their protection measures. TEK as the partner hosting the trial execution will provide specific measures at their facilities to ensure proper management of any data (technical or personal) involved in the trial,

7.3.16 Thessaloniki

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS (THESSALONIKI)
Team	Dr. Georgios Papastergios, Mr. Charistes Christantonis, Mrs. Vassiliki Paschalidou, Mrs. Maria Varthi
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	Environmental Data, Air Pollution Data, Meteorological Data, Traffic Data
Will you re-use any data?	Cannot answer this question, yet
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	Projects and other activities of the Municipality of Thessaloniki,
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	Support our use case
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	Data will be collected from various applications. Formats to be expected vary (i.e., csv, excel, pdf, images, shp, other)
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	Yes
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	The Municipality has a Data Protection Officer. We consult him for such issues.
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	No, to the best of our knowledge

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	
Will you provide clear version numbers?	
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	
What metadata will be created? How? (<i>Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.</i>)	
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
<i>Error! Reference source not found.</i> [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	We shall consult this with our DPO and appropriate partners of the consortium, when needed.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	

What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	
How will you handle requests for data access?	
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Error! Reference source not found. **[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]**

Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to

facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Error! Reference source not found. [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	
For what period will data remain re-usable?	

Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Error! Reference source not found. [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long	

should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

Error! Reference source not found. [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]

Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; 	NO
--	----

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?</p>	

Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	
Will you engage in big data processing?	
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	
Will you engage in web scraping?	
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	

Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	A Data Protection Officer is employed by the Municipality of Thessaloniki.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Possibly no
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	Possibly no

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	Possibly no
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	

7.3.17 ALBA JULIA

Data collection tables

General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	[Alba Iulia Municipality]
Team	[insert here the name representative(s) responsible for completing this document" - Alba Iulia Team]
[data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? <i>(Deliverables are not included in this question)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data about public transport/buses, with dedicated module - it also allows the collection of statistical data, such as no. of passengers - data on public transport/bicycle mobility, with dedicated module - no. of users, routes, no. of bicycles in use/free - data on general vehicle traffic - optimization of traffic flows, on the main streets in the city, time traveled by cyclists, routes, distances
Will you re-use any data?	- video cameras - data showing whether the lines dedicated to public transport are being used properly
What is the origin of the data? <i>(Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data about public transport - buses and bicycles: intelligent system integrated on the vehicles, communicating with the traffic management centre - data on general traffic: video cameras
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	- all data type: efficiency of routes, development of transport facilities, traffic safety, optimization of the application dedicated to cyclists
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	- screenshots, real time images, graphics and statistics
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
How will you trace the collected data? <i>(For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data)</i>	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	software used for communication between vehicles (buses and bicycles) and the traffic management centre
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	Yes. We have data management procedures for personal data, compliant with: EU regulation 2016/679, EU directive 2016/680, EC directive 2002/58, EC directive 31/2000, CEDP Guide 3/2019 National law 102/2005 National law 190/2018 National law 363/2018
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	no

Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
[digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	according to our internal procedures for data and documents archiving
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	according to our internal procedures for file management
Will you provide clear version numbers?	yes
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	yes
What metadata will be created? How? (<i>Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.</i>)	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage

Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
[openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	The data that will be available openly includes anonymized datasets related to smart city solutions, public transport systems, and non-sensitive environmental data. Personal data will not be openly shared to comply with privacy regulations.
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	The data will be accessible through deposition in a trusted, open-access data repository, such as Zenodo or a similar platform compliant with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	The data, along with associated metadata, documentation, and code, will be deposited in a dedicated project repository, integrated with a publicly accessible repository, ensuring secure long-term storage and access.
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted	Yes, the team has assessed the requirements for depositing data in trusted repositories, ensuring compatibility with repository standards for metadata, data formats, and access controls. Legal and ethical reviews have also been conducted to ensure compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations.

repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	Authorized users will need access to standard data retrieval software, such as APIs, web browsers, and potentially specialized data analysis tools
Will there be any restrictions on data access? <i>If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).</i>	Yes, there will be restrictions on accessing personal or sensitive data due to GDPR and contractual obligations. Personal data will be anonymized, and some proprietary data may be restricted due to intellectual property rights and data-sharing agreements with stakeholders.
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	Yes, there will be restrictions on accessing personal or sensitive data due to GDPR and contractual obligations. Personal data will be anonymized, and some proprietary data may be restricted due to intellectual property rights and data-sharing agreements with stakeholders.
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	The data will remain available and findable for at least 5 years after the project ends. Metadata will remain available indefinitely, even after the data itself is no longer accessible, ensuring that potential users can still understand and evaluate the project's findings.
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CCO? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata will be made openly available under a CCO public domain dedication, ensuring that it contains all necessary information to allow users to locate and access the relevant data.
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	IT Department and management team at the Municipality of Alba Iulia will oversee the access process, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and best practices.
How will you handle requests for data access?	Requests for data access will be handled through a formal process, where users must submit a written request detailing their intended use of the data. The team will review requests based on the nature of the data and the requester's credentials.
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	The identity of individuals requesting data access will be verified through institutional or governmental identification, such as academic or organizational credentials, or a secure login process tied to verified user accounts within the repository.

Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

[standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	Yes, the team will follow recognized standards such as Dublin Core for metadata, ISO 19115 for geographic information, and W3C standards for data sharing to ensure interoperability with other datasets and systems.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	Yes, standard vocabularies
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	Yes, any project-specific vocabulary or ontology developed will be openly published in a trusted repository, allowing others to reuse, refine, or extend them under an open license.
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	Yes, all data will be made available in machine-readable formats such as CSV, or XML to ensure easy reuse and integration with other systems and platforms.

Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
[embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? <i>Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.</i>	Yes, data such as anonymized smart city data, non-sensitive environmental data, and public transport data will be reusable and openly shareable. Personal or sensitive data will not be reusable due to privacy restrictions.
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	Yes, the reusable data will be made freely available in the public domain to allow the widest possible reuse.
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	Yes, documentation such as readme files, methodology descriptions, and codebooks will be provided to ensure proper validation and facilitate data reuse.
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	Potential groups include academic researchers, urban planners, smart city developers, public transport authorities, and policy makers interested in sustainable city solutions.
Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	Restrictions apply only to personal or sensitive data, which will not be reusable. For all other data, there will be no restrictions on reuse for any lawful purpose, and it will be available indefinitely.

When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	The data will be made available for reuse immediately after project completion. There are no embargo periods.
For what period will data remain re-usable?	The data will remain reusable for at least 10 years following the end of the project.
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	Yes, the data will be licensed for reuse under the CC0 public domain dedication, ensuring it can be freely reused without restrictions.

Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
[risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	informatic breach (low-medium possibility)
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	according to our internal risk management procedures and standards
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	technical: passwords, admin/ user accounts on computers organisational: office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	no
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	no
What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data	according to our internal risk management procedures and standards

breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	according to the national regulations about data and documents archiving
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	yes, there are institutional date archives
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	the traffic management centre officer in collaboration with the public transport company
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	the Municipality and the public transport operator (company)
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	according to our internal GDPR procedures and standards, which are compliant with EU and national regulations
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	Yes, a third party will be involved in data management and storage. A possible solution is the involvement of a trusted cloud service provider, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) or Microsoft Azure, which will be responsible for securely storing the data. They will handle anonymized and non-sensitive data categories, such as environmental data and data related to smart city solutions and public transport. Personal or sensitive data will remain under the direct control of the Alba Iulia Municipality team, being stored locally or on protected servers that comply with GDPR regulations.

Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS	
<i>To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer</i>	
[personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]	
Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:	- personal data will be collected in compliance with the GDPR regulation and national law

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal data; ● Data on criminal convictions and offences; ● Operational data for LEAs; ● Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; ● Classified information on national and/or international grounds; ● Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	NA
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	Citizens will be informed about the use of the traffic management tools. Where explicit consent collection is possible, it will be required (eg: for using an app dedicated to public bikes, or other traffic management tools dedicated to end users).
<p>If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?</p>	j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest
<p>If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR,</p>	NA

how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	no
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	anonymisation of recognizable data
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	according to the partnership agreement and the project plan
Will you engage in big data processing?	no
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	no
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	no
Will you engage in web scraping?	no
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	no
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage

any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	yes
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	information to be provided when the traffic management centre of the city is in a more advanced setup stage
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	no
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	Ioan CANTIMIR: ioan.cantimir@apulum.ro

Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data management within your organisation?	The Municipality of Alba Iulia has allocated financial resources for data management, including funding for storage infrastructure and security measures. Human resources include a dedicated data management team consisting of IT specialists and data protection officers. Technical resources involve secure servers, cloud services, and data management tools to ensure proper handling of project data.
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	Yes, additional costs may arise for ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles, including data formatting and repository fees. These costs will be covered (as far as possible) by the project's allocated budget for data management and technical infrastructure.

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	Yes, there may be fees for storing data in dedicated repositories, such as cloud storage services or specialized data platforms. These fees will be covered (as far as possible) by the project's budget for IT services and infrastructure.
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	Yes, service fees for specialists may be required for repository maintenance, data security, and technical support. These fees will also be covered (as far as possible) by the allocated project budget.
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	The anticipated costs include the time and effort needed for data cleaning, anonymization, documentation (e.g., metadata creation), and uploading to repositories. These efforts will involve IT personnel and data managers, with costs accounted for in project staffing and operational budgets.

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

Funded by the European Union

The Project "iDriving - Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies" has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147004.